

Public Health Emergency Preparedness Playbook

LESSONS FROM THE RADx-UP COVID-19 INITIATIVE
JUNE 2025

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The COVID-19 pandemic exposed deep-rooted health disparities in the U.S., disproportionately affecting communities with limited healthcare services or access. In response, the National Institutes of Health (NIH) launched the Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics — Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) initiative to address inequities in access to testing, treatment, and reliable public health information. With no existing roadmap to ensure equitable testing, data collection, or community engagement during emergencies, the Public Health Emergency Preparedness Playbook fills that gap.

The playbook is a collection of best practices, insights, and tangible resources drawn from the lessons learned by the RADx-UP program to address future public health emergencies. Designed to serve as a roadmap for health practitioners, community organizations, policymakers, and researchers working to reduce negative health impacts in underserved communities, the playbook was created to establish lasting frameworks for health equity.

The playbook demonstrates how the 137 RADx-UP research projects and the RADx-UP Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC) enhanced understanding of effective virus testing strategies and improved community engagement in clinical research.

PLAYBOOK AT A GLANCE

- ✓ 27 Guides and Manuals
- ✓ 21 Training Resources & Templates
- ✓ 20 Articles
- ✓ 13 Assessment & Evaluation Tools
- ✓ 35 Case Studies
- ✓ 62 Videos & Presentations
- ✓ 66 References & Resources
- ✓ 5 Dissemination Resources

Key Recommendations from this Playbook Include:

- **Build and Sustain Communities of Practice (CoPs):** Develop robust networks that foster trust, collaboration, and knowledge sharing through regular engagement, digital tools, and inclusive leadership.
- **Center Community Voices in Research and Data:** Collaborate with communities to design research tools, data practices, and evaluation strategies that are culturally relevant, transparent, and respect data sovereignty.
- **Ensure Equitable Access to Testing and Care:** Remove barriers by implementing community-led solutions like mobile testing, multilingual education, peer outreach, and partnerships with trusted institutions.
- **Communicate Effectively and Combat Misinformation:** Use culturally relevant messaging, trusted messengers, and plain language materials to build public understanding and trust during emergencies.
- **Plan for Long-Term Impact and Sustainability:** Invest in local solutions, align funding with community priorities, and integrate sustainability and policy relevance from the start of any emergency response effort.

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ACRONYMS

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CBPR	Community-Based Participatory Research
CCPH	Community-Campus Partnerships for Health
CDCC	Coordination and Data Collection Center
CDE	Common Data Element
CEC	Community Engagement Core
CEnR	Community-Engaged Research
CHW	Community Health Worker
CoP	Community of Practice
C2G	Community Collaboration Grant
DCRI	Duke Clinical Research Institute
EIT	Engagement Impact Team
ERC	Engagement Resource Center
GMB	Group Model Building
PHE	Public Health Emergency
P4I	Partnering for Impact
RADx-UP	Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics – Underserved Populations
RP2	Rapid Research Pilot Program
SDOH	Social Determinants of Health
SEBI	Social, Ethical, and Behavioral Implications
UNC	University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

INTRODUCTION

Community Engagement as the Foundation for Data and Discovery

A key lesson from RADx-UP is that effective interventions rely on trustworthiness and trust and engaging communities to support reliable data collection. RADx-UP integrated community engagement at every stage—from creating common data elements (CDEs) to adapting study protocols based on local input. This approach led to more inclusive participation, better data accuracy, and clear communication of how findings were shared. The RADx-UP CDCC established a shared infrastructure to combine and share diverse datasets across the consortium. Ultimately, the playbook uses these findings to guide scientific research and local decision-making.

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UNDERSERVED POPULATIONS

The NIH definition of underserved populations includes medically and/or socially vulnerable populations:

- residents of nursing homes and assisted living facilities;
- community-dwelling older adults;
- individuals with intellectual, developmental, sensory, or physical disabilities, cognitive impairment or dementia, or communication disorders;
- homeless populations;
- individuals involved with the criminal or juvenile justice systems (incarcerated or under community supervision);
- individuals with medical comorbidities known to increase risk of severe COVID-19, including heart failure and related cardiovascular conditions, diabetes mellitus, chronic lung disease, obesity, HIV/AIDS;
- pregnant and post-partum women;
- children and adolescents;
- individuals living in congregate housing such as shelters or residential treatment facilities;
- individuals in overcrowded housing;
- individuals with substance use disorders or serious mental illness;
- migrant and immigrant populations;
- residents of tribal lands or reservations;
- communities exposed to high rates of air pollution or other toxic exposures; and
- rural and remote communities.

Evolution of the COVID-19 Pandemic

In the early days of the pandemic, widespread virus testing was essential as cases surged and millions were infected, with underserved communities suffering disproportionately. By the end of 2020, the U.S. recorded over 7 million confirmed cases and more than 367,000 deaths, highlighting significant inequities.

As diagnostic tests became available in 2020, procuring and distributing them was the top priority. When vaccines became available, and vaccination efforts ramped up in 2021, focus shifted to include providing accurate vaccine information and access.

The unprecedented global pandemic magnified existing health disparities across the U.S., underscoring the nationwide health crisis and the need for the RADx-UP initiative (Webb Hooper et al., 2020. COVID-19 and Racial/Ethnic Disparities. JAMA. 2020;323(24):2466-2467).

Program Structure and Phases

The RADx initiative was a billion-dollar Congressional allocation, with RADx-UP comprising \$400-500 million and the CDCC \$80 million. RADx-UP was one of four [RADx programs](#) to speed innovation in developing, commercializing, and implementing technologies for COVID-19 testing.

The other three programs were:

- **The RADx Tech** initiative aimed to speed the development, validation, and commercialization of innovative point-of-care and home-based tests and improve clinical laboratory tests that could directly detect the virus.
- **RADx[®] Radical (RADx-rad)** supported new, non-traditional approaches, including rapid detection devices and home-based testing technologies, that addressed gaps in COVID-19 testing, including new or non-traditional applications of existing approaches to make them more usable, accessible, or accurate.
- **The RADx[®] Advanced Technology Platforms (RADx-ATP)** program sought to increase testing capacity and throughput by identifying existing and late-stage testing platforms for COVID-19 that were far enough advanced to achieve rapid scale-up or expanded geographical placement in a short amount of time or by scaling up technologies.

INTRODUCTION

The RADx-UP consortium was a network of more than 137 community-engaged research (CEnR) project teams across the U.S., its territories, and Tribal Nations, along with the NIH RADx-UP CDCC. Each of the 137 NIH-funded research testing projects partnered with trusted community organizations, faith-based groups, and/or local leaders to effectively foster receptive environments for testing.

The NIH funding cycles evolved along with the pandemic. Phase I focused on understanding testing patterns and implementing strategies to increase accessibility. Phase II expanded on technological advances in testing and began integrating school-based research. Phase III evaluated rapid testing interventions, focusing on community initiatives. Phase IV involved analyzing cross-site data and disseminating findings to inform ongoing health equity initiatives (See **Figure 0.1**).

The research projects committed to collecting CDEs to assess the social, ethical, and behavioral barriers to COVID-19 testing. RADx-UP collected and collated these data across the consortium to understand trends, shared the data, and published findings, utilizing a CEnR approach, resulting in unprecedented participation and collection of scientific data that provides lessons learned for future public health emergencies. Overall, community members in underserved populations who participated in the study are responsible for the success of RADx-UP in terms of scope, reach, and sheer number of assets created.

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The RADx-UP CDCC was a partnership between the Duke Clinical Research Institute and the UNC School of Medicine’s Center for Health Equity Research, with close collaborator Community-Campus Partnerships for Health (CCPH). The CDCC would become the backbone for organizing funded CEnR projects across the U.S. Focusing on underserved populations was intentional and effective.

INTRODUCTION

The four specific aims of the RADx-UP CDCC were to:

1. Create a community-centered, flexible program infrastructure
2. Support a participatory and inclusive community engagement program
3. Support research projects with COVID-19 testing guidance and emerging science.
4. Collect, harmonize, integrate, and disseminate data to scientific and local communities.

In addition to the 137 funded RADx-UP projects, the CDCC-led grant programs resulted in 25 rapid research pilot projects and 70 community collaboration outreach grant recipients.

FIGURE 0.3: OVERVIEW OF RADx-UP PROGRAM STRUCTURE

Impacts of CEnR and Collaborative Partnerships

From the outset, community engagement was crucial in implementing effective testing strategies. The RADx-UP researchers found trusted partners in community organizations, health departments, and academic institutions to create tailored solutions for communities often left out of public health conversations. The primary populations served, by self-reported race and/or ethnicity, included Hispanic/Latino (80 projects), African American/Black (74 projects), Asian (32 projects), American Indian/Alaska Native (20 projects), and Hawaiian/Pacific Islander (17 projects). Projects were creative in engaging with communities by listening through CoPs, working groups, and other sharing forums to understand barriers and engage communities in ways that empowered them.

INTRODUCTION

Project settings such as schools, community health centers, churches, prisons, farms, and other locations proved invaluable. Partnerships with Tribal Nation leaders, lay health workers, and teachers are just some successful ways RADx-UP projects collaborated with underserved communities. RADx-UP aimed not only to provide greater access to testing and vaccines but also to change the approach to public health by prioritizing community engagement, empowering local voices, and implementing culturally responsive practices throughout the research process (Figure 0.5).

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INTRODUCTION

RADx-UP developed CoPs where individuals could collaborate, share ideas, and document grassroots efforts to reduce disparities. Trust and strong partnerships between researchers and community members improved participation and led to better health interventions. By using culturally adapted strategies, and platforms for sharing, RADx-UP effectively engaged diverse populations, establishing relationships that may help address future health crises.

FIGURE 0.6: WHAT COMMUNITY-ENGAGED RESEARCH LOOKS LIKE

WHAT *PEOPLE THINK* COMMUNITY-ENGAGED RESEARCH LOOKS LIKE...

WHAT COMMUNITY-ENGAGED RESEARCH *ACTUALLY LOOKS LIKE*...

How This Playbook Helps

There was no existing playbook for how to reach underserved populations during the COVID-19 pandemic health crisis. The Public Health Emergency Preparedness Playbook is a compilation of best practices, insights, and practical resources drawn from this historic collection of scientific data and lessons learned for future public health emergencies. It was developed in response to the need for building lasting frameworks for health equity in the U.S.

The playbook offers strategies and practical tools for addressing public health crises through community-engaged approaches—especially where health disparities are greatest. It captures the collaborative efforts of the 137 RADx-UP research teams and the CDC. It serves as a roadmap for health practitioners, community organizations, policymakers, and researchers committed to translating scientific insights into practical strategies for addressing future public health crises.

This resource shares:

- Best practices for implementing community-engaged public health strategies
- Tools for harmonized data collection and infrastructure design
- Methods to communicate and share results transparently
- Approaches to sustain partnerships and evaluate long-term impact

By drawing from RADx-UP's collective lessons, the playbook aims to help others build on what worked. It is a blueprint for advancing health equity in future emergencies—centered on partnership, trust, and the power of shared data.

The playbook draws on a comprehensive knowledge base that includes over 372 publications. Selected resources created and/or used to implement RADx-UP were cataloged in a digital key assets index, which can be useful to academic scholars, community partners, future researchers, and the NIH.

The RADx-UP Public Health Emergency Preparedness Playbook aims to improve the preparedness of all communities for challenges by sharing best practices, insights, and tangible resources.

How to Use This Playbook

This playbook is a resource for anyone dedicated to improving testing equity during a public health emergency (PHE). Guidance is provided on how to use the playbook and its tools effectively.

- Each chapter covers a specific part of the testing equity program, offering clear insights and practical strategies that can be adapted to different situations.
- At the end of every chapter, you'll find a resource toolkit that summarizes the key points. These toolkits include useful templates, checklists, and extra materials that match the chapter's focus.
- Chapter and toolkit resources will either be provided in the appendices of this playbook or available as downloadable files. All downloadable resources will also be accessible on the [NIH RADx® Data Hub](#), where they will remain freely available for future use.
- For convenience, both the chapter overviews and toolkits (marked with the "Toolkit" banner) are formatted for printing, allowing you to create quick reference guides to share with teams or community members.

By using the playbook's design and toolkits, you can put equitable testing practices into action in your community. We hope this guide supports your efforts to enhance health equity and improve access to testing during any PHE.

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Conclusion

The RADx-UP program has played a crucial role in understanding and addressing the health disparities worsened by the COVID-19 pandemic. By engaging communities from the start, the initiative shows that progress in public health equity is achievable even during a crisis.

- **Section 1** focuses on capacity building, community engagement, and creating communities of practice.
- **Section 2** explains how to conduct testing in underserved areas, manage data systems, and perform community-engaged research.
- **Section 3** covers lessons learned about sharing results, communicating research impacts, and understanding the implications for policy and practice.
- **Section 4** discusses program evaluation and long-term sustainability.

Following the RADx-UP journey from 2020 to 2025, this playbook provides a clear roadmap for collecting knowledge, setting up programs, sharing outcomes, and evaluating their impact—all to ultimately save lives.

Relevant Publications

A list of publications, data sources, or scholarly work that support the evidence base and offer pathways for further reading.

- Webb Hooper M, Nápoles AM, Pérez-Stable EJ. COVID-19 and Racial/Ethnic Disparities. *JAMA*. 2020;323(24):2466-2467. doi: 10.1001/jama.2020.8598.
- National Institutes of Health. *RADx-UP White Paper*. 2024. Available at <https://www.nih.gov/sites/default/files/2024-12/RADx-UP-White-Paper-March-2024.pdf>
- Narayanasamy S, Veldman TH, Lee MJ, et al. RADx-UP Testing Core: Access to COVID-19 Diagnostics in Community-Engaged Research with Underserved Populations. *J Clin Microbiol* 2023;61:e00367-23. <https://doi.org/10.1128/jcm.00367-23>

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SECTION ONE: Setting Up the Program

SECTION ONE OVERVIEW

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This section lays the groundwork for establishing a responsive and resilient CEnR public health program by leveraging CoPs — multidisciplinary groups of people working together to address common concerns. The section offers insights into building collaborative networks, engaging community partners, and fostering inclusive environments to support health equity during public health crises like COVID-19. This section provides strategies for **structuring relationships, mobilizing action**, and **aligning shared goals among diverse partners**.

Chapter 1: Establishing and Mobilizing an Effective Community-Engaged Program

Summary

This chapter introduces the concept of CoPs and explores how RADx-UP utilized them to unite partnerships during the COVID-19 pandemic. It provides frameworks for building trust and sustaining engagement with partners, particularly in virtual environments.

Key Topics Covered

- Definition, history, and purpose of CoPs in public health
- RADx-UP's approach to mobilizing CoPs through virtual and non-virtual methods
- Case studies including Engagement Impact Teams, Working Groups, and the COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy series
- Strategies for effective communication and partner compensation
- Resource toolkits and practical templates for CoP implementation

“RADx-UP is a consortium of many projects, and it is very important not only for these teams to work together at the project level but also for the team to work together at the consortium level. We do that by facilitating meetings, facilitating working groups, facilitating connections among the projects, and having technologies to create a community of practice.”

MICHAEL (MICKY) COHEN-WOLKOWIEZ, MD, PHD

Co-Principal Investigator,
RADx-UP Coordination and
Data Collection Center

Chapter 2: Strengthening Partnerships to Reach Communities

Summary

This chapter focuses on capacity building through community engagement strategies rooted in the CoP model. It highlights the tools, training, and funding mechanisms that empowered community-based organizations (CBOs) and individuals to lead public health initiatives.

Key Topics Covered

- CDCC Community Engagement Framework: values and guiding principles
- Initiatives like Community Collaboration Grants and Partnering for Impact publication workshops
- Case studies on community health worker (CHW) CoPs, publication training, and tailored engagement support
- Empowerment through technical assistance, shared learning, and skill-building opportunities
- Toolkit and webinar resources to sustain capacity beyond the immediate crisis

Lessons Learned in This Section

RADx-UP's early investment in structured CoPs created sustainable pathways for collaboration during and beyond the COVID-19 pandemic. The initiative underscored the value of clear communication, equitable compensation, and inclusive practices that center community expertise. These approaches can serve as adaptable models for future public health responses and long-term engagement strategies.

“What we’ve seen during the pandemic and the work of RADx-UP is really an intentional effort to engage community groups and partner with them at all levels. Our commitment to the community, our commitment to engage them really serves to build trust with them by saying to them that we value your role in helping us to do our work.”

AL RICHMOND, MSW
Executive Director,
Community-Campus
Partnerships for Health

How do you establish and mobilize a community of practice?

When a PHE strikes, **bringing people together quickly and effectively** can make all the difference. A PHE response establishes an administrative structure with clear rules and processes, a team to work with, or a CoP.

This chapter examines how CoPs foster a space where partners can connect, share knowledge, and collaborate to address pressing community needs. Through the RADx-UP initiative, we learn how building trust, creating open communication, and setting shared goals can transform a network of individuals into a powerful movement.

Key Topics Covered

- Administrative structure of the CDCC, and CoPs, how they formed and functioned, and why they matter in public health
- How RADx-UP successfully built, mobilized, and facilitated a national network of partners
- Examples of RADx-UP strategies include Engagement Impact Teams, Working Groups, and the COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy.
- How to keep partners engaged and motivated, including paying community members fairly for their time and expertise

In Your Toolkit

Helpful outlines, templates, and real-world examples will assist you in establishing effective communication structures and collaborative spaces. These tools can help ensure your community remains engaged, informed, and ready for future PHEs.

Case Examples

- **Engagement Impact Teams:** Offered personalized support to research teams and community partners, helping them remain connected, troubleshoot challenges, and achieve their goals
- **Working Groups:** Brought together diverse partners to co-create equity-driven resources, build capacity, and publish guidance tailored to specific communities and populations
- **COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy Series:** Convened researchers and community leaders to translate research into practice and strengthen local responses to COVID-19 through equity-focused virtual conferences
- **Community Partner Compensation and Guidance:** Developed streamlined and equitable payment systems that recognized and respected community partners' contributions during the pandemic response

OVERVIEW

CHAPTER ONE: ESTABLISHING AND MOBILIZING AN EFFECTIVE COMMUNITY-ENGAGED PROGRAM

PHOTO COURTESY RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

During a **public health emergency (PHE)**, the ability to rapidly assemble resources, expertise, and community engagement is crucial. This chapter highlights the strategies and tools used to establish a robust and cohesive network of partners. It emphasizes the importance of building trust, maintaining clear communication, and aligning shared objectives for **underserved populations**. By incorporating the insights and expertise of community leaders within the administrative framework, the RADx-UP program demonstrates how collaborative efforts can lead to quick and effective responses to public health emergencies.

CoPs are groups of people who come together because they share a common interest or goal—in this case to support research projects with COVID-19 testing and emerging science—and want to work with others to learn more about it, address challenges and share solutions.

A successful CoP unites individuals who share a common purpose, vision, and a strong commitment to action. For the RADx-UP program, this involved engaging a wide range of partners, including community organizations, healthcare professionals, academic institutions, and public health departments. These partners collaborated to develop innovative solutions to the unprecedented challenges presented by the pandemic.

GLOSSARY

Public health emergency (PHE)

A situation requiring immediate action to protect the public's health

Underserved populations

Groups with limited access to essential services due to systemic barriers

In the context of a CoP, the term “community” refers to the individuals responsible for managing and directing the program, rather than the local populations being served through community engagement. The RADx-UP CDCC served as the main organization leading the CoP efforts. The CDCC facilitated the evolution of the CoP while supporting research teams with training, guidance, and resources. The CDCC was organized into four pillars of support groups.

COVID-19 TESTING CORE

Focused on improving testing strategies.

DATA SCIENCE AND BIostatISTICS CORE

Assisted projects with collecting, managing, and analyzing data.

COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT CORE

Helped projects reach out to communities, provide education, and increase participation in testing.

THE ADMINISTRATIVE CORE

Along with the Tracking and Evaluation Team, Communications team, and other partners, the Administrative Core helped the CDCC create an infrastructure to support the RADx-UP consortium and to disseminate information and results.

Background

Establishing the RADx-UP Coordination and Data Collection Center to Build Communities of Practice

At the start of RADx-UP, efforts focused on supporting testing programs that encouraged community involvement. The CDCC established a key partnership with CCPH, a nonprofit which aims to work together to create collaborative and interdisciplinary solutions to local and global challenges through engaged scholarship and service.

The structure established in consultation with CCPH became the foundation for the RADx-UP Community of Practice (RADx-UP CoP). This included:

- **RADx-UP Advisory Groups:** The RADx-UP CDCC established several advisory groups, including the Steering Committee, External Advisory Board, and Data Stewardship Committee. Each committee developed a charter to outline expectations, roles and responsibilities, and meeting cadence.
- **Publications & Dissemination Committee:** This committee established the RADx-UP Publications Policy, supported the development of scholarly products, and oversaw the publication of journal supplements. With consultative support from the Publications & Dissemination Committee members, the CDCC created the Partnering for Impact (P4I) initiative to support the preparation of consortial publications in a process that included the participation of at least one community partner. This process included a set of steps and support mechanisms for the development, preparation, and review of scholarly products (abstracts, scientific presentations, manuscripts) derived from information and data aggregated from RADx-UP research project teams.

- **Community Engagement Initiatives:** The CDCC Community Engagement Core established Engagement Impact Teams to serve as the key point of contact for RADx-UP projects. The establishment of Engagement Impact Teams supported projects, led orientation sessions for new projects, and guided partnerships to enhance community engagement. These teams helped onboard projects to CDCC services, such as coordinating and obtaining testing and supplies, providing and sharing community engagement expertise, and sharing guidance on data collection and sharing.
- **Support for Research Projects:** The RADx-UP Testing Core focused on shared goals of providing testing protocols and guidance to expedite access and uptake of COVID-19 testing. Strategies shared led to significant cost savings in test procurement for underserved populations. The CDCC established the Rapid Research Pilot Program (RP2), including the development of processes for application submission and review, award selection and onboarding, ongoing evaluation and tracking, and offboarding. This program extended the reach and impact of the RADx-UP Consortium to respond to the COVID-19 crisis.

In the early stages of RADx-UP, the CDCC focused on assigning staff to specific projects and planning resources to meet program goals. Each of the four RADx-UP cores created evaluation plans and work plans to guide their efforts. To help manage tasks and track progress, the CDCC partnered with the project management platform Asana and developed a tool for monitoring metrics and reporting updates. Using Asana helped the Cores work efficiently and adapt to challenges, which allowed them to quickly advance the program's objectives. Initial activities included capacity planning, communication strategies, and the establishment of various grant programs to support community partners in COVID-19 testing initiatives.

The CDCC also developed a communication plan that included creating the RADx-UP website, newsletter templates, FAQs, and other tools to share information. During the hectic early days of the pandemic, the RADx-UP Testing Core took on the task of getting COVID-19 tests to project sites. They created testing protocols, plans, and reviews to help each site follow best practices. The Testing Core stayed updated on guidelines from the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention and FDA, and shared this information with sites as new evidence became available. This core also published several papers about how they quickly obtained and distributed tests to underserved populations. Their efforts saved over \$1 million by providing free and discounted tests.

What Is a Community of Practice?

Communities of practice have become an important way to share knowledge, solve problems, and learn together in different areas, especially public health. The idea of CoPs started in the business world in the 1990s, where they helped teams work together better, come up with new ideas, and improve how they do their jobs. Later, healthcare adapted these ideas to create spaces for people with similar interests to collaborate, share experiences, and grow their knowledge, which ultimately benefits local communities.

CoPs are made up of people who actively work in a field and want to share tips, ask questions, and learn from each other. Members have skills and experience that match the topic the CoP focuses on. For example, the RADx-UP CoP, through the Child Health working group, brought together community organizations and school staff to focus on how to increase access to COVID-19 testing in school environments. The main purpose of a CoP is to connect people who have the same interests so they can share ideas, tools, and advice. CoPs give members a chance to improve their skills, solve problems, and use best practices. By learning from each other, members can build strong relationships and gain helpful experiences. CoPs also help participants grow their confidence and develop the skills needed to work with their communities effectively.

The RADx-UP Community of Practice

The RADx-UP program functioned as a CoP and illustrated how CoPs could address health equity challenges during a health crisis such as the COVID-19 pandemic. The RADx-UP CDCC served as the organizing entity for the initiative's CoP efforts. The CDCC's coordination of research teams included a wide range of education, training, implementation guidance, and facilitation. The core purpose of the CoP was to connect the unique strengths, knowledge, and cultural insights of CBOs to elevate COVID-19 testing within underserved populations. The RADx-UP program showed how CoPs can help solve health equity problems during public health crises like the COVID-19 pandemic. The main goal of this CoP was to use the knowledge and cultural expertise of local organizations to improve COVID-19 testing in underserved communities.

RADx-UP CDCC COP GOALS

- Create a more connected community
- Support, expand, and disseminate knowledge
- Enhance and maintain multidirectional interactions and co-learning

Engagement Tactics

The RADx-UP program utilized various tools and strategies to improve community collaboration and engagement in addressing challenges related to COVID-19 testing. One key initiative was the Community Collaboration Grant (C2G) program, which provided \$50,000 in direct funding to support community partners in enhancing the capacity, training, and support for COVID-19 testing. Community-serving organizations, faith-based groups, tribal nations, and similar organizations were eligible to participate. Other notable tools and strategies are highlighted in case studies in this playbook, and include:

- The P4I program, which was designed to support consortial publications using data from the CDCC. This initiative trained community partners to contribute as authors on manuscript writing teams, fostering collaboration between research teams and the communities they serve.
- The Engagement Resource Center offered a wide range of materials hosted on the RADx-UP website. These included toolkits, videos, informational handouts, and research briefs that were accessible to RADx-UP projects, scientific communities, and the public.
- The RADx-UP Image Bank, a collection of representative photographs from projects across the country to support communications and recruitment efforts.
- Compensation: Procedures were also established to ensure fair compensation for community partners, recognizing their vital contributions to advancing local COVID-19 initiatives.

Together, these programs and resources demonstrated the RADx-UP program’s dedication to empowering communities and fostering collaboration in the fight against COVID-19.

The RADx-UP CoP successfully enhanced community engagement during the pandemic, even when participants were spread out in different places. They used virtual tools and digital platforms to connect people and share resources effectively. This approach made it easier for members to exchange ideas and knowledge quickly, which was especially important for supporting underserved communities during the COVID-19 crisis. By relying on these tools, community organizations were able to stay connected and share strategies that worked, despite the challenges of physical distance.

The following chart outlines the regular meetings and opportunities that the RADx-UP CoP organized to help members learn, share, and connect.

GLOSSARY

CEAL Community Engagement Alliance

	PURPOSE	CONTENT	AUDIENCE
RADx-UP Scientific Meeting	Annual conference to share scientific methods, findings, and early results of the RADx-UP projects to increase understanding of the project-specific impact of the community-centered research conducted	Selected projects and community partners jointly present data and results that highlight the impact of the community-centered research conducted	RADx-UP consortium, scientists, community members, and the public
COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy	Annual multi-day conference to increase access to research results and evidence-based practices by engaging diverse partners, share equity frameworks	Co-learning and active discussion around COVID-19 testing equity and its related factors, incorporating annual themes from project presentations and other research	RADx-UP consortium, and partners such as the Community Engagement Alliance (CEAL), not posted on NIH website
Engagement Impact Team Project Meeting	Informal monthly meetings to support individual RADx-UP projects and connect them with CDCC technical experts	Facilitate connections to community engagement expertise and data harmonization support	RADx-UP consortium (project teams and their community partners, NIH, CDCC)
Working Groups	Online spaces for projects to tackle specific topics and challenges that may commonly occur among similar populations	Share ideas, collaborate on resources and scholarship, and provide feedback to CDCC and NIH	RADx-UP consortium (project teams and their community partners, NIH, CDCC)
Project-wide Meeting	Monthly meeting to share quality improvement and collective learning across teams	Project teams and community partners share experiences and best practices in community engagement strategies	RADx-UP consortium (project teams and their community partners, NIH, CDCC)
Community Connections	Quarterly online gathering of RADx-UP community partners with a focus on sharing and discussion.	Facilitate networking and collaboration of community partners.	RADx-UP community partners

The case studies in this chapter illustrate how RADx-UP successfully built and mobilized a CoP to support its public health mission during the COVID-19 pandemic. These examples show how trust-building, structured communication, and knowledge exchange enabled a diverse group of partners to collaborate effectively and drive equity-centered solutions across the consortium.

- 1. Engagement Impact Teams:** Served as core facilitators between RADx-UP projects and the CDCC, offering tailored technical assistance, tracking milestones, and fostering co-learning across research teams through sustained communication and culturally responsive guidance.
- 2. Working Groups:** CDCC created spaces for focused collaboration among stakeholders addressing equity for specific populations (e.g., Black, Hispanic, AI/AN communities), generating practical tools, publications, and policy resources rooted in community experience.
- 3. COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy Series:** CDCC hosted annual convenings to accelerate translation of research into practice, promote knowledge exchange, and strengthen community-academic partnerships with actionable tools and localized implementation strategies.
- 4. Community Partner Compensation and Guidance:** CDCC developed clear and equitable compensation structures for community partners, reinforcing the value of their contributions and supporting trust-based engagement throughout the initiative.

Engagement Impact Teams (EITs) served as the main link between RADx-UP project teams and the CDCC. Each team included one or more CDCC staff members in their EIT to help them stay on track with milestones and connect them to necessary resources. These teams played an important role in ensuring projects quickly accessed CDCC resources to implement their testing and research strategies successfully.

EITs kept detailed records of each project's progress, including accomplishments, challenges, questions, and requests for support. They held regular monthly meetings to share updates with the NIH and worked with CDCC staff to find solutions and plan strategies for improving project development. Outcomes from these meetings informed strategies to extend the reach of the program to yet-to-be reached populations, highlighting the importance of bidirectional communication.

In addition to administrative tasks, EITs helped bridge the gap between academic researchers and community members. They guided the teams in creating culturally sensitive plans to improve COVID-19 testing in underserved communities, which helped build trusting relationships. Their work created an environment where collaboration and open communication could thrive.

Using consistent communication methods such as virtual meetings and emails, EITs gained a deep understanding of the projects they supported. This approach fostered mutual learning, with project teams sharing their challenges and community insights to improve research designs and activities.

CASE STUDY 1.1 | ENGAGEMENT IMPACT TEAMS

FIGURE 1.2: RADx-UP PROGRAM STRUCTURE

Resource Spotlight

JOURNAL PUBLICATION

Supporting Community Driven, Large Scale Research Initiatives: An Engagement Impact Team Model *[Forthcoming; in preparation]*

RADx-UP ENGAGEMENT IMPACT TEAMS: SUPPORTING DOCUMENT TYPES

The documents below were created to define the structure, responsibilities, and community engagement functions of the Engagement Impact Teams (EITs), which served as a central support mechanism across RADx-UP project sites.

DOCUMENT NAME	DESCRIPTION
EIT Community Engagement Roles	Describes all community engagement tasks carried out by EITs in support of RADx-UP project teams. (See Appendix A.1)
EIT (Community Engagement) Roles & Responsibilities for Project Specialist	Defines the duties of Project Specialists responsible for leading community engagement within EITs.
EIT (Community Engagement) Roles & Responsibilities for Associate Project Specialist	Outlines the role of Associate Project Specialists in supporting engagement activities and team functions.

CASE STUDY 1.2

WORKING GROUPS

The RADx-UP CoP created various working groups (WGs) to promote community engagement, learning, and sharing experiences to improve COVID-19 testing equity in underserved populations. The WGs focused on specific populations such as Hispanic, Black, American Indian/Alaska Native, sexual and gender minorities, children, and CHWs. These WGs included both structured groups with clear goals and objectives—known as the *Community Engaged Working Groups* and *Scientific Task Forces*—and unstructured, flexible groups known as *Collective Impact Networks*, exemplified by the Tribal Nations WG. Each WG type had different members, goals, and compensation levels (for more about the structured and unstructured WG models, see the Resource Spotlight section below).

For structured WGs, the RADx-UP program provided guidelines for forming new groups, including developing a charter, selecting partners, and ensuring diverse expertise. The program also fostered unstructured Collaborative Impact Networks. These groups provided opportunities for more organic collaboration, peer learning, and community-driven initiatives without strict formal goals, allowing participants to adapt and respond to emerging needs flexibly.

All groups—whether structured or unstructured—were supported through regular virtual meetings and governance structures designed to promote community engagement, knowledge sharing, and capacity building. They emphasized the importance of diversity and expertise in these groups. A steering committee was established to oversee progress and ensure alignment with program objectives.

Watch a short video [here](#).

CASE STUDY 1.2 | WORKING GROUPS

The RADx-UP WGs addressed issues related to social determinants of health (SDOH), promoted community capacity building, and considered Social, Ethical, and Behavioral Implications (SEBI). Examples of working group successes can be found in their group work products:

- The Engaging Black/African American working group created a guide, “[Advocating for Racial Equity in the US Healthcare System](#),” aimed to deepen understanding, strengthen patient-provider relationships, and foster shared decision-making in healthcare settings. Developed in collaboration with community members, it offered practical strategies and tools designed to enhance patient and provider engagement while addressing the barriers that contribute to poorer health outcomes in underserved communities.
- The Child Health working group partnered with the ABC Science Collaborative and the RADx-UP Publications & Dissemination Committee to lead the publication of two special supplements in the journal *Pediatrics*. This [first *Pediatrics* supplement was published in February 2022](#) and was a collective effort of 67 authors across several institutions and shared what had been learned about children returning to school during the COVID-19 pandemic (See Appendix A.2 for lay summary). A [second supplement in *Pediatrics* was published in July 2023](#), representing 109 authors, including eight community members, across 16 RADx-UP Return to School institutions, and shared what had been learned about reach, access, and effectiveness of COVID-19 testing in school settings. ([Video summary](#) and refer to Appendix A.3 for lay summary)
- The [Social Determinants of Health](#) and [Building Capacity](#) working groups explored systems thinking and created group models to show the many barriers and facilitators to COVID-19 testing and vaccination.
- The Engaging Hispanic/Latino/Latinx working group led the publication of an article in the [Journal of Clinical and Translational Science](#).

CASE STUDY 1.2 | WORKING GROUPS

Resource Spotlight

JOURNAL PUBLICATION

- Community-Engaged Research in RADx-UP: Lessons on Building Capacity through Working Groups [*Submitted for publication*]

RADx-UP WORKING GROUPS: SUPPORTING DOCUMENT TYPES

The documents below supported the creation and coordination of RADx-UP Working Groups, offering tools and templates to guide structure, governance, and collaboration across diverse groups.

DOCUMENT NAME	DESCRIPTION
RADx-UP Establishing a New Working Group	Provides a step-by-step guide for creating a new working group, including formation criteria. (See Appendix A.4)
RADx-UP Working Group — Facilitation and Support	Outlines tasks and support roles for maintaining effective working group operations.
RADx-UP Working Group Governance — Roles and Responsibilities	Defines the responsibilities of members and leadership to ensure accountability and clarity. (See Appendix A.5)
Types of RADx-UP Working Groups	Describes the different formats (e.g., structured, unstructured) and focus areas of working groups.
New Working Group Charter Slides	Template slides to define a group’s purpose, goals, membership, and scope of work.
Working Group Communications Plan	Details the approach for maintaining clear, consistent, and bidirectional communication.

CASE STUDY 1.3

RADx-UP COVID-19 EQUITY EVIDENCE ACADEMY SERIES

The RADx-UP project recognized the urgent need to respond to COVID-19 by quickly translating reliable evidence and knowledge into practice. It also emphasized the importance of creating and informing local, community-led implementation strategies. Between 2021 and 2023, RADx-UP hosted four RADx-UP COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy meetings. These sessions brought together researchers, community leaders, and government practitioners to share their experiences, ideas, and recommendations to address disparities in COVID-19 testing.

The virtual conference was designed to share the best practices and implementation strategies to fight COVID-19 in underserved communities. Initially used for HIV/AIDS and other disease advocacy groups, the Evidence Academy conference model highlights that while knowledge transfer can occur, translating evidence into practice requires realistic, local implementation strategies. The CDCC developed a low-cost, regional conference model to achieve several goals:

- Improve access to research results and evidence-based practices
- Encourage structured, in-depth discussions among participants
- Promote networking and collaborations
- Engage relevant partners in creating follow-up action plans

The Evidence Academy series focused on understanding the science and current evidence of COVID-19 testing in the most impacted communities. The series aimed to provide ongoing access to resources from all four Evidence Academies, along with other materials generated over the years, to help translate community-engaged science into practice for improved health outcomes.

CASE STUDY 1.3 | RADx-UP COVID-19 EQUITY EVIDENCE ACADEMY SERIES

Key Accomplishments

The COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy served as a pivotal virtual series to address disparities in COVID-19 testing within underserved populations.

- **Virtual Gatherings:** The nationwide virtual convenings focused on timely and evolving aspects of the COVID-19 response, such as innovations in testing, equitable vaccine infrastructure, and community engagement strategies.
- **Comprehensive Data Sharing:** Events featured “Data Profiles” that offered national overviews of RADx-UP projects, highlighting geographic distribution, populations served, and areas of innovation.
- **Community-Driven Topics:** Sessions addressed real-time challenges and solutions in COVID-19 testing, including cultural and linguistic adaptation, school-based testing, policy alignment, and multi-sector partnerships.
- **Strategic Takeaways:** Each event produced lay summaries, roundtable recommendations, and tools to guide future initiatives in community-academic partnership and health equity research.
- **Sustained Engagement:** The Evidence Academy series evolved to emphasize long-term sustainability, documenting and disseminating lessons learned to inform future health emergency preparedness and community engagement.

FIGURE 1.3: THE EVIDENCE ACADEMY UTILIZED AN ARTIST TO CREATE AN ILLUSTRATION OF KEY TAKEAWAYS WHILE THE EVENT WAS IN PROGRESS.

CASE STUDY 1.3 | RADx-UP COVID-19 EQUITY EVIDENCE ACADEMY SERIES

Resource Spotlight**JOURNAL PUBLICATIONS**

- **Adapting the Evidence Academy model for virtual stakeholder engagement in a national setting during the COVID-19 pandemic** — Article in the *Journal of Clinical and Translational Science* focused on the Equity Evidence Academy structure. [[Visit Website](#)]
- **Community-Centered Recommendations from the RADx-UP COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy Virtual Conference Series** — Article focused on EA dissemination and outcomes. [*Forthcoming; accepted for publication*]

Equity Evidence Academy (EA) Instructional Guide — A manual for conducting a conference using the Equity Evidence Academy model. (See Appendix A.6)

COVID-19 EQUITY EVIDENCE ACADEMY 2021: TRANSLATING INNOVATIONS IN TESTING (FEB. 24-25, 2021)

- [Data Profile](#): An overview of the different RADx-UP and Community Engagement Alliance (CEAL) projects across the nation, as well as a snapshot of the current body of knowledge on COVID-19 testing in communities of most significant impact.

COVID-19 EQUITY EVIDENCE ACADEMY 2021: LOOKING FORWARD: BRIDGING INFRASTRUCTURES FOR EQUITABLE COVID-19 TESTING AND VACCINATION (NOV. 17-18, 2021)

- [A Lay Summary Report](#): Information about attendees, the six cross-cutting themes of the event, a summary of keynote presentations, takeaway observations and recommendations from breakout sessions and roundtable discussions, illustrations from the event, and our lessons learned.

COVID-19 EQUITY EVIDENCE ACADEMY 2022: COVID-19 TESTING EQUITY THROUGH MESSAGING ACCURACY AND ACCESSIBILITY (SEPT. 28-29, 2022)

- [Key takeaways](#) by the presenters in the Advancing Community-Academic Partnerships Presentation Series (ACAP) where researchers and community partners shared promising practices and strategies for developing and maintaining equitable community-academic research partnerships while promoting an increased understanding of the importance of community engagement when conducting research. These key takeaways were grouped in the categories of: 1. trust in the foundation, 2. create access to healthcare, and 3. invest in community members.

COVID-19 EQUITY EVIDENCE ACADEMY 2023: FROM POLICY TO PRACTICE: SUSTAINING LESSONS LEARNED FOR COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT IN COVID-19 TESTING EQUITY (SEPT. 28-29, 2023)

- [Data Profile](#): the latest evidence related to the impact of community-academic partnerships and community engagement on COVID-19 testing efforts and to provide a forum to explore how community-engaged research can offer a path toward a healthier future for all.

CASE STUDY 1.4

COMMUNITY PARTNER COMPENSATION AND GUIDANCE

Community partners play a key role in community engagement methods and CEnR practices thanks partly to their strong connections to the communities being studied. Unlike researchers at universities, these partners are often not set up to get paid easily through university systems. This can create problems and delays in compensating them fairly for their time and work.

To address this, RADx-UP worked with CCPH as a go-between to manage and expedite payments. Instead of going through complicated university systems, community partners were paid directly by CCPH. This made the process smoother and built more trust with the people doing the work.

Here's How it Worked

- Community partners were paid \$100 per hour or received a set amount (called a stipend or honorarium) for their contributions to relevant events or meetings.
- They could be paid by mailed check, direct deposit, or electronic gift card.
- They had to fill out a few forms, like a W-9 tax form and a payment request form, and send them through a secure online portal.
- CDCC staff helped track who attended specific events or meetings and made sure partners were given the right forms.
- Payments were processed once a month. Partners had to submit paperwork by the 25th of the month to get paid the following month.

For community partners who contributed to RADx-UP initiatives regularly, CCPH kept records and sent tax forms if their total payments were over \$600 in a year. All personal information was kept safe and private.

CASE STUDY 1.4 | COMMUNITY PARTNER COMPENSATION AND GUIDANCE

What We Learned

- It's important to have clear and simple steps for how community partners will get paid. This helps everyone know what to expect and keeps the process fair.
- Payment systems should be flexible and improve over time based on the needs of the community partners using them.
- Community partners need help understanding required forms, like the W-9, and why they are needed. Giving clear instructions builds trust and avoids delays.

This compensation system made it easier for community partners to get paid and showed that RADx-UP valued their time and contributions. Paying people fairly and on time is a simple but powerful way to show respect and build strong partnerships.

Resource Spotlight

Equitable Compensation for Community Engagement Guidebook

— This Urban Institute toolkit includes practical guidance and approaches for creating an equitable compensation plan for your organization's community-partnered research projects. [[Visit Website](#)]

Key Takeaways for Future Public Health Emergencies

RADx-UP showed that establishing a CoP is a crucial first step to facilitating communication and building a structure for effective collaboration during a public health emergency. The RADx-UP CoP successfully managed a broad consortium of practitioners and relevant partners to create impacts and save lives.

Lessons learned for creating CoPs during a future PHE by aim:

- **Contribute to a more connected community and support, expand, and disseminate knowledge:** In the future, PHEs should leverage established and innovative communication methods to build organizational structure and open communication. Virtual tools used to communicate across the consortium of participants included Project-wide Meetings, the Evidence Academy, EITs, WGs, and consistent efforts to inform partners through external communications, such as Community Connections newsletters and scientific meeting reports. Overall, study deliverables are based on building trusting relationships through good CoP facilitation of open and transparent communication. Resources from RADx-UP reflect a purposeful approach to open communication through systematic methods that prioritize inclusion.
- **Enhance and maintain multidirectional interactions and co-learning:** A CEnR approach successfully brought typically siloed groups together to create innovation. The network supported diverse methods of meeting and supporting the study site teams to collect data, create open forums for feedback to leadership, and implement innovative locally applied interventions.

GLOSSARY

CEnR Research conducted with active community involvement at all stages

Conclusion

RADx-UP showed how CoPs can organize effective strategies to involve communities, especially during public health emergencies. By bringing together knowledge from local organizations and encouraging teamwork and sharing ideas, the CoP model helps improve decisions and creates positive change. This program highlighted the importance of clear communication, transparency, and a focus on fairness. These lessons can guide leaders in future CoPs, helping them connect with underserved communities. By using what was learned, communities can be better prepared for future health crises, ensuring everyone has a voice and the tools to succeed.

Toolkit

1. FEATURED RADx-UP RESOURCES

Practical resources developed directly by the CDCC or RADx-UP projects. These may include publications, guides, or curated tools specific to implementing a program like the RADx-UP initiative.

- Equity Evidence Academy Series:
 - **COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy 2021: Translating Innovations in Testing** (Feb. 24-25, 2021) [[Download PDF](#)]
 - **COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy 2021: Looking Forward: Bridging Infrastructures for Equitable COVID-19 Testing and Vaccination** (Nov. 17-18, 2021) [[Download PDF](#)]
 - **COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy 2022: COVID-19 Testing Equity Through Messaging Accuracy and Accessibility** (Sept. 28-29, 2022) [[Visit Website](#)]
 - **COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy 2023: From Policy to Practice: Sustaining Lessons Learned for Community Engagement in COVID-19 Testing Equity** (Sept. 28-29, 2023) [[Visit Website](#)]
- **Advocating for Racial Equity in the US Healthcare System: Guiding Patient-Provider Relationships for Improved Health Outcomes** — A comprehensive guide co-created by the RADx-UP Engaging Black/African Americans Working Group and CPH. [[Visit Website](#)]
- **Adapting the Evidence Academy model for virtual stakeholder engagement in a national setting during the COVID-19 pandemic** — Article in the *Journal of Clinical and Translational Science* focused on the Equity Evidence Academy structure. [[Visit Website](#)]
- **Community-Centered Recommendations from the RADx-UP COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy Virtual Conference Series** — Article focused on EA dissemination and outcomes. [*Forthcoming; accepted for publication*]
- **Promoting inclusion in COVID-19 research for diverse Hispanic/Latino(x) populations: Recommendations from the RADx[®] Underserved Populations Hispanic/Latino/Latinx working group** [[Visit Website](#)]

2. SUPPLEMENTAL RESOURCES

Resources developed outside the CDCC but shared via the Engagement Resource Center or by project partners. These materials offer supplemental value and represent real-world utility during a PHE response.

- **Equitable Compensation for Community Engagement Guidebook** — This Urban Institute toolkit includes practical guidance and approaches for creating an equitable compensation plan for your organizations' community-partnered research projects. [[Visit Website](#)]

3. “DOWNLOAD & DO” — READY-TO-USE TOOLS

This section includes hands-on templates, workflows, sample communications, onboarding documents, planning checklists, data collection tools, or forms for immediate application.

Related to Engagement Impact Teams (EITs):

- **EIT Community Engagement Roles** — This document describes all EIT tasks related to community engagement with the RADx-UP projects. (See Appendix A.1)

Related to Equity Evidence Academy (EA):

- **Equity Evidence Academy (EA) Instructional Guide** — This document acts as a guide for conducting a conference using the Equity Evidence Academy model. (See Appendix A.6)

Related to Working Groups (WG):

- **RADx-UP Establishing a New Working Group** — The purpose of this process document is to outline the required steps to establish a new WG as part of the RADx-UP program. (See Appendix A.4)
- **RADx-UP Working Group Governance — Roles and Responsibilities** — The purpose of this process document is to outline the roles and responsibilities of WG members responsible for governance. (See Appendix A.5)

4. RELEVANT PUBLICATIONS

A list of publications, data sources, or scholarly work that support the evidence base and offer pathways for further reading.

- Hennein R, Gita JM, Turimumahoro P, et al. Core components of a Community of Practice to improve community health worker performance: a qualitative study. *Implement Sci Commun.* 2022;3(1):27. doi: 10.1186/s43058-022-00279-1.
- James-McAlpine J, Larkins S, Nagle C. Exploring the evidence base for Communities of Practice in health research and translation: a scoping review. *Health Res Policy Syst.* 2023;21(1):55. doi: 10.1186/s12961-023-01000-x.
- Lesser EL, Storck J. Communities of practice and organizational performance. *IBM Systems Journal.* 2001;40:831–841.

What does building the capacity to work and truly partner with communities take?

This chapter examines how community partnerships, grounded in shared values, mutual respect, and continuous learning, can lead to lasting change. Drawing on the RADx-UP model, we see how investments in tools, training, and tailored support empowered local organizations and individuals to lead. From small grants to publication workshops, the focus in RADx-UP was on ensuring communities weren't just involved—they were equipped, trusted, and supported to drive public health solutions themselves.

Key Topics Covered

- How the RADx-UP Project fits into the stream of community engagement science and used a Community Engagement Framework to build a foundation of equity, trust, and transparency
- Funding strategies for capacity-building, such as small grant funding, tailored training, and peer-led learning
- The role of CHWs, academic-community co-presentations, and publication workshops in elevating local voices
- Why sustainable partnerships require compensation, flexibility, and space for reflection

In Your Toolkit

Templates, webinars, and guides to help you apply for small grants, lead collaborative writing projects, train community teams, and build your lasting partnerships.

Case Examples

This chapter features four real-world examples of community-centered partnerships in action:

- **Community Health Worker Symposium:** Recognized and supported CHWs as trusted messengers, emphasizing their role in improving health equity
- **ACAP Presentation Series:** Presentation series that enabled community-academic project teams to share effective, co-designed research partnerships and receive recognition for their contributions to the broader RADx-UP network
- **Partnering for Impact Publication Workshop Series:** Built writing and publishing skills among community partners to ensure their voices appeared in academic literature
- **CCPH Community Engagement Services and Trainings:** Offered RADx-UP project site consultation services and national, virtual trainings, grounded in CCPH Principles of Partnership and practical tools for success

CHAPTER TWO: STRENGTHENING PARTNERSHIPS TO REACH COMMUNITIES

PHOTO COURTESY RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

As health disparities have highlighted the need for targeted interventions, bridging academic expertise with community knowledge through meaningful partnership has become vital. The impact of community engagement and collaborative partnerships has been described in various RADx-UP publications in the following areas:

- Enhancing recruitment, data collection, and workforce capacity for research
- Informing effective health messaging and outreach strategies
- Guiding research implementation through community-based participatory approaches
- Building and sustaining trusted relationships within communities
- Evaluating and strengthening the effectiveness of engagement efforts

The CDCC's guiding principles on community engagement and **Communities of Practice (CoP)** define the values (equity, transparency, trust, respect, mutual understanding and accountability) — or core beliefs — which help center the work, interactions, and decisions of community-engaged work.

GLOSSARY

CoP Groups collaborating across fields to share knowledge and grow professionally

The CDCC Community Engagement Framework (See Appendix B.1) values and principles are to:

- Promote the long-term sustainability and success of community-engaged initiatives
- Provide opportunities for reflective conversations
- Create opportunities to listen, learn, and inform
- Embrace individual differences
- Engage without fear of judgment or retaliation
- Empower diverse communities

By fostering an environment of continuous learning, relationship building, and mutual support, CoPs not only enhance individual skills but also facilitate the broader aims of community engagement.

Background

The RADx-UP CDCC participated directly in fostering community engagement through a variety of initiatives designed to reach underserved populations. The RADx-UP CoP facilitated relationships between academic institutions, NIH, and local organizations, fostering an environment where learning and sharing were prioritized. This dynamic flow of insights and ideas ultimately strengthened community trust and mobilized grassroots support during the pandemic. These capacity-building initiatives were aimed at both community leaders and their academic research partners.

Capacity Building: Capacity building refers to enhancing the skills, resources, and organizational structures of communities to address public health challenges and disparities effectively. This includes developing competencies among community members, mobilizing resources, strengthening organizations, fostering collaboration, empowering leadership, and improving data management capacity. Ultimately, capacity building aims to create resilient communities that are better equipped to promote health equity and improve health outcomes.

Community Engagement: Community engagement aims to empower social groups and networks and increase local participation in finding solutions. Community engagement can help improve decision-making, build trust, and strengthen relationships. It can also help local governments make sustainable decisions and drive social transformation.

To stay true to the community engagement values and principles, it was important to have those most affected by the research at the table. Therefore, some of the capacity-building efforts focused on developing competencies of the community leaders to be more effective research partners. For example, RADx-UP provided a crash course in manuscript writing to community partners (Partnering for Impact Publication Workshop Series) and encouraged co-led scientific presentations at RADx-UP events (**ACAP** Oral Project Presentations). See the case studies below for more information about these capacity-building activities.

Another approach was to educate academic researchers on effective community engagement. CCPH provided direct one-to-one community-engagement training for academic research teams. More broadly, the CDCC focused on the role of **CHWs**, a CBO-led outreach role, that proved successful to many RADx-UP research projects in sharing insights about the value of their work across the consortium.

The CDCC's most direct form of community engagement capacity building was through its Community Collaboration Grants (**C2G**) program. It offered up to \$50,000 to support the direct costs incurred by CBOs who knew how best to reach their communities. The CDCC relied on its partnership with CCPH as well as its broad network of research projects and their partners to spread the word about the grant opportunity.

GLOSSARY

ACAP Advancing Community-Academic Partnerships — A forum to share best practices for equitable community-academic research partnerships

CHWs Trusted frontline public health workers who connect communities to services

C2G Funding to strengthen community-led COVID-19 testing and engagement efforts

PHOTO COURTESY RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

By fostering an environment of continuous learning, relationship building, and mutual support, CoPs not only enhanced individual skills but also facilitated the broader aims of community engagement. Ultimately, by capitalizing on the strengths of diverse CBOs, RADx-UP was able to champion equitable access to COVID-19 testing and vaccines.

Finally, in partnership with CCPH, the CDCC was able to define shared values and guiding principles about community engagement, which aimed to guide the CDCC in supporting the projects. Using their community engagement expertise, they developed an onboarding toolkit and offered trainings and tailored support for RADx-UP projects.

Strategy for Engagement: Community Collaboration Grants

The Community Collaboration Grant (C2G) Initiative exemplifies the RADx-UP framework for capacity building. The C2G program provided \$50,000 for direct funding to community partners looking to advance capacity, training, support, and community experience with COVID-19 testing initiatives to fulfill community-identified needs. The program provided a platform for updates from the CDCC, information on community collaboration grants, and engagement with applicants through a webinar series aimed to improve comprehension of vital pre- and post-award activities related to budget preparation, justification, and grant management.

Participants formulated strategies for effective communication, emphasizing the capabilities of CBOs, grant management requirements, and information exchange with academic

researchers and administrative offices. Through this initiative, partners acquired valuable insights and practical skills to enhance their community collaboration endeavors.

The RADx-UP CDCC began soliciting C2G applications on February 26, 2021, and closed its last application cycle on April 23, 2023. The program received a total of 209 applications across seven cycles and funded a total of 70 projects (33%). Investing over \$3.7 million dollars in supporting organizations in 27 states, the C2G program helped organizations increase training, education, communication, information dissemination, and capacity building related to COVID-19 testing, isolation, and contact tracing in communities. The webinars created to onboard the new awardees can be found in the resources section at the end of the chapter.

FIGURE 2.1: RADx-UP C2G PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION STATES & TERRITORIES

Resource Spotlight

C2G GRANT APPLICATION WEBINAR SERIES

This three-part webinar series was designed to guide community-based organizations through the full lifecycle of applying for and managing a grant. Each session provides practical tips on navigating pre-award preparation, budget development, and post-award responsibilities.

- Part 1: Getting Started, an Overview of the Pre-Award Process [[Watch Video](#)]
- Part 2: How to Develop a Grant Budget and Budget Justification [[Watch Video](#)]
- Part 3: An Overview of the Post-Award Process [[Watch Video](#)]

Disclaimer: These webinars were created based on NIH guidance available at the time of recording. Some information may no longer reflect current NIH policies or procedures.

The case studies in this chapter highlight RADx-UP's efforts to build capacity and strengthen partnerships with CBOs through funding, training, and co-learning initiatives. These examples emphasize how investing in communities as co-leaders in research efforts leads to stronger engagement, better data, and more sustainable health equity outcomes.

1. **CHW Symposium:** Showcases the vital role CHWs played as trusted messengers and frontline responders during the pandemic, and how their expertise was elevated through symposia, policy recommendations, and strategic support for long-term sustainability.
2. **ACAP Presentation Series:** Features a presentation series that enabled community-academic project teams to share effective, co-designed research partnerships and receive recognition for their contributions to the broader RADx-UP network.
3. **Partnering for Impact Publication Workshop Series:** Describes a 12-part training series designed to build the scholarly capacity of community partners and support the co-development of peer-reviewed publications using RADx-UP data and collaborative authorship models.
4. **CCPH Community Engagement Trainings and Services:** Highlights the tailored onboarding, technical assistance, and coaching provided to projects through CCPH, reinforcing principles of equity, shared power, and community-centered research practices.

CASE STUDY 2.1

COMMUNITY HEALTH WORKER SYMPOSIUM

The RADx-UP CDCC hosted a Community Health Worker Symposium that highlighted the critical role of CHWs in addressing health disparities during the COVID-19 pandemic.

RADxUP
Community Health Worker Symposium
Simposio de Promotoras

CHWs who collaborated with RADx-UP projects served in multiple roles from advisory to outreach to shared project leadership. Also known as “lay health advisers” or “health navigators,” and in Spanish as “promotoras” or “promotores de salud,” CHWs are essential links between community members and healthcare services. They assume critical roles both in community and clinical settings.

RADx-UP studies involving CHWs were reviewed and resulted in the policy paper [Opportunities to Enhance Health Equity by Integrating Community Health Workers into Payment and Care Delivery Reforms](#). This paper highlighted how CHW roles included disseminating culturally and linguistically appropriate information about the COVID-19 pandemic, providing direct services such as administering COVID-19 tests, and coordinating care and health system navigation.

Voices from the Field

The symposium welcomed over 70 CHWs (~130 attendees in total) from across the U.S. for a dual language virtual event that included prerecorded audio interviews with CHWs sharing their insights and advice from the field:

- Insights from CHWs [[Watch Video](#)]
- CHW In-depth interview with Satta Johnson [[Watch Video](#)]
- CHW In-depth interview with Shnika Spearman [[Watch Video](#)]

CASE STUDY 2.1 | COMMUNITY HEALTH WORKER SYMPOSIUM

The symposium aimed to connect activities that focused on CHWs within the CDCC, link projects that supported keeping CHW models sustainable, and understand the benefits and challenges faced by RADx-UP projects in maintaining CHWs in research and practice. The event also worked to emphasize the important role CHWs play in increasing access to COVID-19 testing for underserved communities.

Discussions led by CHWs covered the services they provided and the need for funding that would last overtime. These conversations created a feedback loop, giving community members a chance to share their needs and ideas, making sure that health programs responded to local concerns. Two key points from the event were:

- CHWs are vital to pandemic responses because they offer services that reach beyond what healthcare systems usually provide.
- Programs designed to support CHWs need stable funding to ensure long-term health equity.

The inclusion of keynote speakers and the formation of a CHW Advisory Group improved event planning while highlighting the important contributions CHWs make to RADx-UP projects. The lessons from the symposium offer valuable insights for future public health emergencies, underscoring the need to integrate CHWs into plans for emergency preparedness and response.

Resource Spotlight**RADx-UP PROJECT CHW PUBLICATIONS**

- Community health workers as Puentes/bridges to increase COVID-19 health equity in Latinx communities of the Southwest U.S. [[Visit Website](#)]
- Co-creating a theory of change to advance COVID-19 testing and vaccine uptake in underserved communities [[Visit Website](#)]
- Effectiveness of a COVID-19 testing outreach intervention for Latinx communities: A cluster randomized trial [[Visit Website](#)]
- A pragmatic randomized trial of home-based testing for COVID-19 in rural Native American and Latino communities [[Visit Website](#)]
- Exploration of multilevel barriers and strategies that affected early COVID-19 vaccination and testing [[Visit Website](#)]

CASE STUDY 2.2

ACAP PRESENTATION SERIES

The Advancing Community-Academic Partnerships Presentation Series (ACAP), part of the Equity Evidence Academy (EA), aimed at sharing promising approaches and lessons learned between RADx-UP project teams. ACAP presentations allowed EA attendees to:

- Gain an increased understanding of the importance of community engagement in community-engaged research.
- Learn new promising practices and strategies for developing, implementing, and maintaining equitable community-academic research partnerships.
- Learn how RADx-UP project teams are translating promising practices and strategies into other COVID-19 testing and vaccine projects and/or other community-engaged research projects.

The ACAP Presentation Series was an opportunity for RADx-UP project teams of all kinds to share their effective models of community-engaged research partnerships between community organizations and academic institutions. Teams were encouraged to submit a presentation, and to work collaboratively to co-develop and co-present their presentation. Event attendees include RADx-UP project team members from community organizations and academic institutions, RADx-UP CDCC staff members, NIH leaders and project officers, and others involved in the outcomes of RADx-UP.

ACAP VIDEO SUMMARY:

FIGHT COVID MILWAUKEE: PARTNERSHIPS FOR TRUSTED MESSAGING & COMMUNITY-ENGAGED RESEARCH
 Dr. Desha Levy, PhD, RN, FAHA
 Dr. Hope Minichino, and
 Dr. John Meyer, MD, MBA, Professor and Director, MCW Institute for Health & Equity
 BESSE LEVY, MEDICAL COLLEGE OF WISCONSIN
 FIGHT COVID MILWAUKEE PROJECT TEAM MEMBER
 CO-PRESENTED BY PASTOR CLIFFORD TAYLOR, WORD OF HOPE MINISTRIES
 AND JOHN MEYER, MEDICAL COLLEGE OF WISCONSIN

[\[Watch Video\]](#)

CASE STUDY 2.2 | ACAP PRESENTATION SERIES

Presentation abstracts that responded to and met the criteria were invited to submit a poster for display in a virtual gallery. Abstracts that received the highest scores by the ACAP Review Committee were invited to provide oral presentations during the event. Oral presentations' participating community partners received \$1,000 for their time and effort.

The [inaugural ACAP](#) featured four oral and 12 poster presentations by RADx-UP community-academic project partnerships. The teams emphasized tailored approaches to meeting individual community needs.

FIGURE 2.2: HIGHLIGHTED ACAP PROJECT PRESENTATION SUMMARIES

CASE STUDY 2.3

PARTNERING FOR IMPACT PUBLICATION WORKSHOP SERIES

The P4I program was created to help communities get involved in writing **publications**, especially ones using data from the RADx-UP Data Hub. These publications required at least one community partner on the writing team.

This process includes a set of steps and support mechanisms for the development, preparation, and review of scholarly products (abstracts, scientific presentations, manuscripts) derived from information and aggregated data from across the RADx-UP research project teams.

P4I workshops were designed to bolster the capacity building of participants by enhancing their understanding of peer-reviewed journals and the workings of the publication process.

GLOSSARY

Publications Materials that are written, printed, or digitally produced and shared publicly

PARTNERING FOR IMPACT VIDEO OVERVIEW:

[\[Watch Video\]](#)

RADx-UP projects' community partners were invited to attend a series of 12 capacity-building workshops to explore RADx-UP's support mechanisms for writing, with a focus on crafting compelling manuscript outlines. These workshops sought to equip attendees with essential strategies for selecting the most suitable journals and effectively submitting their manuscripts. The curriculum not only emphasized linking individual research to existing published discourse but also reviewed citation managers and literature searches.

CASE STUDY 2.3 | PARTNERING FOR IMPACT PUBLICATION WORKSHOP SERIES

- ESSENTIAL DOCUMENTS FOR IMPLEMENTATION**
-
- **Concept Proposal Template** — The statistics team along with P4I group created a template that researchers could use to submit their research idea for consideration (and requests for participation) by members of the consortium
 - **Analysis Proposal Template** — Template for writing team leads to submit an analysis proposal after their concept had been made available online for at least 14 days.
 - **Statistical Analysis Plan Template** — Once an analysis proposal was reviewed and approved by Partnering for impact, the statistics team met with each individual writing team to create a unique SAP for that manuscript. Statistical analysis plan tailored for each manuscript.
 - **RADx-UP Publications Policy** — CDCC policy created for all individuals involved with writing or reviewing abstracts, presentations, and manuscripts.

RADx-UP invited community partners to attend 12 workshops designed to teach them about writing for academic publications. The workshops focused on topics such as creating clear outlines for manuscript introductions, using citation managers, and conducting literature searches. These sessions aimed to build skills and increase the overall success of community and academic teams working together.

Some community partners joined the workshops and planned to be part of writing teams. However, others felt that their time was better spent directly engaging with their communities, especially during a PHE.

Videos and slides from the P4I Publication Workshop Series can be found in the Resource Toolkit section of this chapter.

CASE STUDY 2.4

CCPH COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT SERVICES AND TRAININGS

CCPH, a nonprofit membership organization that promotes health equity and social justice through partnerships between communities and academic institutions, played a pivotal role in capacity building and community engagement by offering essential training and support tailored for RADx-UP projects. As a co-lead of the CDCC Community Engagement Core, CCPH provided expertise in fostering community engagement through a comprehensive onboarding toolkit designed for the Engagement Impact Teams (EITS).

Onboarding Toolkit for EITs

The CCPH Best Practices for Community Engagement Training (See Appendix B.2) served as a resource for EITs, equipping them with the necessary tools to cultivate and sustain equitable partnerships. CCPH emphasized a community-centered, participatory approach, ensuring that the focus remained on building capacity and optimizing outcomes for all involved. By leveraging their extensive knowledge and providing targeted technical assistance, CCPH sought to empower RADx-UP projects to enhance their community engagement efforts.

CCPH's Training and Office Hours

The CCPH team hosted Office Hours and trainings tailored to assist CBOs and academic institutions involved in RADx-UP projects nationwide. These virtual consultations aimed to address challenges in increasing COVID-19 testing uptake and maximizing community engagement by providing tailored recommendations, resource lists, and support in refining engagement strategies and partnerships.

The CCPH RADx-UP team, composed of experienced facilitators, provided dynamic training sessions that covered various essential topics, including community engagement frameworks and effective communication techniques. These quarterly trainings were designed to build capacity among community partners and academic collaborators, ensuring they are well-prepared to navigate the complexities of health promotion and partnership sustainability in their endeavors.

CASE STUDY 2.4 | CCPH COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT SERVICES AND TRAININGS

CCPH Lunch & Learn Series

CCPH hosted eight short, interactive workshops to improve community-academic partnerships with real-world examples and opportunities to practice. Recordings from the series in English and Spanish, as well as slide decks and additional resources, are housed on the [CCPH website](#).

Resource Spotlight

- Best Practices for Community Engagement Training (See Appendix B.2)
- CCPH Office Hours Flowchart (See Appendix B.3)
- CCPH Principles of Partnership [[Visit Website](#)]

Key Takeaways for Future Public Health Emergencies

Insights from the RADx-UP program, drawn from participant feedback, publications, and community engagement activities, offer valuable guidance for future efforts in building and sustaining CoPs. These lessons are summarized below:

- 1. Professional Development:** Integrate training and skill-building opportunities into CoP activities.
- 2. Information Sharing:** Use regular meetings and accessible digital tools to promote knowledge exchange.
- 3. Relationship Building:** Prioritize trust and collaboration through relationship-focused activities.
- 4. Collective Learning:** Leverage community experiences to create shared resources.
- 5. Sustained Engagement:** Conduct regular reflection to innovate and maintain member commitment.
- 6. Feedback Loops:** Incorporate external perspectives to adapt and integrate innovative solutions.

Conclusion

The RADx-UP program shows how partner capacity building and supporting CoPs can help improve public health projects. CoPs focus on activities like professional development, sharing information, and building relationships to give community members a stronger role in public health work. Likewise, programs such as the C2G Webinar Series and the CHW Symposium show the importance of clear communication and skill-building for successful community-academic partnerships. These programs offer helpful tools, advice, and places to exchange ideas, giving community organizations and academic groups the skills they need for managing grants, teamwork, and partnerships.

RADx-UP highlights how important it is to create welcoming spaces where people can work together and learn. It also emphasizes the value of sharing information, being open, and keeping communities involved over time. As public health keeps changing, CoPs and approaches centered on communities will continue to play a key role in preparing communities to handle challenges and to achieve fair health results. These methods help create long-term solutions and positive changes in public health.

Toolkit

1. FEATURED RADx-UP RESOURCES

Practical resources developed directly by the CDCC or RADx-UP projects. These may include publications, guides, or curated tools specific to implementing a program like the RADx-UP initiative.

- **RADx-UP CDCC Community Engagement Framework** — The Community Engagement Core's framework is intended to assist CDCC leadership and staff in effectively managing interactions and initiatives across various contexts. Although primarily an internal resource, it provides practical guidance for engaging diverse audiences, including internal team members and external partners. This flexible framework prioritizes inclusivity and responsiveness, addressing the complexities of collaborating with multiple partners at different stages of engagement. (See Appendix B.1)
- **Opportunities to Enhance Health Equity by Integrating Community Health Workers into Payment and Care Delivery Reforms** — Policy paper from Duke-Margolis Center for Health Policy, UNC Center for Health Equity Research and Duke Clinical Research Institute delivers policy recommendations to enhance and prioritize CHW models into existing healthcare transformation reforms to address health inequities in the U.S. [[Visit Website](#)]
- **CCPH Principles of Partnership** — The CCPH Guiding Principles of Partnership are not meant to be prescriptive or adopted verbatim but rather to be used for discussion or as a model for developing one's own principles of partnership. [[Visit Website](#)]

CHWs sharing their insights and advice from the field:

- **Insights from CHWs** [[Watch Video](#)]
- **CHW In-depth interview with Satta Johnson** [[Watch Video](#)]
- **CHW In-depth interview with Shnika Spearman** [[Watch Video](#)]

Related to C2G Grant Application Webinar Series:

This three-part webinar series was designed to guide community-based organizations through the full lifecycle of applying for and managing a grant. Each session provides practical tips on navigating pre-award preparation, budget development, and post-award responsibilities.

- **Part 1: Getting Started, an Overview of the Pre-Award Process** — This 3-part webinar series was developed to give community partners a step-by-step guide on writing and submitting grant applications. [[Watch Video](#)]
- **Part 2: How to Develop a Grant Budget and Budget Justification** — This 3-part webinar series was developed to give community partners a step-by-step guide on writing and submitting grant applications. [[Watch Video](#)]
- **Part 3: An Overview of the Post-Award Process** — This 3-part webinar series was developed to give community partners a step-by-step guide on writing and submitting grant applications. [[Watch Video](#)]

***Disclaimer:** These webinars were created based on NIH guidance available at the time of recording. Some information may no longer reflect current NIH policies or procedures.*

Related to P4I Publication Workshop Series:

The P4I Publication Workshop Series supported community partners and researchers in co-developing scholarly products using RADx-UP data. This 12-part series covered the full publication process — from concept development and journal selection to writing, submission, and responding to reviewer feedback — with an emphasis on community-engaged authorship and shared learning.

- **Workshop #1: The Analysis Concept and Proposal Process** — Gain insight into how to submit the concept and analysis proposal as part of the Partnering for Impact Consortial Publications Process. (No video available.)
- **Workshop #2: The Data Dashboard & Data Linkage Dashboard** — Training where our data experts share how to navigate the data dashboard and generate ideas for an analysis concept using RADx-UP aggregated data. (No video available.)
- **Workshop #3: Journal Selection** [[Download PDF](#)] — Take a deep dive into the recommendations from a published author to learn how to navigate which journal is most appropriate for your manuscript. [[Watch Video](#)]
- **Workshop #4: Journal Submission** [[Download PDF](#)] — Learn how to navigate journal submissions and gain understanding of journal requirements. [[Watch Video](#)]
- **Workshop #5: An Introduction to Utilizing Research Search Engines** [[Download PDF](#)] — Strengthen your manuscript with published articles that can be used as reference. [[Watch Video](#)]
- **Workshop #6: Using Citation Manager** [[Download PDF](#)] — Learn how to use citation managers to organize your research and make creating a bibliography easier. [[Watch Video](#)]
- **Workshop #7: Writing the “Introduction”** [[Download PDF](#)] — Don’t let writing a manuscript be intimidating. Our presenter will take us through each section, starting with the Introduction, and provide mentorship to support you throughout the process. [[Watch Video](#)]
- **Workshop #8: Writing the “Methods”** [[Download PDF](#)] — Next in the manuscript development process is the methods section. Learn from our presenter on how to best approach completing the methods section. [[Watch Video](#)]
- **Workshop #9: Writing the “Results”** [[Download PDF](#)] — Next in the manuscript development process is the results section. Learn from the presenter on how to best approach completing the results section. [[Watch Video](#)]
- **Workshop #10: Writing the “Discussion”** [[Download PDF](#)] — The end of the manuscript will be a discussion of results. Learn from the presenter on how to best approach completing the discussion section. [[Watch Video](#)]
- **Workshop #11: Dealing with Reviews** [[Download PDF](#)] — Once a manuscript is submitted to a journal, it must go through a review process. Learn from the presenter on how to best approach dealing with reviews. [[Watch Video](#)]
- **Panel with Q&A: A Discussion on Community-Engaged Research & Publications** — Watch a panel discussion by Partnering for Impact Workshop presenters about community-engaged research and publications. [[Watch Video](#)]

2. SUPPLEMENTAL RESOURCES

Resources developed outside the CDCC but shared via the Engagement Resource Center or by project partners. These materials offer supplemental value and represent real-world utility during a PHE response.

- **Community Health Worker Best Practice Toolkits for Designing, Implementing, and Showing the Impact of CHW Programs** — A series of toolkits have been developed in collaboration with CHWs and CHW allies with extensive expertise in CHW model implementation in both community-based and healthcare settings. Contribution to best practices for engaging with community health workers. This was a trusted external resource selected for the RADx-UP Engagement Resource Center not created with RADx-UP funds. [[Visit Website](#)]
- **Hispanic Services Council Social Needs Screening Tool (English/Spanish)** — Developed by the Hispanic Services Council in Tampa, Florida, a collaborative partner in the RADx-UP project, this resource consists of a 10-question survey designed to identify participants' unmet needs concerning housing, food, utilities, and other essential areas. Participants can also express their desire for additional resources and support. This resource is accessible in both English and Spanish. (See Appendix B.4)
- **CATCH-UP: Practice Assessment** — This document provides a tool for assessing which strategies are in place in a primary care practice when it comes to improving COVID-19 care. It also provides a mechanism for prioritizing practice improvement activities. (See Appendix B.5)

3. “DOWNLOAD & DO” — READY-TO-USE TOOLS

This section includes hands-on templates, workflows, sample communications, onboarding documents, planning checklists, data collection tools, or forms for immediate application.

- **Best Practices for Community Engagement Training** — CDCC/CCPH onboarding training for EITs on best practices for community engagement. This resource primer includes an overview of the best practices for community engagement. (See Appendix B.2)
- **CCPH Office Hours Flowchart** — This document is a flowchart with information about CCPH and their process for office hours. (See Appendix B.3)

4. RELEVANT PUBLICATIONS

A list of publications, data sources, or scholarly work that support the evidence base and offer pathways for further reading.

- Barrett ES, Andrews TR, Roy J, et al. Community- versus health care organization-based approaches to expanding at-home COVID-19 testing in Black and Latino communities, New Jersey, 2021. *Am J Public Health.* 2022;112:S918-S922. <https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2022.306989>
- Berkley-Patton J, Thompson CB, Templeton T, et al. COVID-19 Testing in African American Churches Using a Faith Health– Academic Partnership. *Am J Public Health.* 2022;112:S887-S891, <https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2022.306981>
- Rodriguez NM, Martinez RG, Ziolkowski R, et al. “COVID knocked me straight into the dirt”: perspectives from people experiencing homelessness on the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic. *BMC Public Health.* 2022;22:1327. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-022-13748-y>
- Stadnick NA, Cain KL, Watson P, et al. Engaging underserved communities in COVID-19 health equity implementation research: An analysis of community engagement resource needs and costs. *Front Health Serv.* 2022; 2:850427. doi: 10.3389/frhs.2022.850427
- Strathee SA, Abramovitz D, Harvey-Vera AY, et al. A brief peer-led intervention to increase COVID-19 vaccine uptake among people who inject drugs in San Diego County: Results from a pilot randomized controlled trial. *Open Forum Infect Dis.* 2023; 10(8):ofad392. doi: 10.1093/ofid/ofad392

PHOTO COURTESY RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

SECTION TWO: Implementing the Program

SECTION TWO OVERVIEW

PHOTO COURTESY RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

The RADx-UP CDCC comprises four pillars: the Data Science & Biostatistics Core, the Community Engagement Core, the Testing Core, and the Administrative Core. These pillars provided essential expertise and guidance to researchers working with underserved populations. This section of the playbook provides a detailed exploration of how the program was operationalized, from testing to data collection to best practices in community engagement. With a strong foundation of community-based research and a national coordination effort, RADx-UP used adaptive, inclusive, and responsive strategies to expand COVID-19 testing and build equitable infrastructure for a public health response.

Chapter 3: Supporting Diagnostic Testing in Underserved Populations

Summary:

This chapter explores how the RADx-UP Testing Core supported projects nationwide to provide equitable testing access to underserved populations through technical assistance, procurement systems, and community-informed innovations.

Key Topics Covered:

- Role of the Testing Core in test selection, procurement, and distribution
- Creation of testing resources, guides, and rapid pilot projects
- Collaborative efforts with working groups and community partners
- Development and dissemination of public education materials
- Case studies including Say Yes! COVID Test program and making testing materials accessible for all

Chapter 4: Data Collection and Storage

Summary:

This chapter details how data was gathered, standardized, and used to inform public health action within RADx-UP. It highlights the critical balance between rapid response and robust, ethical data practices.

Key Topics Covered:

- Design and deployment of Common Data Elements (CDEs)
- Community-informed data collection and consent processes
- Data sharing protocols, especially in Tribal Nation contexts
- Dashboards, core analytic datasets, and harmonization efforts
- Case studies on Long COVID data, Tribal data sovereignty, and Engagement Impact Team (EIT) support models

“RADx-UP rapidly developed community-informed Common Data Elements and implemented rigorous data collection across a large consortium, overcoming language barriers, technical challenges and data privacy concerns. We learned many lessons in the process and believe that our work provides a strong foundation for future community-engaged research projects.”

LISA WRUCK, PHD
Co-Principal Investigator,
RADx-UP Coordination and
Data Collection Center

Chapter 5: Best Practices for Conducting Community-Engaged Research

Summary:

Focusing on trust, partnership, and mutual respect, this chapter showcases best practices for meaningful community engagement in public health research and how RADx-UP operationalized these principles throughout the program.

Key Topics Covered:

- Frameworks and principles for community engagement (CTSA, AAMC)
- RADx-UP community engagement strategies and partner types
- Use of the RADx-UP Image Bank, Equity Evidence Academy, and Engagement Resource Center
- Case studies on local branding, feedback systems, and relationship-building
- Emphasis on co-leadership and trust in research partnerships

Lessons Learned in this Section

Implementing the RADx-UP initiative across a diverse range of communities revealed critical insights. Community engagement is not only foundational but also essential for both successful program implementation and long-term public trust. Responsive data strategies that incorporate consent, transparency, and cultural relevance ensure both ethical integrity and actionable insight. And finally, equitable testing access requires flexible, community-driven models with strong technical and logistical support. These lessons will shape the future of inclusive, effective public health responses.

“What we’re learning through this work is that we’re putting our communities everywhere in a strong position to face another community disaster or other communicable diseases that come in the future.”

GISELLE CORBIE, MD, MSC
Co-Principal Investigator,
RADx-UP Coordination and
Data Collection Center

How do you make testing more accessible for everyone?

Public health emergency response requires defining and identifying cases using the appropriate testing technology. Identified cases lead to mitigation and interventions. When COVID-19 rose to the level of being declared a public health emergency, many underserved populations lacked access to reliable testing. This chapter demonstrates how RADx-UP's Testing Core changed that story. By supporting over 130 projects nationwide, the Testing Core provided hands-on guidance with test selection, procurement, and implementation, especially in underserved populations.

Key Topics Covered

- How the Testing Core supported local testing strategies with procurement, regulatory guidance, and real-time assistance
- Creation of easy-to-understand resources and public education tools for underserved populations
- Rapid pilot projects for innovative testing methods and delivery approaches
- Understanding barriers to testing and building community-informed solutions

In Your Toolkit

Find sample emails, step-by-step guides, and real-life examples to help you plan testing programs that reach everyone. Use practical tools to team up with local groups, adjust testing to fit your community's needs, and see what's working. Whether you're getting ready for a future health emergency or working to fix current gaps, these resources can help you create fair and effective testing solutions.

Case Examples

The chapter features real-life examples of innovation in testing outreach to underserved populations:

- **Reaching underserved populations at risk:** A mobile lab tested people experiencing homelessness.
- **Communicating with target audiences using participatory methods:** Teens helped design solutions through “design-athons” for inclusive testing campaigns.
- **Nationwide At-home Testing Pilot:** The Say Yes! COVID-19 Test campaign gave out millions of free at-home tests across the U.S.

These stories demonstrate how local partnerships, creativity, and trust made testing more accessible—and how those lessons can inform future public health responses.

OVERVIEW

CHAPTER THREE: SUPPORTING DIAGNOSTIC TESTING IN UNDERSERVED POPULATIONS

PHOTO COURTESY RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

Background

Testing is an important tool in any public health emergency. It helps find cases early and connect people to care. But during the COVID-19 pandemic, many communities had a hard time getting tested (Willems et al., 2022). Barriers such as limited access to healthcare, mistrust stemming from historical and ongoing medical injustices, and the spread of **misinformation** about COVID-19 contributed to uneven testing uptake. These factors interacted with broader social and structural inequities, influencing testing behaviors and access.

RADx-UP was created to help fix these problems. The Testing Core worked with over 130 local projects across the country. They gave advice, helped choose the right tests, and shared tools that made testing easier to understand and use. As the pandemic changed, so did the rules and resources.

As more people were vaccinated and COVID-19 cases declined, participant recruitment became increasingly challenging, prompting many studies to shift their focus. Conducting research in resource-scarce areas, such as rural regions or prisons, presented additional logistical and operational difficulties. These challenges necessitated innovative approaches to collect and test samples while ensuring safety and regulatory compliance. The Testing Core helped teams adjust by giving real-time updates, simple guides, and clear instructions in different languages. They also helped build trust by working closely with local groups.

GLOSSARY

Misinformation False or misleading information that can spread quickly and impact public understanding

This chapter shares examples of how RADx-UP made testing fairer and more available. These stories show how teamwork, trust, and quick support can improve public health in any emergency.

RADx-UP COVID-19 Testing Core

The RADx-UP COVID-19 Testing Core, along with the Data Science and Biostatistics Core, the Administrative Core, and Community Engagement Core, was one of the four pillars of the RADx-UP CDCC. The Testing Core's role was to partner with community-engaged project teams to offer scientific expertise and guidance on COVID-19 **diagnostics**. The Testing Core supported testing projects by reviewing project plans, providing technical support, giving scientific and study design guidance, and helping with test procurement as needed. They created assessment tools to make sure the research teams' testing strategy met study goals for their populations served and provided brief reports to keep study teams updated on changes in rules.

GLOSSARY

Diagnostics A test or method to figure out what disease/condition a person has

COVID-19 TESTING DEFINITIONS

- **At-home testing:** Diagnostic tests that individuals can perform at home without the need for professional supervision. These tests are designed to be simple to use and provide quick results.
- **Point-of-care tests:** Diagnostic tests conducted at the time and place of patient care, such as a doctor's office, hospital, or clinic. They provide rapid results, allowing for immediate clinical decision-making.
- **Diagnostics:** This term encompasses all tests and procedures used to identify the presence of a disease or condition. In the context of COVID-19, diagnostics include various methods to detect the virus or the body's response to it.
- **Emergency-use authorized tests:** These tests are approved by the FDA for use during emergency situations, such as the COVID-19 pandemic. They are authorized based on the best available evidence at the time to ensure timely diagnostics in critical conditions.
- **Laboratory-developed tests:** These tests are created and used within a single laboratory. They do not undergo the same approval processes as FDA-authorized test kits but must comply with certain regulatory standards to ensure accuracy.
- **FDA-authorized test kits:** These are commercially available test kits that have undergone FDA review and been authorized for use. They meet specific standards for accuracy and reliability, making them suitable for widespread public use.
- **Clinical Laboratory Improvement Amendments (CLIA) approved:** Tests approved under CLIA meet regulatory standards for laboratory testing to ensure the accuracy, reliability, and timeliness of test results, crucial for effective public health response.
- **Home collection devices:** These are tools provided to individuals to collect samples (such as saliva or nasal swabs) at home, which are then sent to a laboratory for analysis. They provide a convenient and safe way to conduct COVID-19 testing without visiting a healthcare facility.

Source: U.S. Food and Drug Administration. COVID-19 Test Basics. [\[Visit Website\]](#)

Protocol Review and Testing Plan

- The Testing Core reviewed the scientific and study design of each project, provided technical support for test methods, gave advice on FDA regulatory issues, and helped procure the tests.
- The Testing Core worked closely with the FDA and advised research projects on evolving regulatory guidance, such as regarding which tests were approved for emergency use, the differences between lab-made tests and FDA-approved test kits, and whether tests needed to be approved under CLIA.
- The Testing Core kept a repository of emerging technologies — a source of information about COVID-19 tests, including point-of-care tests, home collection devices, and at-home testing, and offered quick reference guides to help projects' choose tests.

Vendor Management and Supply Chain

The Testing Core supported RADx-UP projects in accessing COVID-19 tests by collaborating with more than 80 diagnostic suppliers. In future public health emergencies, a centralized Testing Core could serve as a key resource for oversight, guidance, and **procurement**, acting as an intermediary between research teams and test manufacturers.

Collaborative Efforts to Support Understanding Testing

With Testing Core support, the **Communities of Practice** worked to understand and improve testing barriers. The RADx-UP Working Groups shared ideas, created resources, and published papers. They worked with the Group Model Building (GMB) team to make visual tools that show how people understand testing information and how their social interactions affect each other. The diagrams help explain the challenges of virus testing in underserved communities.

For example, the Building Community Capacity & Impact Working Group [made a diagram](#) showing how different parts of a system or program influence each other and lead to changes in how misinformation and missing information affect fair testing.

GLOSSARY

Procurement Finding, buying, getting, and inspecting a product (like COVID tests)

Communities of Practice Group collaborating across fields to share knowledge and grow professionally

The Social Determinants of COVID-19 Testing and Vaccination Working Group [made a diagram](#) and table to explore how social determinants of health (**SDoH**) affect COVID-19 testing and vaccine uptake. It also includes figures showing pathways for community engagement that address transportation and access to testing, digital and **health literacy**, and social needs screenings and help.

The Child Health Working Group led two collaborative efforts to bring evidence from child health and return-to-school projects through a curated collection of papers in the journal Pediatrics.

The Testing Core aimed to provide guidance about and facilitation of testing technologies and resources to communities served. Ultimately, RADx-UP was able to collect nearly 500,000 test results over the pandemic and distribute millions of tests for personal use within communities served.

GLOSSARY

SDoH Conditions in the environments where people live, work, and learn that affect health outcomes

Health literacy The ability to find, understand, and use health information to make informed decisions

FIGURE 3.1: RADx-UP COVID-19 TESTS SUBMITTED VIA THE NIH RADx-UP CDES

Resource Spotlight

JOURNAL PUBLICATIONS

- A Systems Perspective of How Community-Engaged Public Health Addresses Social Determinants of Health: A Case Study of a Population-Based COVID-19 Testing Program [\[Visit Website\]](#)
- Navigating a Pandemic in the K-12 Setting: Keeping Our School Communities Safe. [\[Visit Website\]](#)
- Navigating a Pandemic in the K-12 Setting, Part 2: COVID-19 Testing and Vaccination. [\[Visit Website\]](#)

EQUITABLE COVID-19 TESTING: A MULTI-PERSPECTIVE VIEW OF THE COMPLEXITIES

Group Model Building causal loop diagrams visually represent how different elements of a system or intervention are connected, paying specific attention to how different elements interact or cause one another to change.

- Building Community Capacity & Impact: Diagram that explores the impact of missing information and of misinformation on testing [\[Visit Website\]](#)
- Social Determinants of COVID-19 Testing and Vaccination: Diagram that explores the impact of social determinants of health on testing [\[Visit Website\]](#)

RADx-UP Testing Research Insights

RADx-UP projects collected data about the differences in infection rates, disease progression, health outcomes, access to healthcare, and more. They used these data to write publications that revealed the barriers and solutions to improve testing and vaccination in underserved communities.

Researchers found social, ethical, and behavioral implications factors related to testing and vaccination. Disparities in testing and vaccination hesitancy, motivation, access, and uptake exist among different underserved populations. Programs like **in-reach** and **outreach** through clinics, mobile units, reduced-cost/free testing and vaccination, employer-sponsored resources, and at-home testing improved access and uptake to COVID-19 testing and vaccination.

GLOSSARY

In-reach engages individuals already connected to a program by providing additional services or support. **Outreach** targets external audiences, especially underserved populations, to build trust, raise awareness, and deliver health services or information.

FACTORS THAT AFFECTED TESTING AND VACCINATION

SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS	INTERPERSONAL AND SOCIAL FACTORS	ENVIRONMENTAL, COMMUNITY, AND OTHER SOCIO-POLITICAL FACTORS	STRUCTURAL FACTORS
<p>The data showed greater vaccination hesitancy among Black/African American, Hispanic/Latino, and Asian American, Native Hawaiian, and Pacific Islander populations. Other factors such as age, education, employment, socioeconomic status, presence of comorbidities, political affiliation, access to health care, and having been vaccinated against COVID-19 were associated with testing uptake. Other individual-level factors (misinformation, lack of buy-in, fear of testing positive) also affected uptake.</p>	<p>Misinformation increased testing and vaccination hesitancy. Trusted messengers, especially people within social networks and healthcare providers, were crucial in addressing hesitancy and improving uptake.</p>	<p>Vulnerable populations faced disparities in testing and vaccination access based on social determinants (e.g., transportation and language barriers). Facilitators at the community, organizational, and governmental levels improved access, acceptance, and uptake, including in-school testing, syringe exchange programs, and state-run free testing sites.</p>	<p>Researchers found that a lack of staff to implement testing and limited internet access to telehealth (especially for Tribal Nations) affected testing rates. Transportation or driving times, location of centers or services, inflexible work schedules, fear of losing employment while getting tested, wait times or scheduling, fear of exposure while waiting to be tested, and the cost of testing impacted uptake.</p>

Researchers identified a host of strategies to address barriers to testing. These included convenient vaccination locations or mobile vaccination services, culturally tailored vaccine literacy campaigns in multiple languages, employer support, and insurance coverage of vaccinations. In addition, providing testing in heavily traveled areas (e.g., supermarkets, churches, schools, neighborhoods), offering transportation and incentives, improving communication about testing, and outreach to local employers to accommodate clinical visits were ways to address barriers to testing.

Resource Spotlight

- Examining COVID-19 testing and vaccination behaviors by heritage and linguistic preferences among Hispanic, Latino, or Spanish RADx-UP participants. [[Visit Website](#)]; (See Appendix C.1 for lay summary); [[Watch Video](#)]

Case Studies

The case studies in this chapter showcase the diverse strategies used by RADx-UP projects to enhance access to COVID-19 testing in underserved communities. These efforts reflect how community-informed, technically supported approaches can reduce testing disparities and improve public health response through innovation, tailored outreach, and collaborative implementation.

- 1. Rapid Research Pilot Program:** CDCC funded 25 small-scale, community-based projects to test innovative diagnostic approaches, emphasizing outreach to marginalized groups including those experiencing homelessness and housing instability.
- 2. Making Testing Information Accessible for All:** CDCC developed accessible, culturally tailored educational resources—including videos and flyers—to improve understanding and confidence in COVID-19 testing and vaccination among low-literacy populations.
- 3. Partnering with the U.S. Food and Drug Administration:** The RADx-UP Testing Core collaborated with the FDA during the COVID-19 pandemic to prioritize diagnostic tool reviews, facilitate regulatory guidance for underserved communities, and improve test accessibility, exemplifying the critical role of partnership between research entities and regulatory agencies in enhancing public health responses.
- 4. Sharing Testing Resource Information Dissemination:** Testing Core shared timely, practical information on test types, regulatory updates, and selection strategies through web resources, quick-reference guides, and project-wide communications.
- 5. Say Yes! COVID Test (SYCT) and You & Me COVID-Free (YMCF) Toolkit for Engaging Diverse Communities:** CDCC created from the Say Yes! COVID Test and You & Me COVID-Free campaigns, this toolkit outlines best practices for designing and implementing community-engaged public health programs in underserved areas.

PHOTO COURTESY RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

CASE STUDY 3.1

RAPID RESEARCH PILOT PROGRAM

The RADx-UP CDCC managed a subaward program, the Rapid Research Pilot Program (RP2), to fund small-scale research initiatives focused on improving access to and the uptake of COVID-19 diagnostic testing in underserved and vulnerable communities. The program sought to identify the factors contributing to the disproportionate effects of COVID-19 on these groups and to develop targeted interventions to address disparities.

CASE STUDY 3.1 | RAPID RESEARCH PILOT PROGRAM

Researchers applied for up to \$200,000 in funding to conduct community-engaged studies within a 1-year timeframe. The program encouraged applications from community health departments, historically Black colleges and universities, tribally controlled colleges and universities, Hispanic-serving institutions, and other minority-serving institutions, as well as from industry, tech incubators, innovation offices, and government entities. Ultimately, 25 subawards were funded through the RADx-UP CDCC.

Novel RP2 projects included:

- **Crowdsourcing Innovative Technologies:** This project encourages community members to find new testing tools.
- **Youth and Teen Engagement:** Using “designathons” to involve young people in creating a self-testing method
- **Mobile Laboratory:** Studying how to provide accessible testing to homeless and transitional populations. Project profile video [\[Watch Video\]](#)

FROM THE FRONT LINES

RADx-UP Grants for Research, Testing, and Community Engagement with Dr. Priya Sarin Gupta, MD, MPH. [\[Watch Video\]](#)

FIGURE 3.3: RADx-UP RAPID RESEARCH PILOT PROJECTS AT A GLANCE

Collected in the RADx-UP Publications Dashboard as of May, 2025

PUBLISHED MAY 2025

CASE STUDY 3.2

MAKING TESTING INFORMATION ACCESSIBLE FOR ALL

The CDCC responded to requests from the projects for evidence-based lay-friendly materials about COVID-19 testing and vaccination that could be shared broadly among the people most impacted by the virus. These included flyers about when to test after someone was vaccinated, how to use a popular at-home COVID test, and a video about the importance of testing, even after the introduction of vaccines. RADx-UP projects tailored their community-facing messaging for the communities they served through representative language and images.

Flyers/Posters/Handouts

- [“I’m Vaccinated - When Do I Need to Get Tested for COVID-19?”](#) — The flyer, available in English and Spanish, helps people understand when they should get tested for COVID-19 after being vaccinated.

CASE STUDY 3.2 | MAKING TESTING INFORMATION ACCESSIBLE FOR ALL

Videos

- *The How to Test with Flowflex* video series—developed by the RADx-UP Testing Core in collaboration with the FDA, ACON Laboratories, and the Social Determinants of COVID-19 Testing and Vaccination Working Group. These videos, available in English and Spanish and tailored for both adults and youth, were created to promote test utilization and build trust in COVID-19 testing across diverse communities.

How to Test with a *FlowFlex* COVID-19 At-Home Test

- [[Watch in English](#)]
- [[Watch in Spanish](#)]
- [[Ages 2-13 Years – Watch in English](#)]

How to Read Results of Your FlowFlex COVID-19 Rapid At-home Test

- [[Watch in English](#)]
- [[Watch in Spanish](#)]

- Public-facing video about the importance of testing in the environment of vaccination and low rates of COVID-19.

- [[Watch in English](#)]
- [[Watch in Spanish](#)]

CASE STUDY 3.3

PARTNERING WITH THE U.S. FOOD AND DRUG ADMINISTRATION

In the early days of the COVID-19 pandemic, the RADx-UP Testing Core began working with the Food and Drug Administration (FDA), especially with Dr. Tim Stenzel from the Office of In Vitro Diagnostics and Radiological Health. This partnership helped ensure that the diagnostic tools needed for the RADx-UP initiative were given priority and followed changing federal rules.

From 2021 to 2023, the Testing Core stayed in close contact with the FDA, meeting as needed to discuss how to help underserved communities. These discussions included topics such as regulatory guidance and laboratory-developed tests, and reviewing materials such as training videos for at-home COVID-19 test kits.

Some key outcomes of this collaboration were:

- The FDA reviewed data from RADx-UP projects that submitted laboratory-developed tests or asked for emergency use authorization, allowing the agency to prioritize its reviews to promote health equity.
- The Testing Core acted as a bridge between underserved communities and the FDA, making sure the challenges faced by these populations were considered in real-time decisions.
- Although the NIH eventually decided to focus only on FDA authorized commercial tests instead of non-authorized assays, the Testing Core's work with the FDA helped make the transition smoother by securing the necessary reviews and advice.

CASE STUDY 3.3 | PARTNERING WITH THE U.S. FOOD AND DRUG ADMINISTRATION

One big success from this partnership was an instructional video for the *Flowflex* COVID-19 at-home test kit. The FDA gave feedback that led to accessibility improvements, like making the video easier to use for people with low vision. This highlighted the importance of making testing instructions clear and accessible for everyone.

This case shows how important it is for research groups and regulatory agencies to work together during public health emergencies. By partnering with the FDA, RADx-UP was able to speed up the review process for diagnostics and ensure that underserved communities were a key focus in testing strategies.

CASE STUDY 3.4

SHARING TESTING RESOURCE INFORMATION

The Testing Core worked to share timely, relevant testing information as the needs changed during the pandemic. It relied heavily on the [Project Testing Requirement Guide](#) for up-to-date information about COVID-19 test availability according to population and setting. A **COVID-19 Testing tips** web page offered expert scientific and technical support, ensuring precise interpretation of NIH and CDC policies and FDA regulations. And the RADx-UP **project-wide meeting** was a useful forum to provide updates to RADx-UP awardees on new testing tools.

As testing preferences changed over the course of the pandemic, the Testing Core provided quick reference guides for various testing options for RADx-UP projects. These included the following quick reference guides:

- At Home Testing
- Point Of Care Testing
- Antibody Testing
- Saliva Testing

The Testing Core showed that test access can be improved by sharing timely test information and by coordinating in response to community needs.

GLOSSARY

Project-wide meeting

A monthly gathering of all RADx-UP partners

CASE STUDY 3.5

SYCT AND YMCF TOOLKIT FOR ENGAGING DIVERSE COMMUNITIES TO PLAN AND IMPLEMENT PUBLIC HEALTH PROGRAMS

The toolkit developed through the RADx-UP–affiliated Say Yes! COVID Test (SYCT) and You & Me COVID-Free (YMCF) programs serves as an invaluable resource for designing and implementing community-engaged public health initiatives. It emphasizes the importance of fostering meaningful partnerships with communities to ensure equitable access to health resources and support, particularly in underserved areas.

This comprehensive guide highlights key strategies and methodologies for successfully engaging diverse communities. It offers step-by-step instructions for navigating the complexities of public health programs, from initial planning to final implementation. Drawing from the lessons learned during the distribution of over 2 million free at-home COVID-19 tests, the toolkit provides practical advice on overcoming barriers, improving communication, and tailoring initiatives to meet the specific needs of each community.

CASE STUDY 3.5 | SYCT AND YMCF TOOLKIT

FIGURE 3.4: SAY YES! COVID TEST (SYCT) AND YOU & ME COVID-FREE (YMCF) TOOLKIT

Moreover, the toolkit underscores the role of community leaders, researchers, and communicators in driving impactful health interventions. By showcasing real-world examples and actionable strategies, it serves as a blueprint for future efforts aimed at addressing health disparities and enhancing public health preparedness. The toolkit is a testament to the success of collaborative approaches and the critical importance of community-led solutions in achieving lasting health outcomes.

Resource Spotlight

PUBLICATION

- Say Yes! COVID Test: A Health Communication Campaign to Encourage Use of Rapid, At-Home Antigen Testing in Underserved and Historically Marginalized Communities. [[Visit Website](#)]

TOOLKIT

- Toolkit for Engaging Diverse Communities to Plan and Implement Public Health Programs. [[Download PDF](#)]

Key Takeaways for Future Public Health Emergencies

Several strategies identified by RADx-UP researchers to address virus testing barriers can also be applied to future public health emergencies. In underserved communities across the country, communities set up easy-to-access testing locations, offered mobile testing services, created test and vaccine literacy campaigns in various languages, and provided employer support or insurance coverage for testing and vaccinations. Across the U.S., testing was made available in places people frequently visit, such as supermarkets, places of worship, schools, and neighborhoods. Incentives and transportation were offered to encourage testing, communication about testing was improved, and local employers were encouraged to accommodate clinical visits.

The RADx-UP program has demonstrated that increasing access to COVID-19 testing in underserved populations is achievable during a pandemic when supported by community-based research, tools, resources, and expertise from a centralized coordinating center. The Testing Core provided essential real-time technical expertise to ensure safe and adaptive testing (Compton et al., 2024). These strategies show that with the right tools, resources, and expertise, it is possible to increase virus testing and treatment in underserved populations during a pandemic, with a goal of stopping the spread and ultimately saving lives.

Key takeaways include:

- **Activate Community-Engaged Research:** Community-based research methods foster greater community engagement, which in turn enhances the co-creation and co-implementation of testing strategies. This collaborative process ultimately improves access to COVID-19 testing among underserved populations. Supporting these efforts with a central coordinating center—offering resources, tools, and expert guidance—is essential to maximize their effectiveness.
- **Create User-friendly Tools and Strategies:** Adaptable and easy-to-use tools designed to fit the needs of different communities—including testing quick reference guides, lay friendly instructions, and language-specific flyers—aided in monitoring testing methods and made sure they responded well to feedback from the public and changing health needs.

- **Create Partnerships to Prepare Communities:** The Testing Core's investment in partnerships and innovative efforts improved how communities engaged with testing. These efforts ensured that projects could get tests when they needed them, and that underserved communities could access healthcare advancements in the future.
- **Focus on the Importance of Messaging:** The integration of tools such as causal loop diagrams help make clear the pathways through which misinformation spreads and impacts public perception. Through better understanding and by providing accessible resources and practical messaging, organizations can empower communities to make informed decisions regarding testing and public health measures.

Conclusion

RADx-UP offers lessons learned during a historic public health emergency. By offering technical testing assistance, pathways to government agencies that evaluate and authorize new testing science, culturally appropriate materials, and platforms for knowledge sharing, RADx-UP highlights the importance of transparency, timely information, and community engagement. These principles, applied to testing initiatives during a health crisis, are essential in overcoming the barriers posed by misinformation and mistrust, and ensuring an effective public health response.

PHOTO COURTESY RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

Toolkit

1. FEATURED RADx-UP RESOURCES

Practical resources developed directly by the CDCC or RADx-UP projects. These may include publications, guides, or curated tools specific to implementing a program like the RADx-UP initiative.

- **RADx-UP Testing Requirement Guide** — In this guide, the RADx-UP CDCC Testing Core has assembled useful information for current and prospective RADx-UP projects to keep pace with the evolving nature of the pandemic, the test methods, and the FDA regulatory landscape. [\[Download PDF\]](#)
- **Rapid Research Pilot (RP2) Program Overview** — The RP2 operations team led webinars to provide information on the project, including budget, goals, timeline and general FAQs. [\[Download PDF\]](#)
- **Toolkit for Engaging Diverse Communities to Plan and Implement Public Health Programs** — Say Yes! COVID Test and You & Me COVID-Free program leaders and community partners worked together to develop a toolkit to share learned lessons and guide future community-engaged public health programs in underrepresented communities. The toolkit's main goals are to highlight the importance of community engagement, outline how to go about fostering it, and describe the vital role of communities in improving public health both now and in the future. [\[Download PDF\]](#)
- **Equitable COVID-19 Testing: A Multi-Perspective View of the Complexities** — GMB causal loop diagrams visually represent how different elements of a system or intervention are connected, paying specific attention to how different elements interact or cause one another to change.
 - a. Building Community Capacity & Impact: Diagram that explores the impact of missing information and of misinformation on testing [\[Visit Website\]](#)
 - b. Social Determinants of COVID-19 Testing and Vaccination: Diagram that explores the impact of social determinants of health on testing [\[Visit Website\]](#)
- **Video: How to Test with FlowFlex** — The video series developed by the Social Determinants of COVID-19 Testing and Vaccination Working Group in collaboration with the RADx-UP Testing Core, the FDA, and ACON Laboratories (manufacturer) to provide instructional guides in English and Spanish on COVID-19 testing for adults and juveniles, aiming to promote test utilization and trust. [\[Watch Video\]](#)

- **“I’m Vaccinated - When Do I Need to Get Tested for COVID-19?”**

Flyer offered in English and Spanish that provides guidance on when vaccinated individuals do or do not need testing for COVID-19. (See Appendix C.2)

RADx-UP CDCC Testing-Related Articles:

- Examining COVID-19 Testing and Vaccination Behaviors by Heritage and Linguistic Preferences Among Hispanic, Latino, or Spanish RADx-UP Participants [[Visit Website](#)]
- A Systems Perspective of How Community-Engaged Public Health Addresses Social Determinants of Health: A Case Study of a Population-Based COVID-19 Testing Program [[Visit Website](#)]

2. SUPPLEMENTAL RESOURCES

Resources developed outside the CDCC but shared via the Engagement Resource Center or by project partners. These materials offer supplemental value and represent real-world utility during a public health emergency response.

- **ASU Testing Repository** — A one-stop, reliable source for comprehensive information about COVID-19 tests worldwide. Search all tests in the market and in the pipeline by multiple parameters including test type, technology, regulatory status, country of origin and more. The Testing Commons is updated regularly. Collaboration with Mara Aspinall from ASU; RADx-TECH; FDA [[Visit Website](#)]
- **Interpretation of SARS-CoV-2 Immune Response Tests** — Blog post from Dr. James Everhart within the Testing Technology Trends from our partner ASU website, intended to share insights, knowledge and strategies to help academic and community audiences navigate the challenges and improve decision-making. [[Visit Website](#)]
- **How viral variants and vaccination impact COVID-19 test performance?** — Blog post from Dr. Gayani Tillekeratne within the Testing Technology Trends from our partner ASU website, intended to share insights, knowledge and strategies to help academic and community audiences navigate the challenges and improve decision-making. [[Visit Website](#)]
- **Best Practices for the Design of Accessible COVID-19 Home Tests** — This comprehensive Best Practices document details recommendations for test designers and manufacturers to create user-friendly and accessible COVID-19 home tests. While the initial focus is on COVID-19 testing, the ergonomic and accessible design principles outlined can also be applied to home tests for other diseases and conditions. [[Visit Website](#)]

3. RELEVANT PUBLICATIONS

A list of publications, data sources, or scholarly work that support the evidence base and offer pathways for further reading.

- Willems SJ, Castells MC, Baptist AP. The Magnification of Health Disparities During the COVID-19 Pandemic. *J Allergy Clin Immunol Pract*. 2022 Apr;10(4):903-908. doi: 10.1016/j.jaip.2022.01.032.
- Compton WM, Hooper MW, Hodes RJ, Pérez-Stable EJ. Lessons From COVID-19 Testing Research: The Power of Rapid Response. *Am J Public Health* 2024;114:S343_S346, <https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2024.307653>
- U.S. Food and Drug Administration. COVID-19 Test Basics. Available at: <https://www.fda.gov/consumers/consumer-updates/covid-19-test-basics>
- Narayanasamy S, Veldman TH, Lee MJ, et al. RADx-UP Testing Core: Access to COVID-19 Diagnostics in Community-Engaged Research with Underserved Populations. *J Clin Microbiol* 2023;61:e00367-23. <https://doi.org/10.1128/jcm.00367-23>
- Johannesson JM, Glover WA II, Petti CA, et al. Access to COVID-19 testing by individuals with housing insecurity during the early days of the COVID-19 pandemic in the United States: a scoping review. *Front. Public Health* 2023;11:1237066. doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2023.1237066
- Singler L, Uhlenbrauck G, Corbie-Smith G, et al. Say Yes! COVID Test: A Health Communication Campaign to Encourage Use of Rapid, At-Home Antigen Testing in Underserved and Historically Marginalized Communities. *Inquiry*. 2023 Jan-Dec;60:469580221146046. doi: 10.1177/00469580221146046.
- Katzmarzyk PT, Myers CA, Nelson MR, et al. Exploring barriers to SARS-CoV-2 testing uptake in underserved black communities in Louisiana. *Am J Human Biol* 2023;35(7):e23879. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajhb.23879>
- Lee RM, Handunge VL, Augenbraun SL, Nguyen H, Torres CH, Ruiz A, Emmons KM; RADx-MA Research Partnership. Addressing COVID-19 Testing Inequities Among Underserved Populations in Massachusetts: A Rapid Qualitative Exploration of Health Center Staff, Partner, and Resident Perceptions. *Front Public Health* 2022;10:838544. doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2022.838544.

Why does careful data collection matter during a health emergency?

Chapter 4 reviews the behind-the-scenes work of the RADx-UP Data Core, the engine driving how information was collected, protected, and used across more than 130 research projects. Gathering data in a public health emergency is more than numbers; it's about trust, clarity, and ensuring the community's voice shapes what's being measured. This chapter highlights how the RADx-UP team balanced speed and ethics, building systems that tracked COVID-19 testing patterns and respected privacy and cultural context.

Key Topics Covered

- How common data elements (CDEs) were designed, refined, and made culturally relevant
- Building strong data-sharing agreements, including with tribal nations to uphold sovereignty and trust
- Converting raw data into accessible dashboards, reports, and research tools that inform real-time decisions
- Case studies showcasing lessons from pediatric research, Long COVID data development, and the data collection support model

Lessons Learned

- Communities care deeply about how their data is used and want to be involved in shaping it from the start
- Protecting privacy, promoting transparency, and respecting local data ownership are essential to the ethics of public health research
- Sound data systems aren't just technical, they're relational, requiring trust, flexibility, and continuous feedback between researchers and the communities they serve

In Your Toolkit

Find step-by-step guidance for submitting data to a hub, including how to format and align CDEs, and submit qualitative data. These tools help ensure your data work stays community-driven, ethical, and adaptable.

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA COLLECTION & STORAGE

PHOTO COURTESY RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

Having reliable and accurate data is very important when managing public health emergencies. Good data supports decision making based on evidence. Information like how many people are sick, the number of confirmed cases, and infection trends should guide public health actions. Strong data collection and storage practices mean better evidence for responding to health emergencies.

The goal of the RADx-UP initiative was to examine factors affecting access to COVID-19 testing among underserved populations. RADx-UP investigators looked at differences in infection rates, testing rates, testing access, and how well people were using testing.

The RADx-UP CDCC gathered and stored data collected by the 142 research projects from across the country in a central database at the Duke Clinical Research Institute (DCRI). This data was then processed and transferred to the [RADx Data Hub](#), an NIH repository facilitating sharing, exploration, and analysis of COVID-19-related data to inform public health insights.

GLOSSARY

RADx Data Hub A centralized platform that stores and shares COVID-19 research data to support public health insights and digital innovation

FIGURE 4.1: CDCC DATA-SHARING WORKFLOW

This chapter delves into the methodologies and practices that ensured data was responsibly gathered, standardized, and utilized to inform public health actions. By balancing rapid response with ethical considerations, RADx-UP established robust data collection processes, community engagement strategies, and data-sharing agreements. This chapter explores the design and deployment of common data elements (CDEs), community-informed consent processes, data-sharing protocols, dashboards, core analytic datasets, and harmonization efforts. Additionally, case studies provide practical insights into process adaptations to collect Long COVID data, effective support models, and partnering with Tribal Nations, showcasing the RADx-UP initiative's commitment to inclusive and respectful research practices.

Background

Processes for Reliable Data Collection and Sharing

The RADx-UP CDCC included four pillars focused on project support: Data Science & Biostatistics Core (Data Core), Community Engagement Core, Testing Core and Administrative Core. These pillars provided essential expertise and guidance to researchers working with underserved populations. The CDCC's Data Core developed a robust data system to ensure consistency in data collection, identify and correct data quality issues, and to simplify data harmonization and analysis. The Data Core offered substantial support to projects from study start-up through to their final data transfers, including assigning a CDCC informaticist to work closely with each project team.

GLOSSARY

CDEs Common Data Elements help make comparisons or aggregate data possible; they're standard study questions across different projects or sites.

Harmonization Making data from different sources comparable and standardized

Common Data Elements

When RADx-UP started in 2020, the NIH provided CDEs for use by all of the RADx-UP projects. CDEs are standardized questions with consistent response options used across multiple studies, to streamline data collection, harmonization, and analysis across the consortium. The NIH list comprised 135 CDEs containing over 700 data entry fields from various repositories, including the National Library of Medicine CDE repository, the Disaster Research Response (DR2) CDE master codebook and the PhenX Toolkit. The CDCC worked with NIH and the RADx-UP projects to refine the CDEs and divide them into tiers; Tier 1 CDEs were mandatory for all testing projects, while Tier 2 CDEs were recommended, but optional. CDE categories could be in both tiers but with different questions.

FIGURE 4.2: NIH RADx-UP COMMON DATA ELEMENTS

The CDE development process was challenging. Feedback and changes from communities were necessary to ensure relevancy and cultural appropriateness, as described in this chapter's case study on CDEs. CDEs were updated as needed, including adding new elements for COVID-19 vaccinations, modifying sociodemographic CDEs, and developing subsets for pediatric populations and Long COVID studies. Ultimately, the RADx-UP CDEs facilitated cross-consortium analyses using data from numerous RADx-UP projects.

RADx-UP investigators and data experts worked hard to balance the need for quick action during the pandemic with the goal of gathering useful and practical data. The article from the CDCC, "[Standardizing, Harmonizing, and Protecting Data Collection to Broaden the Impact of COVID-19 Research: The Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics-Underserved Populations \(RADx-UP\) Initiative.](#)" explains how they created and started using CDEs.

Other Types of Project Data

The CDCC also provided guidance for other types of data collected by the projects, including:

- Electronic health record (EHR) data that was mapped to CDEs for projects using EHR systems
- Questions selected by the projects from CDE banks or newly created questions
- Qualitative data from surveys, interviews, and focus groups conducted by the projects
- Metadata about the projects collected by the CDCC, including details about project design, data-sharing permissions, and project results

This guide describes data collected by the CDCC, including descriptions of data categories, CDE tiers, and data shared with the NIH RADx Data Hub. (See Appendix D.1)

Data Collection & Storage for RADx-UP Projects: Colectiv, a web-based platform developed for RADx-UP, enabled research teams to securely collect and manage participant data using customizable forms and pre-programmed NIH CDEs. By streamlining electronic consent and ensuring compliance through secure data transfer, Colectiv had the capabilities to enhance the quality and efficiency of data collection across the consortium.

Data Protections and Sharing

INFORMED CONSENT

The RADx-UP CDCC provided template data sharing and use language for **informed consent forms (ICF)** to help align the projects' ICFs with the different levels of data sharing and the types of CDEs. By using the same CDEs and ICF data-sharing language, RADx-UP projects could gather and share data from almost all the populations and communities they studied and worked with. The CDCC kept track of which data-sharing options each project used in their consent forms in a REDCap database and used that information to confirm data-sharing limitations at the time of data transfer.

GLOSSARY

ICF Permission given by participants after understanding a study's risks and benefits

FIGURE 4.3: RADx-UP RE-CONTACT REGISTRY

During the informed consent process, many research participants across the RADx-UP program were asked if they would be interested in participating in future research studies. Participants who agreed to be contacted were added to the **RADx-UP Re-Contact Registry**, which stored their contact information and basic details and would allow them to be contacted about new study opportunities.

HOW DOES IT WORK?

■ Project ■ CDCC ■ Participant

¹ CDCC will typically send out one alert per month that includes up to 3 study advertisements.

² Participants are given opt out information for the registry in every alert.

DATA USE AGREEMENT

Before the CDCC received data transfers from a project, a data use agreement (DUA) outlining the terms and conditions for the transfer, use, and disclosure of data and **protected health information (PHI)** was established between the project's awardee institution and the CDCC. It included details about how the data would be used for research, stored, protected, and shared, as well as the privacy level (full PHI, limited PHI, or de-identified data only) of the data being transferred to the CDCC. The DUAs allowed the CDCC to share data within the RADx-UP program and transfer de-identified data to the NIH RADx Data Hub, but not directly share data with outside researchers. The CDCC also tracked the DUA information in their REDCap database.

DATA PROTECTIONS AND SHARING LIMITATIONS

Data sharing and use in the RADx-UP program were guided by a Data Stewardship Committee, which created a policy for data sharing. At the individual project level, the CDCC made sure projects did not transfer any data that violated their ICFs or DUAs. Using the information about the ICFs and DUAs that was tracked in their REDCap database, the CDCC programmed the data transfer portal to check a project's data file against their allowed privacy level (full PHI, limited PHI, or de-identified) and to reject any files that contained any unallowed data. For example, they ensured projects did not transfer dates and zip codes if their ICF and DUA only allowed **de-identified** data to be shared. The CDCC also set rules for using data in analyses, reports, and dashboards, including **small cell-size suppression** and protection of vulnerable populations.

GLOSSARY

PHI include any identifiable health information, and is protected by the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) Privacy Rule.

De-identified Data with personal identifiers removed to protect participant privacy

Small cell-size suppression refers to a process of masking or removing data from tables or figures to protect the privacy of individuals or groups represented by the data. This is typically done when the counts or values in a cell are very small, as they could potentially reveal sensitive information.

TRIBAL NATIONS

The CDCC worked with RADx-UP projects based within Tribal Nations on terms for data sharing and use. Each Tribal Nation, along with their partner academic institution, decided if, how, and when their participant data would be shared with the CDCC, the consortium, the public, and/or the NIH. A Working Group formed by the RADx-UP Tribal Nations projects also determined rules and a review process for how data would be interpreted and presented in subsequent reports and scholarly products.

Through a supplemental award from the NIH, the CDCC supported the RADx Tribal Data Repository: Data for Indigenous Implementations, Interventions and Innovations (RADx TDR: D4I) in creating an educational video series to help Tribal Nations and their communities understand the purpose and structure of the repository, different systems of data storage, informed consent, and data transfer and use contracts. These four videos as well as lessons shared by the RADx-UP American Indian Working Group can be found in this chapter's [Case Study 4.3](#).

Data Harmonization and Dissemination

DATA HARMONIZATION

The CDCC gathered data from RADx-UP projects based on each project's data-sharing agreements and the participants' consent. This data was compiled in the central RADx-UP database managed by the CDCC. Non-CDE data was stored in this database too. The CDCC data team checked the completeness, quality, and conformance of the CDE data received and worked with the projects to resolve any issues. In total, over 10 million data issues were identified and resolved for the 63 million CDE data points that were submitted to the CDCC.

Figure 4.4 displays the CDE and data point completeness.

FIGURE 4.4: CDE AND DATA POINT COMPLETENESS

* CDE completeness is defined as the percentage of the expected Tier 1 CDEs that were submitted to the CDCC.

* Data point completeness is defined as the percentage of non-blank fields in the submitted CDEs.

DATA DISSEMINATION AND THE NIH RADX DATA HUB

The CDCC de-identified, converted, and transferred much of the data to the RADx Data Hub — a national resource of RADx-generated research data that helps researchers and public health officials understand the impact of the pandemic, including outcomes, disparities, and possible solutions. The Data Hub has its own processes for standardizing, transferring, storing, and using data. The Data Hub provides access to non-RADx-UP researchers and others wanting to analyze COVID-19-related data across the four RADx programs: RADx-UP, RADx-ATP, RADx Tech, and RADx-rad. It includes seven data types: clinical, behavioral, survey/interview, diagnostic/test, biological sample, sequencing, and imaging data. The Data Hub provides a secure workspace to combine approved data and analytic tools, collaborate on the same data versions, share analysis results, cite relevant data for collaborators and the external community, and generate AI-ready datasets for RADx COVID-19 AI machine learning research. RADx-UP projects did not send data directly to the RADx Data Hub; instead, the CDCC collected, de-identified, and processed the data before uploading it to the Hub’s data portal. The CDCC worked with the Data Hub to resolve any questions or data quality issues, and also provided the Data Hub with copies of important project documents like protocols, ICFs, codebooks, case report forms, surveys, and tools.

GLOSSARY

RADx A set of NIH initiatives created to speed up the development, testing, and deployment of COVID-19 diagnostic technologies

RADx Tech An NIH program focused on accelerating the development and commercialization of new COVID-19 testing technologies

RADx-rad An NIH program supporting innovative and non-traditional approaches to COVID-19 testing and pandemic response

Data Use

CORE ANALYTIC DATASETS

The CDC created cross-consortium, analysis-ready, harmonized and aggregated CDE datasets to RADx-UP researchers as **Core Analytic Datasets**. Under the guidance of the RADx-UP Publications and Dissemination Committee, RADx-UP researchers could submit proposals to analyze the data within the Core Analytic Datasets for writing cross-consortium manuscripts and submitting abstracts to national meetings and conferences.

GLOSSARY

Core Analytic Datasets are organized sets of important data collected from RADx-UP projects that can be used to answer key research questions. These datasets include consistent information from many different study sites and are cleaned and prepared so researchers can easily analyze them and find patterns or results that help improve public health.

FIGURE 4.6: CORE ANALYTIC DATASETS

AREA-LEVEL LINKED DATASETS

Using location data from the CDEs, the CDCC prepared a series of area-level datasets from external sources that were used along with the RADx-UP Core Analytic Datasets for epidemiologic analyses. The social determinants of health indices used in the datasets included:

- Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ) Socioeconomic Status (SES) Index
- Social Vulnerability Index (SVI)
- Area Deprivation Index (ADI)
- Child Opportunity Index (COI)
- Pandemic Vulnerability Index (PVI)
- Minority Health Social Vulnerability Index (MH SVI)
- American Community Survey (ACS)
- Community Profile Report (CPR) COVID-19 positivity rate
- CDC COVID-19 Vaccination Coverage

The datasets were also used to create a dashboard with maps and graphs displaying the indices data for the areas where the RADx-UP projects worked and comparing RADx-UP data with the linked datasets for metrics like vaccination rates and COVID-19 positivity rates.

Dashboards and Reports

The CDCC created interactive dashboards and reports using CDE data from the RADx-UP database. These dashboards included graphs, maps, and other visualizations, helping RADx-UP researchers examine data across different projects. This also allowed the CDCC to provide NIH with real-time reports using the latest data.

FIGURE 4.7: EXAMPLES OF CDCC INTERACTIVE DASHBOARDS

These case studies highlight how RADx-UP integrated community input into data governance, created support structures for effective data practices, and upheld ethical standards in complex research settings. Together, they demonstrate the value of community-centered approaches to data stewardship during public health emergencies.

- 1. Using Community Engagement to Refine Common Data Elements (CDEs):** RADx-UP incorporated feedback from researchers and community partners to revise the NIH's initial CDEs and the CDCC co-develop tailored Tier 2 CDE sets for Long COVID and pediatric populations.
- 2. How the CDCC Model Strengthened Data Collection and Project Readiness:** By assigning dedicated staff and establishing a nine-step readiness process, the CDCC's support model helped projects effectively implement data systems and meet data-sharing goals.
- 3. Partnering with Tribal Nations:** RADx-UP honored Tribal sovereignty by supporting community-led data governance and launching a Tribal Data Repository with educational tools to promote Indigenous data stewardship.

CASE STUDY 4.1

USING COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT TO REFINE COMMON DATA ELEMENTS (CDE)

At the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, the NIH developed 135 CDEs containing more than 700 data entry fields to collect standardized information across the RADx research projects. These questions were created quickly to support urgent data needs, and while they enabled consistency across studies, they lacked community context. Researchers and community partners alike raised concerns that many questions felt disconnected from their real-world experiences, especially among marginalized communities. Some questions risked stigmatizing participants or failed to address the social and cultural realities of specific populations. Recognizing this, NIH and the CDCC revised the CDEs through a more inclusive and community-informed process.

From October to December 2020, the CDCC collaborated with the initial 69 RADx-UP projects in a bi-directional feedback loop to refine the original questions. This process incorporated feedback from researchers, administrators, community partners, and CDCC staff. Their joint efforts led to RADx-UP CDEs version 1.0, a revised question set approved by NIH that better reflected community realities and research needs. The CDCC Data Core provided these CDEs to the projects in both REDCap CSV codebook and PDF forms, along with Spanish translated versions of both files.

CASE STUDY 4.1 | USING COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT TO REFINE CDEs

This foundational work informed future CDE development, particularly for specialized populations. Two notable community-engaged processes were used to develop optional Tier 2 CDEs tailored for Long COVID and pediatric populations:

- **Long COVID CDE Task Force:** Building on past lessons, the CDCC convened a task force of community members, patients, partners, and researchers. Over 3 months, the group co-developed 27 new questions across three domains: introductory baseline (including a working definition of Long COVID), critical symptoms, and quality of life. The process emphasized clear communication, trust-building, and mutual respect, ensuring that the data elements were relevant, accessible, and non-stigmatizing.
- **Pediatric CDEs via the Child Health Working Group (CHWG):** The CHWG undertook the goal to develop a subset of Tier 2 pediatric-specific CDEs for the RADx-UP program. Starting with the pediatric CDEs from the Eunice Kennedy Shriver National Institute of Child Health and Human Development (NICHD), group members discussed what research questions the CDEs should address to better serve children and their communities. An 82-page document was divided into 10 categories for review in breakout sessions. Edits and suggestions were collected over several months via virtual meetings and shared documents, culminating in finalized revisions by the first quarter of 2022. The CHWG's feedback directly informed the recommended pediatric CDEs, improving their applicability and sensitivity to child health equity issues.

Resource Spotlight**JOURNAL PUBLICATION**

A community-engaged approach to developing common data elements: a case study from the RADx-UP Long COVID Common Data Elements Task Force [[Visit Website](#)]

CASE STUDY 4.2

HOW THE CDCC MODEL STRENGTHENED DATA COLLECTION AND PROJECT READINESS

A primary function of the CDCC's Data Science & Biostatistics Core was providing infrastructure and personnel support for the RADx-UP projects. The Data Core developed data submission guidance documents and conducted data orientation sessions for each phase of awarded projects. The Data Core assigned a bioinformatician to work with each project to:

- 1.** Conduct data submission interviews, to better understand the project's planned data collection, their data collection tools and database infrastructure, what data they planned to share with the CDCC and in what format, and important study start-up dates. The Data Core bioinformatician also worked with the project's data manager and staff to troubleshoot technical aspects of incorporating the CDEs into their data infrastructure and ensure that the resultant datasets conformed with the CDE format and content.
- 2.** Complete a nine-step data intake readiness process that ensured that all key elements were in place before a project's data manager was granted access to the CDCC's data upload portal. Readiness steps included CDCC review of the project's ICF, DUA fully executed, IRB approval received, and NIH approval for the CDEs the project planned to collect or not collect. Once a project completed all nine steps, they were marked in the CDCC REDCap database as being ready for their first data transfer.
- 3.** Complete the initial data submission, which occurred live during a meeting with the project data manager and the Data Core bioinformatician. The bioinformatician helped the data manager troubleshoot any issues in real time, and walked them through the data quality report that was generated based on their first uploaded dataset.
- 4.** Completed ongoing monthly meetings with the project team and data manager and provided constant support through the final data upload.
- 5.** Ensured that any quality or conformance issues identified in the data quality reports generated with each upload were addressed in accordance with RADx-UP policies.
- 6.** Assisted the projects using electronic health record (EHR) datasets to map their data to the RADx-UP CDEs.

CASE STUDY 4.2 | HOW THE CDCC MODEL STRENGTHENED DATA COLLECTION

Additional Data Core personnel assisted the project teams with the completion of essential documents such as the DUA, as well as forms for registering each project and sharing their data with the RADx Data Hub. Specialized Data Core personnel provided support both to the project teams and the CDCC staff from the other cores who also worked directly with the projects; areas of specialty included qualitative data collection and sharing, Tribal Nations data sharing and use permissions, CDE data analysis, and statistical design consultations.

The Data Core team provided comprehensive, responsive support to the project teams, which resulted in rapid sharing and use of RADx-UP data.

The Engagement Impact Teams (EITs) were also vital for supporting RADx-UP projects. They served as the main link between RADx-UP project PIs and staff and the CDCC (See **Figure 4.8**). Each project worked with one or more EIT members to help meet the goals set by CDCC and NIH. They also offered guidance and support throughout the project stages. Monthly meetings were held to track progress, discuss challenges, request help, and talk about community engagement, enrollment, data collection, and data sharing with the CDCC. EITs also helped connect project teams with CDCC resources and consultations, making it easier to solve technical problems.

CASE STUDY 4.2 | HOW THE CDCC MODEL STRENGTHENED DATA COLLECTION

For programs wanting to use a similar model in future projects, there were various documents created to outline the roles and responsibilities of EITs. These resources outlined how to set up a support system that can help community-based research efforts succeed.

RESOURCE TITLE	DESCRIPTION	INTENDED USER
RADx-UP EIT Role in Project Data Readiness	Outlines the EIT's role in helping research projects meet data collection and readiness targets.	EIT Members
Project Operations Leader Roles & Responsibilities	Describes leadership tasks for managing project operations, timelines, and team coordination.	Project Operations Leaders
Project Specialist Roles & Responsibilities	Details day-to-day support duties related to project engagement and technical assistance.	Project Specialists
Associate Project Specialist Roles & Responsibilities	Provides expectations for junior project staff supporting EIT functions and site follow-up.	Associate Project Specialists
Data Functional Team Roles & Responsibilities	Explains technical support roles in managing data quality, upload processes, and troubleshooting.	Data Support Team Members
Testing and Closeout Team Roles & Responsibilities	Describes final-phase support for project testing metrics and study wrap-up procedures.	Testing and Closeout Team Members

CASE STUDY 4.3

PARTNERING WITH TRIBAL NATIONS

Academic teams who partner with Tribal Nations for purposes of research, especially federally funded research such as RADx-UP, must respect and adhere to local regulations designed to protect tribal members' participation and the resulting data. Tribal sovereignty — which underpins a unique government-to-government relationship — affords Tribal Nations control of their data, commonly referred to as data sovereignty. Data-sharing agreements typically codify the relevant Tribal policies and practices that govern its use, require sharing resources, and ensures community benefit.

All federally sponsored research protocols and data collection undertaken in partnership with Tribal communities must be approved by Tribal Authorities (e.g., Tribal IRBs, Tribal Health Councils). This includes data-sharing agreements and derivative products for dissemination. On RADx-UP, the CDCC completed DUAs with the academic institutions that were awarded funding by NIH. In general, the CDCC did not complete DUAs directly with Tribal Nations. Instead, the NIH-funded academic institutions made separate data-sharing agreements with the Tribal Authorities and provided documentation to the CDCC of the Tribe's decision to share or not share their data with the CDCC and NIH. A few of the academic institutions also declined completing a DUA with the CDCC. The exception to the above was the Cherokee Nation, which was awarded funding directly from NIH and not through a partnering academic institution — in this instance, the CDCC had a DUA directly with the Cherokee Nation. Ultimately, some projects shared all their participant data with the CDCC and/or NIH, some only shared data for participants not subject to the Tribal data-sharing agreements (e.g. participants of other races and ethnicities), and some projects shared no data.

CASE STUDY 4.3 | PARTNERING WITH TRIBAL NATIONS

Working Group

RADx-UP Tribal Nations awardees formed a working group and established rules for data sharing and use by the consortium. Lessons learned from working group members include:

- Principal investigators (PIs) must build relationships with Tribal Nation partners to create trust, promote understanding, maintain openness, and produce high-quality data that is scientifically meritorious and of local benefit.
- Funding resources should be appropriately distributed to support meaningful participation by **all** partners, and not held entirely by and expended only in support of the organization awarded the grant.
- **All** tribal entities contributing to a given study sponsored in this fashion must be involved at the outset in designing, implementing, analyzing, reporting results, and reviewing as well as approving products based on this work. An example on RADx-UP was the active participation by **all** six Urban Indian Health Organizations (UIHOs) on the project titled Community Organizations for Natives: COVID-19 Epidemiology, Research, Testing, and Services (CONCERTS) throughout the research process.
- Principal investigators **and** sponsors should negotiate flexible, extended timelines to enable all Tribal Nations grantees to consider and adapt data-sharing agreements to their local circumstances.

Resource Spotlight

Spero Manson, Distinguished Professor and Director of the Centers for American Indian and Alaskan Native Health at the University of Colorado Anschutz Medical Center and RADx-UP American Indian Working Group member, discussed the context of the COVID-19 pandemic for native communities and how the working group tackled some of the historic challenges of working with the government on research projects. [[Watch Video](#)]

CASE STUDY 4.3 | PARTNERING WITH TRIBAL NATIONS**Educational Video Series**

The RADx Tribal Data Repository: Data for Indigenous Implementations, Interventions and Innovations (RADx TDR: D4I) was separately funded by the NIH. The RADx TDR: D4I will establish a data repository consistent with Tribal sovereignty for researchers and their collaborators interested in working with RADx data provided by American Indian and Alaska Native research participants to better understand and address the impact of COVID-19 and other health disparities. Through a supplemental award from the NIH, the CDCC supported the RADx TDR: D4I in creating an educational video series to help Tribal Nations and their communities understand the purpose and structure of the repository.

Resource Spotlight

See the RADx TDR: [D4I Educational Video Series](#):

- Video 1: The Tribal Data Repository Project
- Video 2: Data Management & Sharing
- Video 3: Consent
- Video 4: Contracts

Key Takeaways for Future Public Health Emergencies

The process of RADx-UP data harmonization, along with feedback from community research sites, offers valuable lessons for handling future public health emergencies. Here are five key points:

- Include community members in design and planning of data collection and sharing processes from the start of any research.
- Respect privacy, transparency, security, and honor data sovereignty when working with underserved populations. It's also important to involve community members in decisions about data early in the research.
- CDEs should reflect the needs of the community partners. These partners should take an active role and work together with researchers to create these data elements.
- Use community input to refine how CDEs are implemented and communicated. Incorporate cultural and linguistic nuances when developing or translating CDEs.
- Cultural considerations are vital, and translating CDEs should go beyond just word-for-word translation. It is essential to consider the community's cultural aspects to ensure inclusivity.

Conclusion

The RADx-UP initiative emphasized the importance of robust data collection and storage processes, community involvement in data collection, and data ownership and access considerations in research. The RADx-UP consortium, along with the NIH, balanced quick action during a pandemic with the goal of collecting useful, harmonized, and practical data. By setting up a strong data collection system, making detailed guidance documents, and giving lots of support to project teams, the Data Core has made sure data collection is consistent and high-quality across the RADx-UP consortium. Using CDEs facilitated cross-consortium analysis and created a standard way to prospectively harmonize data. A community-informed approach to creating CDEs can be quickly scaled and used, overcoming language barriers, data privacy concerns, and technical challenges with data management, while adapting to the local needs of each project. Also, the CDCC's work on data protection and sharing has kept participant information private while allowing for valuable research collaborations. It is hoped that the data in the RADx Data Hub will continue to widen the impact of COVID-19 research and help with future public health responses for underserved communities.

Toolkit

1. FEATURED RADx-UP RESOURCES

Practical resources developed directly by the CDCC or RADx-UP projects. These may include publications, guides, or curated tools specific to implementing a program like the RADx-UP initiative.

RADx-UP CDE Guidelines and Submission Support Documents:

RESOURCE TITLE	DESCRIPTION	INTENDED AUDIENCE
RADx-UP Data Tiers	Explains different data categories and CDE tiers, and what is shared with the NIH Data Hub. (See Appendix D.1)	Investigators, Data Managers
RADx-UP CDCC Data Submission Guidance	Step-by-step instructions for submitting CDEs, including formatting data to align with REDCap CDE codebooks, consent alignment, portal use, issue resolution, and quality conformance. [Download PDF]	Project Teams, Data Coordinators/Managers
Non-CDE Data Submission Guidance	Guidance for submitting qualitative and other non-CDE data collected during RADx-UP studies. [Download PDF]	Qualitative Researchers, Data Teams

2. SUPPLEMENTAL PUBLICATIONS

Resources developed outside the CDCC but shared via the Engagement Resource Center or by project partners. These materials offer supplemental value and represent real-world utility during a PHE response.

- **2-1-1 Counts** — The first tool to provide real-time, searchable and visual presentations of data from 2-1-1 call centers across the nation, 2-1-1 Counts was created by the Health Communication Research Laboratory at Washington University in St. Louis. [[Visit Website](#)]
- **Tips and Tools for Remote Qualitative Data Collection** — A guide on best practices for remote qualitative data collection, produced by the North Carolina Translational and Clinical Sciences Institute (NC TraCS), which contributes to best practices for remote data collection with communities. This is a trusted external resource selected from the Engagement Resource Center not created with RADx-UP funds. [[Download PDF](#)]

3. RELEVANT PUBLICATIONS

A list of publications, data sources, or scholarly work that support the evidence base and offer pathways for further reading.

- Carrillo GA, Cohen-Wolkowicz M, D'Agostino EM, et al. Standardizing, harmonizing, and protecting data collection to broaden the impact of COVID-19 research: the Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics-Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) initiative. *J Am Med Inform Assoc.* 2022;29(9):1480-1488. [doi:10.1093/jamia/ocac097](https://doi.org/10.1093/jamia/ocac097)
- Pike Welch HL, Guest G, Garba H, Carrillo GA, Damman AM, Kibbe WA. A community-engaged approach to developing common data elements: a case study from the RADx-UP Long COVID Common Data Elements Task Force. *JAMIA Open.* 2025; 8(3):oaf046. [doi:10.1093/jamiaopen/oaf046](https://doi.org/10.1093/jamiaopen/oaf046)

How do you make research more fair, inclusive, and community-driven?

Chapter 5 focuses on RADx-UP's approach to deep, respectful, and sustained community engagement. Grounded in national frameworks such as the CTSA's Principles of Community Engagement and the AAMC's Principles of Trustworthiness, RADx-UP ensured that community voices shaped research design, implementation, and dissemination.

Key Topics Covered

- Frameworks and principles for community engagement (CTSA, AAMC)
- RADx-UP community engagement strategies and partner types
- Use of the RADx-UP Image Bank, Equity Evidence Academy, and Engagement Resource Center
- Case studies on local branding, feedback systems, and relationship-building
- Emphasis on co-leadership and trust in research partnerships

Lessons Learned

- Trust and co-leadership are practical necessities, not just ethical ideals
- Partnerships thrive on shared decision-making and tailored outreach
- Resource and recruitment challenges can be overcome when communities and researchers collaborate fully

Case Examples

- **Community-designed logos** (e.g., LinkUP) fostered trust
- **Community Connections** forums provided virtual spaces for shared learning
- **Innovative partnerships**, from Baltimore to the Mississippi Delta, expanded testing and vaccination
- **Systems thinking** and **storytelling** aligned research with local needs

In Your Toolkit

Ready-to-use resources like engagement principles, causal loop diagrams, and consultation materials to help design rigorous, equitable, community-centered research

OVERVIEW

CHAPTER FIVE: BEST PRACTICES FOR CONDUCTING COMMUNITY-ENGAGED RESEARCH

PHOTO COURTESY RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

Background

Investing in Community Engagement to Achieve Health Equity

Community engagement involves building strong, trusting relationships between communities and those working to improve health (CDC, 2011). During the COVID-19 pandemic, it became clear that some **underserved populations** faced more illness, less access to testing, and lower vaccination rates. To address these **health inequities**, the **NIH** supported projects that partnered directly with communities. Through the RADx-UP initiative, researchers worked closely with local leaders and organizations across the country, showing that community-driven research can reduce **health disparities** during public health crises.

GLOSSARY

Underserved populations

Groups with limited access to essential services due to systemic barriers

Health inequities are systematic differences in the health status of different population groups.

NIH The National Institutes of Health is the largest funder of medical research, and funded RADx-UP.

Health disparities Differences in health and healthcare that happen more often in certain groups of people because of unfair social, economic, or environmental conditions

FIGURE 5.1: RADx-UP PROJECT BY SPECIFIC POPULATIONS ENGAGED

RADx-UP Projects

By specific populations engaged

September, 2023. Data is self-reported by projects. Projects may serve more than one population.

† Return to School projects include the same target populations as other projects, but are oriented around keeping schools open

*includes the following: Individuals with or who are either at-risk for diabetes, have received care for diabetes, or are a family caregiver of a person with diabetes; skilled nursing facilities; Arabic-speaking; Criminal Justice Involved (CJI); medical comorbidities increasing risk of severe COVID-19; overcrowded housing; migrants; health workers and peer educators/outreach workers; senior staff from Consortium partner organizations; Underserved populations in Philadelphia; Underserved Populations in Baton Rouge; 211 Helpline Callers; Children; people in high-risk jobs &/or unstably housed; Adults and children > 8 years of age living within pre-identified communities participating in the public health intervention

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Types of Community Partnerships

The RADx-UP initiative worked with many kinds of community partners, such as Community Advisory Boards, community-based organizations, public health agencies, health care systems, associations, foundations, non-profit organizations, local and state representatives, academic institutions, Tribal Nations, and faith-based groups. These partnerships focused on building trust between researchers and local communities.

Below is a list of the types of community partners who worked with RADx-UP researchers.

PARTNERSHIP TYPE	DESCRIPTION
Community Advisory Board	Advisory board with a mission or purpose composed of community members that are not necessarily affiliated with a specific organization.
Community-Based Organization	Community-organized and operated organization aimed at benefiting social health, well-being, and overall functioning.
Public Health Agency	An entity that is governed by or contractually responsible to a local board of health or the department to provide services focused on the health status of population groups and their environments. (e.g., NIH, CDC, SAMHSA, public health department, Federally Qualified Health Center)
Health Care System	An institution that delivers health care services to meet the health needs of people seeking care within their system.
Associations & Foundations	Associations and foundations are non-profits providing services that will meet the needs of a community (e.g., Federally Qualified Health Center). Non-governmental agencies and institutions that are not directly run and operated by community members but seek to benefit the well-being of specific populations. (e.g., UNICEF).
Non-Federal Government Administration	The administration of a particular state, town, county, or district, with representatives elected by those who live there
Academic Institution	Educational institution that grants academic degrees, including school districts (e.g., universities, community colleges, trade schools)
Tribal Nations	Federally recognized and non-federally recognized; includes American Indian or Alaska Native (AI/AN) tribe, nation, clan
Faith-Based Organization	Organizations associated with religious entities (e.g., churches, temples, mosques, inter-faith collaborations, YMCA)
Federally Qualified Health Centers	Federally designated health clinics based in communities.
Other	Catch-all for CPs that don't fit into the above categories.

National Precedents Guiding Best Practices for RADx-UP Community-Engaged Research (CEnR)

Building trusting relationships between researchers and community members is the foundation of community engagement. The RADx-UP initiative was guided by principles and precedents for best practices in community engagement to build new partnerships and to advance the science and art of community engagement throughout the consortium. Fundamental resources included the [Clinical and Translational Science Awards \(CTSA\)](#) Consortium Community Engagement Key Function Committee Task Force on the Principles of Community Engagement (CTSA, 2011) and the [American Association of Medical Colleges \(AAMC\)](#) Center for Health Justice's [Principles of Trustworthiness Project](#) (AAMC, 2025).

- I. RADx-UP utilized national, evidence-based precedents in the **CTSA Principles of Community Engagement (Second Edition)** to guide RADx-UP community engagement practices. This volume “aims to provide scientific-based, practical guidelines” to engage people in a “range of roles, from the program funder, who needs to know how to support community engagement, to the researcher or community leader, who needs hands-on, practical information on how to mobilize the members of a community to partner in research initiatives” (CTSA, 2011). The 1990s marked a turn in participatory scientific studies to improve human health and led to greater community-based participatory research (CBPR) and community-engaged research (CEnR) to address health disparities. This represented a departure from traditional empirical research to participatory models of community engagement with a focus on local applications and best practices for impacted community members. Community inclusion is central to this process and finds its origins in U.S. health studies in the principles of CBPR developed by Israel et al. (1998). As the field progressed, the assessment, documentation, and support of community engagement advanced. Metrics and evaluations of meaningful community engagement advanced further with the validation of the CBPR model by Wallerstein et al. (2020) from the Engage for Equity initiative.

CTSA teams adapted the [International Association for Public Participation's \(IAP2\) Spectrum of Public Participation](#) to create a community engagement continuum guiding U.S. health studies. This model prioritizes community inclusion throughout the research collaboration sites and underlies many of the templates and resources created by RADx-UP (IAP2, 2018).

GLOSSARY

CTSA is a NIH program that supports translational and collaborative research aimed to improve the efficiency, quality, and impact of the process for improving human health.

AAMC AAMC's trustworthiness initiative helped RADx researchers conceptualize partnerships and trusting relationships.

CBPR is a collaborative research approach that involves community members, researchers, and organizational representatives as equal partners vested in improving community health.

IAP2 The IAP2 created the community engagement continuum adapted by CTSA, and later by RADx-UP to describe and evaluate community engagement systematically.

II. The AAMC Center for Health Justice's Principles of Trustworthiness Project offered toolkits and guides associated with the core values of trustworthiness with communities. The Principles of Trustworthiness frame community inclusion in the research process, respecting the knowledge and experience of communities while remaining mindful of the sustainability challenges of community partnerships built during the research process. The AAMC principles promote reflective practices that acknowledge that a “long, ongoing history of mistreatment and abuse has fostered logical distrust of the health care system and other institutions across diverse communities. It is up to institutions with power and privilege to demonstrate they are worthy of trust from their communities. Trust is the foundation of the community-driven, multisector partnerships necessary to create lasting **health equity** for all” (AAMC, 2025).

GLOSSARY

Health equity When everyone has a fair and just opportunity to be as healthy as possible

PHOTO COURTESY RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

The RADx-UP CDCC Principles of Community Engagement

The CDCC further defined aspects of community engagement in RADx-UP with a condensed five-point version of guiding principles:

Community

A group of people with shared identities, culture, language, values and/or interests. Often, members of communities come together to share experiences, thoughts, and ideas or to achieve a common mission. Communities may be virtual, geographically close, or in diaspora.

RADx-UP Community Engagement Core Tenets

Community engagement is an ongoing process of building and nurturing relationships of mutual understanding and trust between communities and those seeking to connect with them, including liaising between community partners and larger systems. Fostering a culture of trust and engaging communities in research is a foundational tenant of the RADx-UP CDCC. The CDCC will prioritize community-engaged work and will strengthen information and resource sharing between academic institutions and community organizations.

Guiding Principles of Community Engagement for the RADx-UP CDCC

The CDCC values creating opportunities to listen, learn, and inform community members and colleagues within the CDCC. Community engagement will occur without fear of judgment or retaliation as mutual understanding and trust are achieved through reflective conversation.

Additionally, the development of creative solutions comes from embracing individual differences and empowering diverse communities. This in turn will promote the long-term sustainability and success of our initiatives.

Vision for Engaging with Community Stakeholders

Community partners are welcome at all stages and to co-lead decision-making. This means community partners can express concerns and provide feedback but also engage in strategic planning and initiate new opportunities to improve the impact of the CDCC and RADx-UP-affiliated projects.

Community Engagement Mission Statement

The RADx-UP CDCC will work within a culture that is informed by community-engaged practices across each core of the CDCC. While the implementation of community engagement may vary based on the content area of the CDCC core (i.e., the Data Core, Testing Core, or Community Engagement Core), the principles of equity, honesty, trust, assurance, and mutual understanding will be core principles that guide our community engagement work.

RADx-UP Community Engagement in Practice

Building on the CDC's guiding principles of community engagement, RADx-UP put these values into action through a range of dynamic initiatives that exemplified community engagement in real-world settings. These efforts collectively reflect how our engagement principles were not only aspirational but operational.

Key initiatives—such as but not limited to the RADx-UP Working Groups, Equity Evidence Academy, Community Connections, Community Collaboration Grants (C2G), Image Bank, and the Engagement Resource Center (ERC)—provided critical platforms for bidirectional learning, co-creation, and community-informed decision-making. Each of these efforts centered community voices, embedded equity into implementation, and fostered sustainable partnerships.

THESE APPROACHES ARE ILLUSTRATED IN THE FOLLOWING CHAPTER CASE STUDIES:

- [Case Study 1.1](#): Engagement Impact Teams
- [Case Study 1.2](#): Working Groups
- [Case Study 1.3](#): Equity Evidence Academy Series
- [Case Study 4.3](#): Partnering with Tribal Nations
- [Case Study 5.2](#): RADx-UP Community Connections
- [Case Study 6.3](#): Engagement Resource Center (ERC)
- [Case Study 6.4](#): RADx-UP Image Bank
- [Case Study 9.3](#): Community Collaboration Grants (C2G)

In addition to these formal initiatives, RADx-UP also prioritized direct consultation with community members through methods like Community Consultation Studios and listening sessions. These participatory approaches were essential to understanding local needs and ensuring that research messages, tools, and strategies truly resonated with the populations we aimed to serve. Taken together, these practices reflected RADx-UP's commitment to putting principles into practice—transforming engagement ideals into collaborative, community-driven actions across the research network.

This chapter's case studies illustrate the tangible benefits of community engagement in public health research—from branding and storytelling to partnership innovations and feedback systems. These examples underscore how community collaboration leads to stronger trust, more relevant interventions, and lasting health equity infrastructure.

- 1. Local Branding at RADx-UP Study Sites:** Demonstrated how tailored visual identities, such as the LinkUP logo, fostered community trust and participation in testing and vaccination campaigns.
- 2. RADx-UP Community Connections:** CDCC created quarterly virtual forums where community partners shared experiences, built networks, and co-developed solutions tailored to their local contexts.
- 3. Highlights of Project Site Innovations:** Showcased three successful partnerships—in Baltimore, the Mississippi Delta, and Nebraska—that implemented responsive, community-driven models to expand testing access and build trust.
- 4. Capturing and Documenting Community Feedback:** CDCC used systems thinking and Community Consultation Studios to transform lived experiences into actionable insights, aligning communication strategies with community needs.

CASE STUDY 5.1

LOCAL BRANDING AT RADx-UP STUDY SITES

Localized branding can significantly enhance community engagement in health initiatives. Twenty-two RADx-UP projects created project-specific logos to show ownership of the work and to foster outreach and trust in the community. This case study highlights the LinkUP project, showcasing how a community-designed logo can encourage participation.

Project Overview

The LinkUP project, a collaboration between the University of California San Diego and OnPoint (a mobile syringe program), aimed to increase COVID-19 testing and vaccination among individuals who inject drugs in San Diego County's La Frontera neighborhood. Recognizing the need for a welcoming visual identity, the project team created an engaging logo.

Logo Development

Inspired by a personal experience—a participant gifting sunflowers—a project leader enlisted local artist Shannon Knox to design the logo. The final product featured a vibrant sunflower with a red heart and an upward arrow, symbolizing hope and positivity. Displayed prominently on a mobile van, the logo sparked curiosity and conversations within the community.

The Impact of Branding

The LinkUP logo was used across various platforms, including stickers on client IDs, facilitating participant identification and data collection. By prioritizing warmth in its design over clinical imagery, the project fostered trust and connection with the community. Knox noted that a thoughtfully designed logo reflects commitment that resonates on a personal level.

CASE STUDY 5.1 | LOCAL BRANDING AT RADx-UP STUDY SITES

Conclusion

The LinkUP project demonstrated good community engagement by creating a community-based brand for its project. By involving community members in the design process and creating a positive visual presence, the project successfully identified its purpose and engaged individuals in critical health initiatives.

Recommendations

- Involve local artists and collaborate with community members for authentic representation.
- Consistently use branding by applying the logo across all outreach materials for a unified message.
- Focus on emotional connections by using imagery that resonates emotionally with the target audience to enhance trust and engagement.

The following are some examples from projects, including a description of the logo development and use submitted by the project staff.

Puipuia le Ola: Protecting Life

“Protecting Life” is translated into 10 distinct Pacific Islander languages spoken in Hawaii and Guam. They are Samoan, Chuukese, Marshallese, Tongan, Pohnpeian, Kosraean, Chamorro, Palauan, Yapese.

The logo was designed collaboratively by our field research team, who are members of the community. This logo served as branding for the project. This logo was made into a t-shirt which all of us wore whenever we conducted fieldwork and community outreach.

CASE STUDY 5.1 | LOCAL BRANDING AT RADx-UP STUDY SITES

Southeast Asians in the U.S.: Health Equity and Research to Understand COVID-19 Stories (SEA US, HEAR US)

The academic research team (especially their student researchers) developed the logo in partnership with a developer. Every aspect of the logo carries with it special meaning, from the waves that signify the population’s migration to the West to the spherical shape symbolizing the global impact of this work. The development of the logo was a long and iterative process.

Rapid Research: Investigating Language as a Barrier to Rapid Testing in Underserved Spanish Speaking Hispanic Populations

Our logo was designed with consideration of geographical and cultural elements unique to the U.S./Mexico border region. Specifically, we included the Franklin Mountains, a staple landmark in our community. Furthermore, we incorporated symbolic elements such as a caduceus for medicine and public health. Moreover, our project focused on reducing language barriers associated with COVID-19 rapid testing, thus, we included the text “Language Breaking Research” within our logo.

Faithful Response II: COVID-19 Rapid Test-to-Treat with African American Churches

The Clergy Response Network designed the logo by first brainstorming on the message they wanted to convey with the logo. They wanted the community to know that it is a faith-based project and the dove is the symbol most recognized in the community that generally says “faith” and for the colors to match up with RADx-UP’s blues. We shared the CRN ideas with a local African American graphic designer and received a few options. CRN voted on their top design with the majority winning, and then made a few tweaks.

CASE STUDY 5.2

RADx-UP COMMUNITY CONNECTIONS

The Community Connections series was a virtual forum for community partners to engage in knowledge sharing and mutual support. Organized as quarterly gatherings, these meetings featured presentations on relevant themes tailored specifically to the community partners' roles on RADx-UP projects. Following the presentations, open discussions encouraged active participation, allowing partners to share successes, challenges, and innovative practices in a collaborative environment. The series also compensated volunteers who contributed to co-creating programs, reinforcing the commitment to equity and mutual benefit.

Through the Community Connections series, partners gained valuable networking opportunities and fostered relationships that could lead to joint initiatives and resource sharing. The focus on relevant topics ensured that the discussions were meaningful, enhanced collective knowledge and empowered partners to improve health outcomes in underserved communities.

CASE STUDY 5.2 | RADx-UP COMMUNITY CONNECTIONS

Recommendations

The Community Connections series exemplifies best practices in community-engaged research by prioritizing inclusivity, collaboration, and continuous learning, and may be a model for future initiatives.

COMMUNITY CONNECTIONS PRESENTATIONS:

- Community Connections Conversation with Rev. Donald Wright Jr., EMBA, MDiv** — Community partner Rev. Donald Wright from Mt. Lebanon Baptist Church (West Baltimore) shared his perspective on faith institutions not solely being a spiritual institution but that they are a place of connectivity and serve to engage in holistic strategies to meet the physical, mental, and emotional needs of their communities. Strong partnerships within the community alongside their operating model (centered on sustainability, trust, and community engaged partnerships) has bridged much needed gaps to inform people on the how/why of research being done, and what the information will be used for. [[Watch Video](#)]

- Community Connections Conversation with SisterLove, Inc.** — Community partner Lisa Diane White from SisterLove, Inc. shared nuggets from her work with Georgia State University on understanding barriers to participation in COVID-19 testing among Black communities. Their project aimed to investigate Black Americans' attitudes to COVID-19 testing, and findings reflected that key reasons for agreeing to take the blood test were (1) family, community, and social responsibility; (2) curiosity; (3) health upkeep; and (4) importance of research. Findings uncovered the following key reasons for not taking the blood test: (1) fear of the known and unknown, (2) fear of needles/blood, (3) discomfort with the testing setting, and (4) seen as unnecessary/no benefit. [[Watch Video](#)]

- Community Connections Conversation with IMPACT-Ohio** — Community partner Florence Siman from El Pueblo described her work in supporting and building the capacity of LatinX and other marginalized communities' programs, civic engagement, policy advocacy, training promotoras, and COVID-19 testing and vaccination drives. Challenges and key lessons learned were shared with the audience, and new connections were made with other local groups. [[Watch Video](#)]

PHOTO COURTESY RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

CASE STUDY 5.3

HIGHLIGHTS OF PROJECT
SITE INNOVATIONS**Building Trust Through Community-Engaged Research in Baltimore**

The COMMIT (Community-Defined Measures to Bridge Health Equity Gaps Community Mistrust and Measure of Institutional Trustworthiness) project exemplified best practices in community-engaged research, particularly in its emphasis on building and maintaining trust within the West Baltimore community. By leveraging longstanding relationships with local organizations, such as Mount Lebanon Baptist Church, and prioritizing community input at every stage of the project, the researchers fostered an environment of mutual respect and understanding. This approach, which included co-designing partnerships, developing ethically consistent memoranda of commitment, and engaging in adaptive learning, allowed for the successful execution of trust-building initiatives around COVID-19 testing, ultimately laying the groundwork for more effective responses to future public health challenges.

Bridging Health Disparities in the Mississippi Delta through Community Collaboration

The RADx-UP Community Collaboration Grant awarded to the Drs. Aaron & Olye Shirley Foundation exemplified the effective use of community partnerships to address significant health disparities in underserved areas. By leveraging a \$50,000 RADx-UP grant, the Foundation, in partnership with the Mallory Community Health Center, brought walk-in COVID-19 testing and vaccination services directly to Holmes and Humphreys counties in the Mississippi Delta. This collaborative effort not

PROJECT SPOTLIGHT: MOBILE TESTING AND VACCINATION IN THE MISSISSIPPI DELTA [\[WATCH VIDEO\]](#)

CASE STUDY 5.3 | HIGHLIGHTS OF PROJECT SITE INNOVATIONS

only provided critical access to healthcare services but also highlighted the importance of community-based initiatives in addressing health inequities. Through 23 community events between October 2021 and July 2022, the project administered 152 COVID-19 tests, 175 vaccines, and 110 booster shots, underscoring the impact of community engagement and partnerships in improving health outcomes in resource-constrained areas.

Community Partnership Enhances mHealth Solutions for Migrant Families in Nebraska

The Mobile Health Targeted SARS-CoV-2 Testing and Community Interventions to Maximize Migrant Children's School Attendance project in Nebraska illustrated the power of effective community partnerships in addressing health disparities faced by migrant families during the COVID-19 pandemic. Spearheaded by principal investigator Russell McCulloh, this RADx-UP initiative collaborated closely with the Title IC Nebraska Migrant Education Program and Buffalo County Community Partners to design a responsive **mHealth** model that prioritized community needs. Initially proposing a two-arm study, the research team adapted their approach based on feedback from community partners, ensuring equal access to resources for all participants, which reflected the collaborative spirit of the project. Enabling 165 migrant families to utilize at-home testing kits and a mobile app for symptom screenings, the initiative gathered significant data to identify barriers faced by families, such as income loss and childcare challenges. The positive reception and insights from qualitative interviews conducted in Spanish further emphasized the importance of community voice in shaping effective health interventions, ultimately demonstrating that mobile health solutions can successfully reach and support isolated populations.

GLOSSARY

mHealth Use of mobile devices to support health services, information, and support during a PHE

CASE STUDY 5.4

CAPTURING AND DOCUMENTING COMMUNITY FEEDBACK

Listening to the Community to Improve Public Health Projects

RADx-UP knew that listening to community voices was key to building trust and improving public health. To do this, the initiative used different ways to gather feedback—especially from people in underserved communities. Two major tools helped make this possible: **Systems Thinking** and **Community Consultation Studios**.

Using Systems Thinking

The Social Determinants of COVID-19 Testing and Vaccination Working Group looked at the big picture. They used “systems thinking” to document feedback loops and dynamics within RADx-UP projects that shaped testing in U.S. communities. Central to this approach was the use of storytelling, which transformed individual experiences into compelling narratives that resonated with partners and community members. The group focused on the critical role of social determinants of health that impact COVID-19 testing. In this way, systems thinking emerged as a best practice that not only documents community feedback but also aligns it with actionable insights for promoting health equity and addressing systemic challenges.

For additional information, refer to the [causal loop diagram](#) analyzing how social determinants of health (SDoH) factors influence COVID-19 testing and vaccination outcomes. This resource shows visual diagrams and written explanations of the working group’s insights into community processes and factors that impact COVID-19 testing. It also includes figures illustrating pathways of community engagement that address transportation and access to testing, digital and health literacy, as well as social needs screenings and assistance.

CASE STUDY 5.4 | CAPTURING AND DOCUMENTING COMMUNITY FEEDBACK

Resource Spotlight

JOURNAL PUBLICATION

- A Systems Perspective of How Community-Engaged Public Health Addresses Social Determinants of Health: A Case Study of a Population-Based COVID-19 Testing Program [[Visit Website](#)]

EQUITABLE COVID-19 TESTING: A MULTI-PERSPECTIVE VIEW OF THE COMPLEXITIES

GMB causal loop diagrams visually represent how different elements of a system or intervention are connected, paying specific attention to how different elements interact or cause one another to change.

- Building Community Capacity & Impact: Causal loop diagram explore missing and misinformation's impact on testing [[Visit Website](#)]
- Social Determinants of COVID-19 Testing and Vaccination: Causal loop diagram explored social determinants of health impact on testing [[Visit Website](#)]

Community Consultation Studios

The CDCC also organized a series of small group sessions called Community Consultation Studios (CCS). These studios gave community members a chance to review materials, give feedback, and shape how information was shared. Through three design sessions and two feedback sessions, the CCS sessions helped improve things like the Engagement Resource Center, research summaries, and even images used for outreach.

The CCS model brought together community partners, researchers, and staff in a safe space to share ideas and improve resources. This two-way feedback system made sure that communities were not just being studied—they were helping shape the research itself.

Key Takeaways for Future Public Health Emergencies

RADx-UP showed that strong partnerships between communities and researchers are essential for effective public health responses. The following lessons can guide future efforts:

What Worked Well

- **Partnerships built on trust:** When community members and researchers worked together from the start, it led to better research and long-term relationships. In some cases, community partners even became co-investigators.
- **Tailored outreach:** Using trusted messengers—like local leaders, peer educators, and community health workers—made outreach efforts more effective. Messaging that reflected community values increased participation in testing and vaccination.
- **Culturally relevant communication:** Sharing information in multiple ways (like flyers, radio, social media, and one-on-one conversations) helped reach more people, especially those with limited internet access.
- **Community feedback improved programs:** Projects that built in regular feedback from the community were able to adapt and improve. This helped make programs more effective and responsive to local needs.
- **Science-based and flexible methods:** Using proven research methods while allowing room for flexibility helped meet the unique needs of different communities during the pandemic.

Implementation Challenges and Potential Solutions

Below are key challenges faced during RADx-UP projects and ideas to address them in future public health emergencies:

CHALLENGE	POTENTIAL SOLUTION
1. Sustaining partnerships after projects end	Build shared ownership into the project design and plan for continued engagement beyond funding.
2. Administrative delays (e.g., IRB approvals)	Start administrative processes early and create pre-approved templates to reduce delays.
3. Limited time, staff, and resources	Prioritize funding for community staff and simplify administrative tasks to reduce burden.
4. Barriers to participation	Offer tech support, provide in-person options, and use non-digital outreach methods.
5. Issues with study design (e.g., resistance to randomization)	Use flexible and community-informed research designs that fit real-life conditions.
6. Small sample sizes and limited representation	Use mixed methods and target outreach to underrepresented groups to broaden impact.

Conclusion

In summary, this section explains the benefits and challenges of community-engaged research. It includes examples from many RADx-UP study locations that used creative ideas and successful methods. These examples show how important it is to build trust, create strong connections with the community, and customize projects to fit local needs.

The lessons learned from these initiatives emphasize the critical role of community engagement in achieving health equity and the necessity of fostering trust and collaboration with community partners.

By integrating these best practices, researchers and public health professionals can enhance their efforts to address health disparities and promote equitable access to resources and information during public health emergencies.

Toolkit

1. FEATURED RADx-UP RESOURCES

Practical resources developed directly by the CDCC or RADx-UP projects. These may include publications, guides, or curated tools specific to implementing a program like the RADx-UP initiative.

- **RADx-UP Community Engagement Brief** — A brief summarizing the CDCC’s community-engaged research practices from internal coordination and building trust and relationships with community partners, to creating communities of practice. The intent is to provide a guide for successful community-engaged interventions to reduce illness and raise rates of COVID-19 testing and vaccination within underserved communities. (See Appendix E.1)
- **Equitable COVID-19 Testing: A Multi-Perspective View of the Complexities** — GMB causal loop diagrams visually represent how different elements of a system or intervention are connected, paying specific attention to how different elements interact or cause one another to change.
 - Building Community Capacity and Impact: Causal loop diagram explore missing and misinformation’s impact on testing [[Visit Website](#)]
 - Social Determinants of COVID-19 Testing and Vaccination: Causal loop diagram explored social determinants of health impact on testing [[Visit Website](#)]

Articles:

- Examining COVID-19 testing and vaccination behaviors by heritage and linguistic preferences among Hispanic, Latino, or Spanish RADx-UP participants. [[Visit Website](#)]; (See Appendix C.1 for lay summary)
- A Systems Perspective of How Community-Engaged Public Health Addresses Social Determinants of Health: A Case Study of a Population-Based COVID-19 Testing Program [[Visit Website](#)]

2. SUPPLEMENTAL RESOURCES

Resources developed outside the CDCC but shared via the Engagement Resource Center or by project partners. These materials offer supplemental value and represent real-world utility during a public health emergency response.

- **AAMC Center for Health Justice: The Principles of Trustworthiness** — This toolkit of materials is for organizations to download and use to facilitate discussions within their communities, develop relationships with a broad coalition, and learn track lessons. It includes the kinds of questions, discussions, and activities that will help an organization and its community to unpack the Principles of Trustworthiness, explore how they come to life locally, and determine what local actions might be taken to demonstrate trustworthiness. Contribution to community/academic partnership best practices. [[Visit Website](#)]
- **Do No Harm Guide: Applying Equity Awareness in Data Visualization** — The Urban Institute’s “Do No Harm Guide: Applying Equity Awareness in Data Visualization” provides a framework to build data representation that purposefully and intentionally represent impacted community participants. [[Visit Website](#)]

3. RELEVANT PUBLICATIONS

A list of publications, data sources, or scholarly work that support the evidence base and offer pathways for further reading.

- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Principles of Community Engagement (2nd Edition). Atlanta, GA: CDC/ATSDR Committee on Community Engagement; 2011. Available at: <https://www.atsdr.cdc.gov/community-stress-resource-center/php/resources/principles-of-community-engagement2.html>
- Clinical and Translational Science Awards Consortium Community Engagement Key Function Committee Task Force on the Principles of Community Engagement. Principles of Community Engagement, Second Edition. 2011. <https://ictr.johnshopkins.edu/wp-content/uploads/2015/10/CTSAPrinciplesofCommunityEngagement.pdf>. (Spanish version: Principios de vinculación comunitaria <https://stacks.cdc.gov/view/cdc/26033>.)
- Israel BA, Schulz AJ, Parker EA, Becker AB. Review of community-based research: assessing partnership approaches to improve public health. Annu Rev Public Health. 1998;19:173-202. doi: 10.1146/annurev.publhealth.19.1.173.
- Wallerstein N, Duran B. Community-based participatory research contributions to intervention research: the intersection of science and practice to improve health equity. Am J Public Health. 2010;100(S1):S40-S46.
- Wallerstein N, Oetzel JG, Sanchez-Youngman S, et al. Engage for Equity: A Long-Term Study of Community-Based Participatory Research and Community-Engaged Research Practices and Outcomes. Health Educ Behav. 2020;47(3):380-390. doi:10.1177/1090198119897075
- Eder M, Evans E, Funes M, et al. Defining and measuring community engagement and community-engaged research: clinical and translational science institutional practices. Prog Community Health Partnersh. 2018;12(2):115-116.
- International Association for Public Participation. IAP2 Spectrum of Public Participation. 2018. https://cdn.ymaws.com/www.iap2.org/resource/resmgr/pillars/Spectrum_8.5x11_Print.pdf.

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SECTION THREE: Sharing Results

SECTION THREE OVERVIEW

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This section of the RADx-UP Playbook emphasizes the critical importance of communicating research findings clearly and impactfully. It demonstrates how RADx-UP effectively disseminated results to communities that faced significant barriers both before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. Additionally, this section outlines policy recommendations to strengthen healthcare systems and create lasting improvements for these communities. By being attentive to community needs and employing accessible, culturally relevant communication strategies, RADx-UP enhanced the reach and influence of its research. These efforts supported increased testing and informed policy, to advance equal health opportunities in underserved populations.

Chapter 6: Sharing Information and Communicating Clearly

Summary

This chapter explains how RADx-UP effectively communicated its research findings to audiences in a manner that was clear and easy to understand. There were two primary areas of focus: first, to develop clear messages tailored to the specific needs of diverse communities; and second, to share those messages in a variety of formats.

Key Topics Covered

- **Breaking down communication barriers:** Addressing misinformation or disinformation and working with trusted community members to share accurate messages effectively.
- **Tailoring messages for specific groups:** Creating bespoke messages that reflect the culture and preferences of individual communities.

“As RADx-UP project teams publish findings, they are demonstrating the immense value of community engagement in the work being done and describing the community impact.”

WARREN A. KIBBE, PHD
Co-Principal Investigator,
RADx-UP Coordination and
Data Collection Center

- **Sharing information in multiple formats:** Using social media, websites, videos, and eye-catching graphics to share information.
- **Highlighting real-life examples:** Sharing stories about how community leaders helped spread accurate information and fought against false claims.
- **Optimizing accessibility of communications materials:** Making information available in different languages and formats to be helpful for everyone.

Chapter 7: Policy and Practice

Summary

This chapter explains how the RADx-UP research findings shaped public health policies and practices to better serve communities facing health challenges during the COVID-19 pandemic. It discusses how working closely with communities and policymakers can make healthcare more accessible and effective in the U.S.

Key Topics Covered

- **Creating fair health policies:** Exploring ideas and actions that help everyone, especially those in underserved areas, have access to healthcare and virus testing.
- **Highlighting community health workers:** Sharing success stories of how these workers helped bring healthcare to communities, with a focus on Hispanic populations.
- **Fighting false information:** Suggesting policies that can stop the spread of misinformation or disinformation and build community trust.
- **Sharing real-life examples:** Telling stories about how specific health frameworks, policy ideas, and community-supported solutions made a difference.

Lessons Learned in This Section

RADx-UP showed the importance of working with underserved communities to effectively share health information. Clear, easy-to-understand communication and community-based policies can improve health during a crisis. Key takeaways include:

- The need for messages that fit the culture of the audience
- The role trusted leaders play in stopping false information
- The importance of policies that make healthcare fair and accessible

How do you ensure the correct information reaches the right people at the right time?

Chapter 6 explores the communication strategies RADx-UP used to share research findings, promote trust, and counter misinformation in underserved populations. It highlights how specific messaging, trusted messengers, and accessible materials ensured critical COVID-19 information reached those most at risk.

Key Topics Covered

- Overcoming communication barriers with community-engaged approaches
- Developing culturally relevant, audience-specific messages
- Using multiple channels, including social media, videos, print, and infographics
- Prioritizing accessibility with translations, plain language, and disability-friendly formats
- Building trust through branding, storytelling, and trusted community leaders

Lessons Learned

- Trusted messengers and culturally tailored messages are essential to counter misinformation
- Visual, plain-language materials increase accessibility and engagement
- One-size-fits-all messages fail: tailored approaches meet communities where they are
- Communications are most effective when integrated early and collaboratively with community partners

Case Examples

- **RADx-UP Image Bank:** A repository of 1,200+ culturally representative photos for inclusive health messaging
- **Engagement Resource Center (ERC):** An online hub of 400+ tools, templates, and resources supporting community-engaged communication
- **Storytelling through video:** Community-led stories humanizing research and sharing lived experiences to build trust
- **Misinformation Iceberg Model:** A systems-thinking approach to uncover deeper causes of misinformation and inform communication strategies

In Your Toolkit

Access sample communication templates, infographics, videos, and multilingual materials to support community-centered messaging. Explore tools for building trust, adapting content to local contexts, and sharing research findings in clear, actionable ways that reach diverse audiences.

CHAPTER SIX: SHARING INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATING CLEARLY

PHOTO COURTESY RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

Background

Sharing research and health information clearly and simply was a key part of RADx-UP during the COVID-19 pandemic. The goal was to make sure everyone had **equitable** access to accurate and helpful information about testing and vaccines.

Understanding Communication Barriers

In a fast-moving health crisis like COVID-19, getting the facts to people quickly can be difficult. Misinformation (incorrect or misleading information) and disinformation (false information shared intentionally) make the truth even harder to ascertain. RADx-UP fought these problems by working directly with trusted community leaders like tribal elders, faith leaders, and local health workers. These leaders were able to share correct information, clear up myths, and build trust within their communities.

GLOSSARY

Equitable Health Equity is the state in which everyone has a fair and just opportunity to attain their highest level of health.

TIPS FOR BUILDING TRUST AND SHARING RESEARCH

- Use trusted messengers: People are more likely to listen to information when it comes from someone they know and trust in their community.
- Tailor the message: Adjust the way you share information to fit the needs of different groups. For example, use easy-to-read written materials for older adults or engaging videos for younger audiences.
- Make it simple and clear: Avoid complicated words or long explanations. Use plain language to explain what the research says and why it matters.
- Ask for feedback: Work with community members to learn what they need and how they prefer to receive information.
- Be consistent: Share information regularly and follow up so people feel informed and included.

Why It Matters

RADx-UP showed that giving people timely and accurate information during a health emergency like the COVID-19 pandemic can save lives. By working with trusted leaders and tailoring messages to fit each community, the project helped fight misinformation and build stronger connections between researchers and the public. Effective communication is not about treating everyone the same—it’s about meeting people where they are and making sure they feel heard and respected.

GUAMPDN.COM
Participants sought for UOG COVID-19 study
The University of Guam is looking for Pacific Islander volunteers to part...

The University of Guam team earned publicity in an article in their local newspaper, [‘Pacific Daily News,’](#) generating awareness of the study’s purpose and contributing to Pacific Islander knowledge of COVID-19.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, trust and timely access to testing, contact tracing, quarantining, and treatment had profound impacts on COVID-19 outcomes. Throughout the program, RADx-UP working groups collected insights about how misinformation or missing information impacts equitable

access to COVID-19 testing. They demonstrated their findings through systems thinking models. These are highlighted in the chapter case studies (See [Case Study 5.4](#)). The teams developed a [causal loop diagram](#), which visually represents how different elements of a system or intervention are connected. They paid specific attention to how different elements interact and cause one another to change. In addition to analyzing the societal impacts of misinformation, RADx-UP created an analysis of how communication challenges delay the sharing of critical health information with communities. The diagram illustrates how public uncertainty about the science, poor communication of research findings, and varying levels of science literacy can impede the uptake of government health recommendations.

Communication Strategies

The RADx-UP program used different methods to make research findings easy to understand and useful for both researchers and communities. The RADx-UP CDCC's Research Communications and Engagement Team included skilled professionals in areas like digital media, simple writing, and creative design. They started by figuring out what communication tools were needed and then worked with project sites, researchers, and the general public to share them. The team sought community feedback to guide decisions about what kinds of materials to create for communities.

FOCUS ON COMMUNICATION THAT REFLECTS AUDIENCE PREFERENCES

The RADx-UP CDCC worked closely with community partners, researchers, doctors, and public health officials to learn about the needs of different groups. They also studied how people preferred to get information. They found that research participants wanted to see themselves reflected in study materials. This led to the RADx-UP Image Bank project, where local photographers captured pictures of COVID-19 testing in communities. How the Image Bank was created is explained in the case studies in this chapter.

Audience-Tailored Approaches

The RADx-UP team used audience feedback to create materials that matched the needs of different groups. They considered things like language, location, education level, age, and literacy. For example, in Texas, they made a guide called *Cuídate Texas!* in English and Spanish (See Appendix F.1). It used graphic novel-style illustrations to show a conversation between a mother and son about the importance of COVID-19 testing. This creative approach helped make the message clear and relatable for local communities.

In another example, the RADx-UP Engaging Black/African Americans Working Group showed how cultural community needs can vary by geography. African American populations in Kansas will be culturally different from those in Harlem. Some people preferred written information, while others liked videos or presentations. By listening to communities, RADx-UP adjusted messages to suit the specific needs of specific audiences. This direct engagement helped avoid treating underserved groups as if they were all the same.

FIGURE 6.2: RADx-UP PROJECT EXAMPLE

Key Messages

During the COVID-19 pandemic, clear and focused messages were essential to fighting misinformation. RADx-UP identified key points to share consistently across all projects:

- Trust in science and its use in public health
- Trust in local health providers
- Confidence in the accuracy of testing and vaccines
- Transparency in COVID-19 data

These messages supported advice from organizations like the CDC and HHS. Basic information, like how to use COVID tests or check their expiration dates, was easy to share across different communities. By focusing on these key ideas from the beginning, RADx-UP projects were able to provide reliable and up-to-date information to the public.

Branding

Early in the program, the RADx-UP CDCC Communications Team created a strong and clear brand identity. They designed a logo, selected colors, and created a brand guide to use for meetings, materials, and websites. They also made presentation templates for projects using approved photos and created a guide to help researchers share their data clearly.

Consistent branding made RADx-UP's research more credible and helped share the program's results through documents like policy briefs and research papers. Projects were encouraged to use the branding tools provided by RADx-UP, while also customizing them to fit their local communities. This helped projects take pride in their outreach and make their efforts more meaningful to their audiences.

Accessibility

The RADx-UP Communications team prioritized making their materials usable by everyone. They followed rules to make online content easy to read, including for people with hearing or vision challenges. They translated select materials into 16 different languages, such as Spanish, Marshallese, and more, and had experts check the translations to make sure they were accurate and culturally appropriate.

To make science easier to understand, they avoided using scientific terms and instead used simple language and visuals like charts and pictures to help people understand the information.

By starting with these methods, organizations can make their research easier to access and understand, leading to better communication and stronger community connections.

Information Sharing Strategies

With their communication strategies in place, the team used several methods to share information and reach audiences, including social media, email newsletters, and online platforms. In all of these formats, the emphasis was on making communications visible and engaging.

PHOTO COURTESY RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

ONLINE PRESENCE

• **Websites**

The RADx-UP.org website was a public webpage managed by the CDCC. It included news, updates on grant-funded programs, details about individual projects, maps and demographics of populations served, events, results, funding opportunities, and a resource library called the Engagement Resource Center (ERC). The ERC held over 400 resources, such as research briefs, multimedia tools, articles, and outreach materials. RADx-UP projects across the country created many of these tools, sharing them publicly to ensure transparency in their work.

The team also developed a secure web portal called **myRADx-UPhome** (MRUH) for RADx-UP members. This portal provided private resources like data guides, grant applications, and a platform for collaboration. Some materials were public, but others required a secure login.

Together, these websites served as the main information hub for the government’s efforts to address health disparities during the COVID-19 pandemic.

• **Social Media**

RADx-UP used Twitter/X (@RADxUP) and LinkedIn to share news, resources, and research findings. They also connected with working groups online to keep communication open and ongoing, even after the grant period ended.

• **Videos**

The team worked with a storytelling agency called Complex Stories to make educational videos on testing, to highlight research projects and share stories about communities’ experiences with research, COVID-19 testing, and vaccinations. The videos included interviews and short stories, helping to build trust and make the research more transparent to both the public and research teams.

FIGURE 6.3: RADx-UP WEBSITE METRICS

DATA VISUALIZATIONS

• Dashboards

The CDCC created several dashboards on the RADx-UP.org website to share updated project data. Using Microsoft Power BI, the RADx-UP **Data Dashboard** let people see project locations, participant details, and testing data. Another dashboard, called the **Publications Dashboard**, collected and showcased research papers related to RADx-UP, making it easier for users to find and learn from them.

FIGURE 6.4: EXAMPLES OF CDCC INTERACTIVE DASHBOARDS

• **Infographics**

To make complex information easier to understand, the CDCC designed clear and simple infographics. These included maps showing where projects took place, details about the people involved, and statistics like grant amounts or total participants. These visuals were shared on the RADx-UP website, used in government reports, and included in presentations to help explain the program’s success across the U.S.

Resource Spotlight

CDCC Data Visualization Style Guide — Data

Visualization Guidance includes colors, fonts, formats, and a reference tool for picking the right visualization for your data. (See Appendix F.2)

BRIEFS, REPORTS AND LAY SUMMARIES

The RADx-UP CDCC created briefs, reports, and simple research summaries to share RADx-UP findings. The CDCC Community Engagement team worked with research teams to make research summaries that turned complicated studies into clear and short documents. The RADx-UP CDCC teamed up with researchers to create **31** research summaries based on study results. These summaries were available in English, Spanish, and sometimes other languages, helping more people understand the findings.

Lay summaries of dense policy briefs were valuable when sharing publicly with communities and policymakers. Partnerships with policy groups such as the Duke Margolis Institute for Health Policy at Duke University made this possible. These simplified versions helped share the main ideas of scholarly works with a lay audience. Finally, the CDCC compiled all information-sharing materials, including presentations, maps, infographics, and publications, to create reports for the National Institutes of Health on RADx-UP activities and results.

Resource Spotlight
RESEARCH BRIEF EXAMPLES

- Research Brief in English: **Community Testing and SARS-CoV-2 Rates for Latinxs in Baltimore** (See Appendix F.3); [\[Watch Video\]](#)
- Research Brief in Spanish: **COVID-19 Vaccine Hesitancy in Delaware's Underserved Communities** (See Appendix F.4)

FIGURE 6.6: EXAMPLES OF RESEARCH BRIEFS

The figure displays three research briefs side-by-side, each in a different language: English, Spanish, and Marshallese. Each brief follows a similar layout with a title, background, purpose, key findings, and conclusions. The English brief is titled 'Assessment of Racial and Ethnic Disparities in Access to COVID-19 Vaccination Sites in Brooklyn, New York'. The Spanish brief is titled 'Experiencias de los trabajadores de atención de la salud de raza negra y latina en funciones de apoyo durante la pandemia de COVID-19: Un estudio cualitativo'. The Marshallese brief is titled 'MELELE'. Each brief includes a logo for RADx-UP and a small icon representing the language.

DIRECT COMMUNICATIONS

The CDCC communicated directly with project teams across the country. As part of the RADx-UP program, projects received a regular newsletter, first biweekly, then monthly, and later quarterly. This newsletter, sent to research staff and community partners, included updates like tasks to do, special events, project highlights, and new resources. It helped build a sense of teamwork among all participants. Members used this newsletter to stay updated on deadlines, research achievements, and outreach activities.

FIGURE 6.7: EXAMPLES OF CONTENT SHARED IN THE CDCC NEWSLETTER

PUBLICATIONS SUPPORT

The CDCC also provided help with publications, guiding research teams on efforts from analyzing data to writing papers, submitting them to journals, and creating easy-to-read summaries of their findings. For example, CDCC publications staff worked on special journal editions that focused on important public health topics during the COVID-19 pandemic. These editions, published in respected journals like the *American Journal of Public Health (AJPH)* journal and *Pediatrics*, highlighted the challenges of engaging communities, supporting children's health, and tackling issues like returning to school safely.

To make publishing easier, the CDCC launched the Partnering for Impact initiative. This effort supported researchers in creating publications based on shared data from the RADx-UP Data Hub. The process was well-organized, involving steps to write and review abstracts, prepare scientific presentations, and complete research papers for publication in professional journals.

Communications Impact on RADx-UP

RADx-UP's communication strategies led to many positive results:

- **Easier access to public health research:** By working with community groups and trusted health leaders, RADx-UP made it simpler for underserved communities to understand important research findings.
- **Better understanding of public health:** Tools like research summaries, infographics, and simplified reports helped researchers and communities work together and share knowledge more effectively.
- **Broader reach through cultural adaptation:** RADx-UP created materials in different languages and formats to meet the needs of diverse communities, making their public health messages more relatable and impactful.

Journal Supplement Collaborations:

The RADx-UP CDCC worked with the American Journal of Public Health (AJPH) to publish two special issues that shared important lessons from the program's research. The first issue, [released in November 2022](#), featured articles from RADx-UP study teams on topics like increasing COVID-19 testing, addressing vaccine hesitancy, testing in prisons, and how community partnerships helped improve health outcomes. The second issue, [published in May 2024](#), focused on the importance of trust and equal partnerships between researchers and communities. A key [article](#) by leaders from the National Institutes of Health highlighted that strong community engagement made testing efforts more successful, health disparities must be addressed, and schools should be part of future pandemic plans. These journal issues helped spread RADx-UP's findings to more people in public health and research.

Case Studies

The case studies in this chapter highlight how RADx-UP used culturally tailored communications and multimedia tools to build trust, counter misinformation, and share research findings with underserved communities. These stories illustrate how trusted messengers, community imagery, and accessible platforms played a vital role in amplifying the initiative's public health impact.

1. The Role of Story Sharing Through Presentations and Videos:

Emphasizes how RADx-UP used community storytelling to humanize data and communicate public health messages, employing video interviews and presentations to build understanding and trust.

2. Misinformation and Missing Information – The Iceberg Model:

Uses systems thinking to visualize and analyze how misinformation obstructs equitable COVID-19 testing, revealing deeper societal patterns and assumptions.

3. Engagement Resource Center (ERC): Describes the creation of a centralized, searchable hub of over 400 community-submitted resources to support engagement, outreach, and health education across the RADx-UP network.

4. The RADx-UP Image Bank: Highlights the development of a digital repository of over 1,200 community-centered photographs, addressing gaps in representative imagery and fostering connection through culturally reflective visuals.

5. RADx-UP Scientific Meetings: Showcases a series of consortium-wide webinars where academic and community partners co-presented findings to share lessons learned and promote real-time knowledge exchange across the network.

CASE STUDY 6.1

THE ROLE OF STORY SHARING THROUGH PRESENTATIONS AND VIDEOS

One of the key parts of the RADx-UP initiative was the use of storytelling to share information in a relatable and human way. RADx-UP Working Groups found that sharing people's personal stories through interviews, photos, and videos helped make the data more meaningful. These stories showed the challenges that different communities faced and helped others better understand social issues affecting health. Sharing these stories also helped build stronger connections between community members, organizations, and healthcare workers. Stories were collected during regular meetings and events held with community partners.

Examples of the stories shared in RADx-UP projects include:

- A spotlight on the RADx-UP project COV-IDD: Testing for COVID-19 in High-Risk Children with Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities. [[Watch Video](#)]
- A spotlight on the RADx-UP project COVID-19 racial/ethnic disparities in Northwest Arkansas (NWA). [[Watch Video](#)]
- A spotlight on the RADx-UP project "Using COVID-19 Testing and Risk Communication Strategies to Accelerate Students' Return to School," which is based at the University of Washington St. Louis. [[Watch Video](#)]
- An in-depth interview with Community Health Worker (CHW), Satta Johnson [[Watch Video](#)]
- RP2 Project Spotlight: Connecting People Experiencing Homelessness and Housing Instability to Rapid COVID-19 Testing. [[Watch Video](#)]

CASE STUDY 6.2

MISINFORMATION AND MISSING INFORMATION: AN ICEBERG MODEL OF EQUITABLE COVID-19 TESTING

The Building Community Capacity and Impact Working Group teamed up with the CDCC's Group Model Building team to explore how misinformation or missing information affects fair access to COVID-19 testing. They used the Iceberg Model to show both what's easy to see and what's hidden beneath the surface of this issue. At the top, above the waterline, are things we can measure, like gaps in testing access. Below the water, the model highlights deeper influences like patterns, systems, and people's beliefs or assumptions that shape what happens above. RADx-UP partners helped explain how these hidden factors lead to the events we observe, as shown in the table on the right. This approach is a powerful tool for uncovering common assumptions that affect public health decisions and can guide how we share information with communities.

CASE STUDY 6.2 | MISINFORMATION AND MISSING INFORMATION

FIGURE 6.8: ICEBERG MODEL OF EQUITABLE COVID-19 TESTING

CASE STUDY 6.3

ENGAGEMENT RESOURCE CENTER

The Engagement Resource Center (ERC) served as a hub of valuable resources designed for researchers, community partners, and individuals seeking information about community health. Located on the RADx-UP CDCC website, it emphasizes topics such as COVID-19 testing, vaccines, health treatments, and promotion of equity in healthcare. It also provides strategies for effective community engagement and research participation.

These resources include guides, data visuals, flyers, videos, reports, and social media toolkits. Each resource is accompanied by its own dedicated page, offering detailed information and clear instructions, such as “download” or “watch,” to facilitate interaction.

The ERC helps users find resources quickly with a filtered search function by research topic or type.

ERC Key Highlights:

- Major achievements: The ERC was developed through the collaborative efforts of project teams and community partners.
- Resource count: The platform includes 411 resources, most of which were contributed by project teams. The top 82 resources have been viewed over 100 times.

Important Lessons Learned:

- Feedback from community participants is essential and having a transparent process to use that feedback responsibly is also important.
- Clearly defining the scope of content for the ERC page helped avoid redundancy with other websites and repositories.
- Close collaboration with the communications team was vital to the ERC’s success.
- Community members and project teams engaging with the ERC represent a sample of the RADx-UP consortium, offering insights into effective practices.

CASE STUDY 6.3 | ENGAGEMENT RESOURCE CENTER

FIGURE 6.9: EXAMPLE OF THE ENGAGEMENT RESOURCE CENTER (ERC)

The screenshot displays the Engagement Resource Center (ERC) interface. At the top, there is a search bar labeled "Search...". Below it are three filter menus: "AUDIENCE", "TOPIC AREAS", and "RESOURCE TYPE". The main content area is a grid of resource cards, each with a colored header and a brief description. The cards include:

- VIDEO: RADx-UP Puipuia Le Ola (Protecting Life) Study**: Audience: Researcher; Topic: COVID-19 Testing, Healthy Behavior, Health; Resource Type: Communications & Social Media Toolkits.
- Video: Welcome to the RADx-UP Project**: Audience: Public, Researcher; Topic: COVID-19 Testing, COVID-19 Vaccination; Resource Type: Communications & Social Media Toolkits.
- Why Does COVID-19 Testing Still Matter?**: Audience: Public; Topic: COVID-19 Testing; Resource Type: Flyers/posters/handouts.
- What to do if You Test Positive for COVID-19**: Audience: Public; Topic: COVID-19 Health and Treatment, COVID-19 Testing; Resource Type: Flyers/posters/handouts.
- What to do if You Test Negative for COVID-19**: Audience: Public; Topic: COVID-19 Health and Treatment, COVID-19 Testing; Resource Type: Flyers/posters/handouts.
- Why Does COVID-19 Testing Still Matter? Powerpoint (English)**: Audience: Public; Topic: COVID-19 Testing, COVID-19 Vaccination; Resource Type: Flyers/posters/handouts.
- UHERO Report**: Audience: Researcher, Public; Topic: COVID-19 Vaccination, Community Engagement, Legal/Policy; Resource Type: Reports.
- Water Bottle Labels for Findings**: Audience: Public, Researcher; Topic: Community Engagement, COVID-19 Research Findings; Resource Type: Communications & Social Media Toolkits.

Recommendations to Follow

PROCESS TIPS:

The ERC model can combat widespread health misinformation. Here are a few essential process tips:

- Engage partners early and include diverse expertise.
- Establish clear channels for collecting feedback and demonstrate accountability for applying that feedback.
- Create new resources when gaps are identified.
- Include community-generated products alongside traditional research outputs, especially when rapid dissemination and relevance to communities are priorities.

DESIGN TIPS FOR ERC PAGES:

- Searchability: Make resources easily searchable by keywords, tags, and categories for topics, audience types, and resource types.
- Color coding: Use color coding to clearly identify different resource types.
- Language tags: Explicitly note the languages in which a resource is available.

CASE STUDY 6.3 | ENGAGEMENT RESOURCE CENTER

Resource Spotlight

Watch a short video [here](#).

JOURNAL PUBLICATION

Reflections on the Development of a Nationwide Community-Engaged Resource Center During the COVID-19 Pandemic — Shares learnings and recommendations related to the entire Engagement Resource Center process. [[Visit Website](#)]

ADDITIONAL RESOURCE

Refining Scholarship — This document provides guidance for uplifting community-generated knowledge and associated products as equally important as research products created in academic settings. It breaks down the types of products this might include and suggests next steps. (See Appendix F.5)

CASE STUDY 6.4

THE RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

Using images that portray real people and their communities can encourage more individuals—particularly those from underrepresented groups—to participate in research. The RADx-UP Image Bank features a collection of 1,222 unique photographs representing diverse communities across the United States.

This Image Bank was established in response to community feedback that the populations served by RADx-UP, such as communities of color and low-income groups, were often absent from the standard stock photos typically used for communications. In contrast, the RADx-UP Image Bank provides representative and accessible images suitable for various materials, including newsletters, social media posts, and educational content. By offering images that resonate with the communities involved, RADx-UP helps projects create materials that are more personal and inclusive. The Image Bank serves as a strong example for other researchers or programs looking to develop communication tools that accurately represent the people they engage with.

Community photographers captured vibrant images at seven different project sites, showcasing people in their everyday environments. RADx-UP Project Coordinators worked with local photographers to organize photo shoots and recruited models from nearby communities. These models represented the diversity of RADx-UP participants, including differences in race, gender, age, and more. The photos included settings like schools, clinics, community centers, testing sites, and places of worship. For privacy and safety, photographers staged clinical scenes, such as COVID-19 testing or vaccination sites. Participants generously gave their consent to use their images, signing forms to ensure proper permissions. Each individual received a \$150 gift card as a thank you for their time, while partnering community sites were awarded a \$500 honorarium for their valuable support. Through these efforts, the project created a powerful collection of images that truly reflected the communities it aimed to serve.

CASE STUDY 6.4 | THE RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

FIGURE 6.10: EXAMPLES FROM THE RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

CASE STUDY 6.4 | THE RADx-UP IMAGE BANK**Resource Spotlight****JOURNAL PUBLICATION**

Development and Utilization of the RADx-UP Image Bank, A Digital Photography Repository. This publication shares learnings and recommendations related to the Image Bank. [[Visit Website](#)]

RADx-UP IMAGE BANK: SUPPORTING DOCUMENT TYPES

The following table highlights the core documents developed to support the RADx-UP Image Bank. These resources guided the collection, submission, and use of photographs across the initiative to ensure representative visual storytelling.

DOCUMENT NAME	DESCRIPTION
Image Bank Scope of Work	Outlines the goals, roles, and expectations for collecting, managing, and using image assets. (See Appendix F.6)
Image Bank Photographer Info Sheet	Outlines tasks and support roles for maintaining effective working group operations.
Image Bank Photo Submission Guidelines	Provides key guidance for interested photographers, including the photographer selection and contracting.
Image Bank Consent Forms (Minor/Adult)	Offers step-by-step instructions for submitting images, including formatting and labeling details.

CASE STUDY 6.5

RADx-UP SCIENTIFIC MEETINGS

RADx-UP held annual scientific meetings to showcase the progress of its projects, share data, and discuss solutions to fight COVID-19. These virtual webinars brought together researchers and community partners to:

- Share study progress and increase knowledge within the RADx-UP community.
- Present preliminary or finalized data and insights.
- Encourage teamwork between researchers and community co-presenters.

The Scientific Meeting series provided a real-time window into study progress on some of RADx-UP's 137 projects. The meetings gave teams a chance to share what they had learned and how they had worked with communities during the COVID-19 pandemic. The main audience included RADx-UP project teams, NIH leadership, and anyone interested in updates about outreach and testing efforts for underserved populations. Each presentation featured a team of researchers and community representatives, emphasizing collaboration.

By opening the series to the public, RADx-UP created a space where data, insights, and challenges could be exchanged freely — providing project teams with opportunities to share what they learned and how they had collaborated.

These meetings achieved several milestones:

- Showcased collaborations and real-time results before projects concluded.
- Discussed methods, findings, and challenges to refine study strategies.
- Published meeting materials like recordings and reports for broader knowledge-sharing.
- Connected diverse populations and study settings for future opportunities.

The series served as a hub for learning, collaboration, and progress, strengthening connections between academic research and community impact.

CASE STUDY 6.5 | RADx-UP SCIENTIFIC MEETINGS

Examples of Scientific Meeting Findings and Reflections

The Scientific Meeting series produced dozens of project presentations co-led by researchers and community partners.

For example, the Cherokee PROTECT project featured a presentation by a Cherokee Nation representative along with a researcher from the University of Oklahoma Health Sciences. The project team trained groups from schools, clinics and community centers on how to use newly available COVID-19 home tests. They explained the study methods. Using collected testing data, the team was able to analyze positivity rates in virus hotspots within the geographic population and compared this with hospitalization rates. The project's study findings and reflections included data to support recommendations to the Cherokee Nation to intensify testing efforts in Cherokee National Health Systems facilities to mitigate virus spread. The study team distributed 100,000 testing and vaccination information brochures within the community and shared plans to test new ways to reach Cherokee Nation populations to encourage virus testing, to stop the spread of COVID-19.

CHEROKEE PROTECT

Sohail Khan (Cherokee Nation); Amanda Janitz (University of Oklahoma Health Sciences)

[\[Watch Video\]](#)

CASE STUDY 6.5 | RADx-UP SCIENTIFIC MEETINGS

In another example, Northwestern University partnered with a local LGBTQ youth center to study community-engaged strategies for understanding COVID-19 disparities impacting sexual and gender minority and racial/ethnic minority youth and young adults. The study conducted a nationwide online survey to understand participants' perceptions of testing and vaccination, as well as how the COVID-19 pandemic impacted their identity. Another aim was to test messaging about virus perceptions, knowledge, and behaviors. More than 1,000 participants completed the surveys in all 50 states and Puerto Rico. The team presented data collected from the surveys, including:

- 95% of respondents agreed that mask-wearing was beneficial
- 75% had been tested in the past, with 11% testing positive at one time.

A key takeaway was that strong community partnerships developed during the process of creating and collecting survey data.

COMMUNITY-ENGAGED STRATEGIES TO UNDERSTAND COVID-19 DISPARITIES IMPACTING SEXUAL AND GENDER MINORITY AND RACIAL/ETHNIC MINORITY YOUTH AND YOUNG ADULTS

Gregory Phillips and Megan Ruprecht
(Northwestern University)

[\[Watch Video\]](#)

Key Takeaways for Future Public Health Emergencies

The RADx-UP program emphasizes the importance of clear and relatable communication during public health emergencies (PHEs). Its strategies provide practical insights for addressing future crises.

- Research teams work with trusted community leaders to deliver critical messages effectively.
- Organizations tailor messages to meet the specific needs of diverse communities rather than relying on uniform communication.
- Efforts focus on simplifying complex information through plain language and visuals, ensuring accessibility for all.
- Stakeholders actively combat misinformation by spreading accurate facts faster than false information circulates.
- The program integrates communication into every part of its initiatives, highlighting the role of relationship-building as a key component.

Conclusion

During a public health emergency, collaboration between communities and organizations proves essential for delivering trusted scientific information about testing, interventions, and solutions. RADx-UP demonstrated success by prioritizing community engagement and ensuring messages were easy to understand.

Effective Strategies:

- Engaging local health leaders to foster trust within communities.
- Developing messages with input from community members to reflect their perspectives and needs.
- Providing materials in multiple languages to accommodate linguistic diversity.
- Using varied communication channels, such as social media and community events, to reach broader audiences.

By making science accessible and incorporating community feedback, RADx-UP reduced health disparities during the COVID-19 pandemic. These strategies offer a promising model for supporting underserved populations in future emergencies.

Toolkit

1. FEATURED RADx-UP RESOURCES

Practical resources developed directly by the CDCC or RADx-UP projects. These may include publications, guides, or curated tools specific to implementing a program like the RADx-UP initiative.

- **CDCC Data Visualization Style Guide** — Data Visualization Guidance includes colors, fonts, formats, and a reference tool for picking the right visualization for your data. (See Appendix F.2)
- **Refining Scholarship** — This document provides guidance for how to uplift and refer to community-generated knowledge and associated products as equally important to research products created in academic settings. It breaks down the types of products this might include and suggests next steps. (See Appendix F.5)
- **Diverse Communities Require Diversity in Messaging Virtual Townhall** — This virtual townhall highlights how using trusted messengers and community-tailored messages can improve public health communication during COVID-19. Presenters share lessons from Harlem and Kansas on building trust and crafting messages that meet local needs.
 - **Malcolm Punter, EdD (Harlem, NY):** Shares how understanding historical barriers to healthcare and working with trusted community partners helped create effective, local messaging through virtual townhalls. [[Watch Video](#)]
 - **Ian Knight (Kansas):** Discusses how his team used research and local input to shape messages that reached diverse populations across Kansas. [[Watch Video](#)]
- **What to do if You Test Positive for COVID-19** — You've tested positive for COVID-19. Now what? This flyer outlines steps to take to care for yourself and help protect others. Example of a handout about COVID guidance if testing positive. (Appendix F.7)
- **Why Does COVID-19 Testing Still Matter?** — This flyer speaks to the role of COVID-19 testing as a continued public health measure to keep our communities healthy. Testing helps treat high-risk cases early. Also, it helps us know when to adjust safety precautions, like indoor masking. Testing assists in areas with low vaccination rates. It helps prevent a resurgence and monitor vaccines. (See Appendix F.8) ; [[Watch Video](#)]
- **Las Pruebas de COVID-19 Siguen Siendo Importantes (FOLLETO)** — This flyer speaks to the role of COVID-19 testing as a continued public health measure to keep our communities healthy. Testing helps treat high-risk cases early. Also, it helps us know when to adjust safety precautions, like indoor masking. Testing assists in areas with low vaccination rates. It helps prevent a resurgence and monitor vaccines. Available in English and Spanish. Example of handout about the importance of COVID-19 testing in lay language in Spanish. [[Download PDF](#)]

Examples from RADx-UP Projects:

- **#Vax4Community** — #Vax4Community is a social marketing campaign to build vaccine confidence and use and reduce health disparities in New York City. A good example of culturally tailored communications campaign. [[Visit Website](#)]
- **Addressing COVID-19 Testing Inequities Among Underserved Populations in Massachusetts (MA) – Lay Research Summary** — A lay language summary of the research findings published in the journal *Frontiers in Public Health* that includes a QR code to the full article. A good example of a lay summary written by a project rather than the CDCC. (See Appendix F.9)
- **El Sol: COVID-19 Comic Toolkit** — Through the years, El Sol has engaged and deployed highly trained lay workers as community health workers (CHWs) and promotores de salud. Their website provides tools, training, and other resources to aid CHWs and promotores in serving their communities. The comic series illustrates topics related to COVID-19 including vaccination, financial stress, emotional support, and exercise. Materials are available in both English and Spanish. Offers community health worker tools and education related to COVID-19 in English and Spanish. [[Visit Website](#)]
- **Juntos, We Can Stop COVID-19!** — Juntos, We Can Stop COVID-19 is a digital communication campaign in English and Spanish to help Latino families take action to slow the spread of coronavirus. The #JuntosStopCovid campaign features Latino culturally relevant, bilingual fact sheets, infographics, and video role model stories. See and share the #JuntosStopCovid campaign in English and Spanish. Example of culturally tailored public health communication materials. [[Visit Website](#)]
- **Native Hawaiian and Pacific Islander COVID-19 Dissemination Webinar** — Webinar hosted by Papa Ola Lokahi and the Native Hawaiian and Pacific Islander COVID-19 Response Team to help Puipuia le Ola staff to share the study's findings with scholars and community health leaders. Easily accessible dissemination of project findings in the Pacific Islander-Native Hawaiian communities. [[Visit Website](#)]
- **Tailored Recruitment Messaging: Increasing representation of Black communities in COVID-19 home testing and surveillance data** — Represent ATL created these recruitment materials after analyzing focus groups of 29 community members tasked with reacting to COVID-19 collateral developed by CDC and Morehouse School of Medicine. The goal was to tailor messaging to the Black community that underscored the importance of COVID-19 testing for individual and public health. (Appendix F.10)

2. SUPPLEMENTAL RESOURCES

Resources developed outside the CDCC but shared via the Engagement Resource Center or by project partners. These materials offer supplemental value and represent real-world utility during a PHE response.

- **Communicating about COVID-19 Vaccinations: Recommendations for Hawai'i** - Now that COVID-19 vaccines are more readily available, the next major public health challenge facing the state is getting people vaccinated. According to a recent study by a team of researchers led by the University of Hawai'i at Manoa College of Social Sciences as part of their Health Policy Initiative, targeted communications strategies may hold the key to encouraging more eligible people to get vaccinated. This page includes a full report and accompanying webinar. These recommendations will continue to be applicable for future research in Hawai'i. [\[Visit Website\]](#)
- **Cuádate Texas!: Tailored COVID-19 Communication** — Guides study participants in Rio Grande Valley, Houston, and Northeast Texas through a conversation between a mother and son about the importance of getting tested for COVID-19 after exposure, using regional specifics in names and language. Good example of culturally tailored public health communications. (See Appendix F.1)
- **Do No Harm Guide: Applying Equity Awareness in Data Visualization** — The Urban Institute's "Do No Harm Guide: Applying Equity Awareness in Data Visualization" provides a framework to build data representation that purposefully and intentionally represent impacted community participants. [\[Visit Website\]](#)
- **COVID-19 Materials Developed for Tribal Use** — The Johns Hopkins Center for American Indian Health has developed materials related to COVID-19 for tribes to distribute in partnership with Indian Health Service and with support from the Walmart Foundation. Example of a health resources library for COVID-19 resources specific to Native American communities. [\[Visit Website\]](#)

3. RELEVANT PUBLICATIONS

A list of publications, data sources, or scholarly work that support the evidence base and offer pathways for further reading.

- **Reflections on the Development of a Nationwide Community-Engaged Resource Center During the COVID-19 Pandemic** — Shares learnings and recommendations related to the entire Engagement Resource Center process. [\[Visit Website\]](#)
- **Development and Utilization of the RADx-UP Image Bank, A Digital Photography Repository** — This publication shares learnings and recommendations related to the Image Bank. [\[Visit Website\]](#)
- **Reflections on the Development of a Nationwide Community-Engaged Resource Center During the COVID-19 Pandemic** — Shares learnings and recommendations related to the entire Engagement Resource Center process. [\[Visit Website\]](#)

How can research shape real-world change in underserved populations?

Chapter 7 demonstrates how research findings influenced public health policies to reduce disparities in COVID-19 testing and care. It shows how community engagement and collaboration with policymakers helped to improve healthcare access and delivery in underserved populations during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Key Topics Covered

- **Health equity policy framework:** Strategies for removing barriers and improving testing access through community-based approaches.
- **Role of community health workers (CHWs):** Policies to integrate CHWs into healthcare systems to expand culturally relevant care.
- **Misinformation countermeasures:** Recommendations for policies to combat false information and build trust in vulnerable communities.

Lessons Learned

- Community engagement must guide every step of policy development.
- CHWs should be formally recognized, supported, and funded to enhance health equity.
- Addressing misinformation is essential for public health success.
- Policies need cultural and linguistic relevance to be effective.

In Your Toolkit

Access the RADx-UP Health Equity Policy Framework, policy briefs, and ready-to-use tools for developing community-informed policy strategies. These resources can support researchers, providers, and policymakers in creating more equitable, culturally responsive, and community-driven public health solutions.

OVERVIEW

Case Examples

- **RADx-UP Health Equity Policy Framework:** Presented actionable strategies to strengthen equitable, community-based testing and guide future pandemic responses
- **Policy Paper on Community Health Workers:** Offered policy recommendations to formally recognize and fund CHWs as essential healthcare team members, improving care access in Hispanic and underserved communities
- **ABC Science Collaborative:** Used real-time data and partnerships with North Carolina schools to show that masking could prevent COVID-19 spread in classrooms, leading to statewide policy changes that supported safe in-person learning
- **Third Annual Equity Evidence Academy:** Explored how risk communication affected public trust, behavior, and policy adherence, emphasizing the need for trusted messengers and tailored messaging

CHAPTER SEVEN: POLICY AND PRACTICE

PHOTO COURTESY RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

Background

During the COVID-19 pandemic, it became clear that public policies needed to include and support local communities. Many underserved groups faced higher infection and **mortality** rates compared to the wider population. RADx-UP sought to close these gaps by teaming up with community partners to improve access to testing and care. For many communities, challenges like poorly located test sites, limited hours, and lack of insurance created serious obstacles to COVID-19 testing. Even before the pandemic, underserved groups struggled to access basic healthcare, and the crisis only made things worse. At first, public health efforts to reduce infections focused on broad, general strategies instead of targeting specific areas and populations that needed the most help. Poor communication and unclear public health messages—usually only offered in English—added to the confusion. The solutions for these issues showed how policies could address major structural problems, such as socioeconomic and racial inequalities that blocked access to care and testing.

GLOSSARY

Mortality The number of deaths in a group of people over time

Several RADx-UP projects worked on creating policies to reduce the spread of COVID-19 in underserved communities. At the same time, governments at the local, state, and federal level were integral to developing a range of policies to control the COVID-19 pandemic's impact on population health (Whitsel, et al., 2023). While government responses played an important role, this chapter focuses on how RADx-UP brought people together and involved communities in crafting public health policies. It also highlights ways to adjust these policies to improve healthcare for underserved populations.

Policy and Practice Implications

The term “**policy**” refers to regulations, procedures, or actions that a public or private organization or institution uses to achieve a goal, grouped into the following categories:

- Access
- Resource allocation
- Data
- Communication and messaging
- Payment

Three common strategies, or foundational components, are:

- Community engagement
- Cross-sector partnerships
- Regulatory guidance such as laws and protocols

Select RADx-UP projects offered a range of strategies and recommendations to incorporate effective policy responses during a pandemic.

GLOSSARY

Policy refers to regulations, procedures, or actions that a public or private organization or institution uses to achieve a goal, grouped into the following strategies: access, resource allocation, data, communication and messaging, and payment.

ASKING QUESTIONS TO INFORM POLICY

RADx-UP demonstrated how research rooted in community partnerships can influence public policy and reshape systems. Across the initiative, projects tackled urgent questions like:

- Can masking and testing allow for the safe return of children to school?
- Can community health workers increase access to and uptake of SARS-CoV-2 tests in communities?

In both cases, the answer was yes, and the path to impact was paved by research-based recommendations and collaboration.

SAFE RETURN TO SCHOOL: A POLICY SHIFT THROUGH THE ABC SCIENCE COLLABORATIVE

In the early months of the COVID-19 pandemic, schools closed under the assumption that reopening would increase virus spread. The ABC Science Collaborative, which is supported by RADx-UP, dispelled that notion by collecting real-time data from over 100 school districts across North Carolina. Their findings showed that when people were using masks correctly, schools could reopen safely—even with classrooms and buses at full capacity. Their work, summarized in a widely circulated lay report, helped shift state policy and set national strategies for reopening based on science, not fear.

The RADx-UP CDCC partnership with the ABC Science Collaborative not only informed local school boards; it also influenced quarantine policy, masking guidance, and states' use of in-school transmission metrics for public health decision-making. The data collected helped reduce unnecessary student quarantines, preserve in-person learning, and promote equitable access to education.

SCALING ACCESS THROUGH CHWS: FROM EVIDENCE TO REIMBURSEMENT POLICY

Another critical RADx-UP question asked: Can **community health workers (CHWs)** improve testing access in underserved populations? Research from multiple RADx-UP projects showed the answer is yes—especially for individuals with limited English proficiency and those disconnected from formal healthcare systems (Phillips, et al., 2023).

Findings led to specific recommendations:

- Integrate CHWs into the healthcare workforce
- Build funding models for CHWs' training and certification
- Design care systems that value CHWs as trusted messengers

These recommendations aligned with national discussions on Medicaid and Medicare reform and informed payment model proposals to sustainably support CHWs in future public health responses.

GLOSSARY

CHWs Trusted frontline public health workers who connect communities to services

Case Studies

The section emphasizes the necessity of establishing inclusive policies during health crises, as underserved groups often face higher risks. It highlights how public policies influenced health disparities and stresses the importance of working together with community partners. The case studies show how these partnerships made public health policies more effective in improving healthcare access and addressing inequities during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The following case studies demonstrate RADx-UP's application of research to inform health policy and public health practice. Grounded in community input, the examples illustrate how inclusive policymaking can address health inequities and elevate the role of trusted community providers in public health responses.

- 1. RADx-UP Health Equity Policy Framework:** Presents a strategic framework with actionable levers to improve access to testing through community-based models and cross-sector collaboration, designed to reduce structural barriers and support equity.
- 2. RADx-UP Policy Paper: Community Health Workers:** Details policy recommendations for integrating CHWs into the healthcare workforce, based on RADx-UP project evidence showing CHWs' impact on testing access and care coordination in marginalized communities.
- 3. The ABC Science Collaborative: Using Data to Help Kids Return to School Safely:** Explains how the ABC Science Collaborative used real-time data and partnerships with North Carolina schools to show that masking could prevent COVID-19 spread in classrooms, leading to statewide policy changes that supported safe in-person learning.
- 4. Third Annual Equity Evidence Academy Theme: Policies Through a Communication Lens During the COVID-19 Pandemic:** Explores how risk communication influenced public behavior and policy adherence during the COVID-19 pandemic, offering insight into how messaging, trust, and social context shaped health outcomes and compliance.

CASE STUDY 7.1

RADx-UP HEALTH EQUITY POLICY FRAMEWORK

The COVID-19 pandemic revealed major challenges for underserved communities to access testing, driven by structural inequalities. To dismantle these obstacles and prepare for future health emergencies, experts developed the Health Equity Policy Framework. This framework focuses on breaking down barriers to testing by using community-based models and building partnerships across different sectors. It emphasizes direct work with communities to design testing strategies that meet their unique needs and to collect meaningful data that can help track efforts to reduce disparities. By prioritizing collaboration and equity, the framework helps to ensure that public health responses truly serve everyone. This framework, called *Scaling Up Equitable Access to Community-Based COVID-19 Testing: Strategies from the RADx-UP Initiative*, is shown in the figure below.

FIGURE 7.2: FRAMEWORK FOR COMMUNITY-BASED COVID-19 TESTING

CASE STUDY 7.1 | RADx-UP HEALTH EQUITY POLICY FRAMEWORK

Overall, the policy framework emphasized a series of **health equity** strategies for RADx-UP projects, providers, and policymakers to improve access to COVID-19 testing.

- RADx-UP research projects:
 - Generate evidence on the most effective communication strategies to reach different communities and test messaging with communities for key decisions and policies
 - Use disadvantage indices to generate data that address community-level health disparities
 - Partner with community health centers to identify communities experiencing higher risk for COVID-19 exposure and adverse outcomes
- Providers:
 - Expand walk-in/no appointment options
 - Provide vaccination and testing beyond business hours
 - Partner with community-based organizations (CBOs) to organize events that are tailored to the cultural and linguistic needs of specific communities
- Policymakers:
 - Extend health coverage to redress systemic inequities in insurance rates
 - Support the development of equity-focused metrics
 - Establish policies to extend services beyond traditional healthcare settings

These are just a few of the framework's health equity strategies. An exhaustive list is in the full report: *Scaling Up Equitable Access to Community-Based COVID-19 Testing: Strategies from the RADx-UP Initiative* [[Visit Website](#)]

GLOSSARY

Health equity is the state in which everyone has a fair and just opportunity to attain their highest level of health.

CASE STUDY 7.1 | RADx-UP HEALTH EQUITY POLICY FRAMEWORK

Resource Spotlight

Levers & Foundational Components [[Watch Video](#)]

Policy Framework Exercise for Community-Based COVID-19 Testing (See Appendix G.1)

Health Equity Framework Video Series Exploring the Components of the Health Equity Policy Framework:

- Part 1: Access [[Watch Video](#)]
- Part 2: Resource Allocation [[Watch Video](#)]
- Part 3: Data [[Watch Video](#)]
- Part 4: Communication & Messaging [[Watch Video](#)]
- Part 5: Payment [[Watch Video](#)]
- Part 6: Foundational Components [[Watch Video](#)]

CASE STUDY 7.2

RADx-UP POLICY PAPER: COMMUNITY HEALTH WORKERS

Select RADx-UP projects targeted policy-oriented approaches to enhancing COVID-19 testing. The evidence they collected demonstrate how Community Health Workers (CHWs) were incorporated into various clinical practices. The success of these initiatives confirms the need for policies that support CHWs' roles in the healthcare workforce.

In the past, CHWs gained recognition in the literature for their capacity to enhance healthcare delivery through patient engagement, care coordination, and patient-centered functions (Hartzler, et al., 2018). As frontline workers, they have been particularly instrumental when their ethnic background and linguistic capabilities aligned with the patients they served. This alignment was pivotal during the COVID-19 pandemic.

FIGURE 7.3: ROLES OF COMMUNITY HEALTH WORKERS

CASE STUDY 7.2 | RADx-UP POLICY PAPER: COMMUNITY HEALTH WORKERS

While the roles of RADx-UP project CHWs varied during the COVID-19 pandemic, they were all crucial to alleviating the pandemic’s negative impact on distressed communities. CHWs served as community advocates; they effectively conducted education and outreach on COVID-19 risks through culturally tailored approaches; and they were instrumental in coordinating care by helping patients navigate the healthcare system, such as making appointments and getting referrals.

Multiple RADx-UP projects identified specific policy actions for legislators to consider for advancing CHWs’ role in reducing inequities and improving patient outcomes. See figure below.

This effort aligned with existing efforts within the federal government to remedy inequities in payment models and care delivery, particularly for **Medicaid** and **Medicare** beneficiaries, during the pandemic (Whitsel, et al., 2023). Similarly, the RADx-UP project results led to policy recommendations around restructuring payment models to incorporate CHWs into clinical practice. This, in turn, can alleviate deficiencies in healthcare system practices that make it difficult to engage hard-to-reach bilingual populations in COVID-19 risk-prevention efforts.

GLOSSARY

- Medicaid** health insurance covers U.S. adults and children with limited income.
- Medicare** health insurance covers people aged 65+ and younger people with disabilities.

Resource Spotlight

- Opportunities to Enhance Health Equity by Integrating Community Health Workers into Payment and Care Delivery Reforms [[Visit Website](#)]
- Community Brief: Prioritizing Community Health Workers in Health Care Reform is Key to Enhancing Health Equity (See Appendix G.2 for Community Brief in English); [[Download PDF — Spanish Version](#)]

CASE STUDY 7.3

THE ABC SCIENCE COLLABORATIVE: USING DATA TO HELP KIDS RETURN TO SCHOOL SAFELY

What They Did

The ABC Science Collaborative, supported by RADx-UP, worked with schools and scientists to answer an important question: Can students safely go back to school during COVID-19?

They studied over 100 school districts and 14 charter schools in North Carolina. The data showed that schools could stay open safely if students and staff wore masks. Even when classrooms and buses were full, there was very little spread of the virus inside schools.

Because of the collaborative's work, North Carolina made changes to its school safety rules, including:

- Allowing full in-person learning (instead of hybrid or remote)
- Letting students ride buses three per seat as long as they were masked
- Changing quarantine rules so that fewer students missed school when exposed to COVID-19

What They Learned:

- Wearing masks was the most important way to stop COVID-19 from spreading in schools.
- Schools could be open safely without needing large amounts of space between people.
- Sharing up-to-date data helped school leaders make smart choices quickly.

CASE STUDY 7.3 | THE ABC SCIENCE COLLABORATIVE

What Others Can Do:

- Work closely with schools to collect and share data in real time.
- Create simple reports and videos so that parents, teachers, and leaders can understand the science.
- Use strong partnerships between schools and scientists to build trust and improve public health policies.

Resource Spotlight

ABC Science Collaborative: What Science Says About Preventing COVID-19 in North Carolina's K-12 Schools (See Appendix G.3)

CASE STUDY 7.4

THIRD ANNUAL EQUITY EVIDENCE ACADEMY THEME: POLICIES THROUGH A COMMUNICATION LENS DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

The third **RADx-UP Equity Evidence Academy**, held in 2022, focused on how public health messages and policies about COVID-19 testing could be more effectively communicated to advance health equity. This particular gathering emphasized the importance of accurate and accessible messaging.

Presenters found that political affiliation, historical distrust, and economic insecurity affected adherence to COVID-19 policies.

The discussions explored:

- How various groups perceived public health policies such as quarantine measures, mask mandates, and social distancing.
- How these perceptions influenced adherence to safety protocols.
- The role of trust and understanding in ensuring compliance with these measures.

The recommendations and strategies provided at the Equity Evidence Academy included strategies for policymakers, providers, and community-engaged projects. They focused on tailoring risk communication to be effective for all audiences and partnering with trusted messengers to counter misinformation.

Resource Spotlight

The Equity Evidence Academy's data profile examines the theme *Policies Through a Communications Lens*, focusing on communicating COVID-19 risk and the factors that affect whether people follow COVID-19 safety policies. [[Visit Website](#)]

GLOSSARY

RADx-UP Equity Evidence Academy An annual virtual gathering during the RADx-UP grant that focused on the current evidence of COVID-19 testing and related factors in the communities most impacted

Key Takeaways for Future Public Health Emergencies

RADx-UP's policy-focused work during the COVID-19 pandemic—whether ensuring safe in-person schooling or embedding trusted community providers into care delivery—highlights the powerful role that community-informed strategies can play in shaping equitable public health responses. These lessons include but are not limited to:

- Community engagement should inform every step of policy development.
- Community health workers (CHWs) must be funded, supported, and sustained.
- Policies must address misinformation as a public health threat.
- Cultural and linguistic relevance drives policy success.
- Economic security and health equity are deeply connected.

Conclusion

The RADx-UP research offers practical advice for policymakers, community groups, and healthcare providers. It suggests creating healthcare services that respect each community's specific culture and challenges. Policymakers are encouraged to collect and share data to identify areas needing support, rethink systems that overlook vulnerable groups, and make public health messages clear and accessible in various languages and formats. Additionally, payment policies should fairly compensate community leaders and organizations for their contributions and local expertise.

Community engagement methods helped establish partnerships between local organizations, healthcare providers, and researchers. These collaborations provided important insights for government policies on preventing infections, reducing hospitalizations, and lowering death rates during pandemics, especially in communities facing systemic challenges. The RADx-UP program showed how research and real-world practices could shape public policies to decrease viral transmission effectively.

Toolkit

1. FEATURED RADx-UP RESOURCES

Practical resources developed directly by the CDCC or RADx-UP projects. These may include publications, guides, or curated tools specific to implementing a program like the RADx-UP initiative.

- **Scaling Up Equitable Access to Community-Based COVID-19 Testing: Strategies from the RADx-UP Initiative** — This policy paper from Duke-Margolis Center for Health Policy, UNC Center for Health Equity Research, and Duke Clinical Research Institute offers a timely perspective into the policy strategies necessary to close equity gaps in COVID-19 testing based on experiences from RADx-UP projects. [[Visit Website](#)]
 - **Executive Summary:** Health Equity Policy Framework (See Appendix G.4)
 - **Community Brief:** Community-Based COVID-19 Testing: Barriers, Solutions and Next Steps (See Appendix G.5); [[Download Spanish PDF](#)]
 - **Framework Training Videos:** Video series exploring the components of the Health Equity Policy framework.
 - Part 1: Access** [[Watch Video](#)]
 - Part 2: Resource Allocation** [[Watch Video](#)]
 - Part 3: Data** [[Watch Video](#)]
 - Part 4: Communication & Messaging** [[Watch Video](#)]
 - Part 5: Payment** [[Watch Video](#)]
 - Part 6: Foundational Components** [[Watch Video](#)]
- **Opportunities to Enhance Health Equity by Integrating Community Health Workers into Payment and Care Delivery Reforms** — A policy paper from Duke-Margolis Center for Health Policy, UNC Center for Health Equity Research and Duke Clinical Research Institute delivers policy recommendations to enhance and prioritize Community Health Worker (CHW) models into existing health care transformation reforms to address health inequities in the U.S. [[Visit Website](#)]
 - **Community Brief:** Prioritizing Community Health Workers in Health Care Reform is Key to Enhancing Health Equity (See Appendix G.2 for Community Brief in English); [[Download PDF — Spanish Version](#)]
- **ABC Science Collaborative: What Science Says About Preventing COVID-19 in North Carolina's K-12 Schools** — The ABC Science Collaborative, a program supported by RADx-UP, showed that North Carolina schools were highly successful in preventing the transmission of COVID-19 within school buildings and offers science-based learnings for the nation's schools to limit COVID-19 spread. (See Appendix G.3)

2. SUPPLEMENTAL RESOURCES

Resources developed outside the CDCC but shared via the Engagement Resource Center or by project partners. These materials offer supplemental value and represent real-world utility during a PHE response.

- **Redressing Systemic Inequities: Five Lessons for Community-Based COVID-19 Testing from the RADx-UP Initiative** — This *Health Affairs* blog post highlights five lessons learned about community-academic partnerships through RADx-UP's work. RADx-UP projects focus on increasing testing access and uptake for historically marginalized populations by implementing five key strategies: deploying mobile units to expand access; using disadvantage indices to prioritize resource redistribution; embedding community feedback into data collection; collaborating with community leaders to create key messages; and expanding provider payments to support community-based models. [[Visit Website](#)]

3. “DOWNLOAD & DO” — READY-TO-USE TOOLS

This section includes hands-on templates, workflows, sample communications, onboarding documents, planning checklists, data collection tools, or forms for immediate application.

- **Policy Framework Exercise for Community-Based COVID-19 Testing** — DIY (do-it-yourself) exercise to guide for developing policy change strategies (See Appendix G.1)

4. RELEVANT PUBLICATIONS

A list of publications, data sources, or scholarly work that support the evidence base and offer pathways for further reading.

- Batista C, Hotez P, Amor YB, et al. The silent and dangerous inequity around access to COVID-19 testing: A call to action. *EClinicalMedicine*. 2022;43:101230. doi: 10.1016/j.eclinm.2021.101230.
- Hartzler AL, Tuzzio L, Hsu C, Wagner EH. Roles and functions of community health workers in primary care. *Ann Fam Med*. 2018;16(3):240-245. doi: 10.1370/afm.2208.
- Khanijahani A, Iezadi S, Gholipour K, Azami-Aghdash S, Naghibi D. A systematic review of racial/ethnic and socioeconomic disparities in COVID-19. *Int J Equity Health*. 2021;20(1):248. doi: 10.1186/s12939-021-01582-4.
- Ray R, Lantz PM, Williams D. Upstream policy changes to improve population health and health equity: A priority agenda. *Milbank Q*. 2023;101(S1):20-35. doi: 10.1111/1468-0009.12640.
- Whitsel LP, Ajenikoko F, Chase PJ, et al. Public policy for healthy living: How COVID-19 has changed the landscape. *Prog Cardiovasc Dis*. 2023;76:49-56. doi: 10.1016/j.pcad.2023.01.002.
- Burgess RA, Osborne RH, Yongabi KA, Greenhalgh T, Gurdasani D, Kang G, Falade AG, Odone A, Busse R, Martin-Moreno JM, Reicher S, McKee M. The COVID-19 Vaccines Rush: Participatory Community Engagement Matters more than Ever. *Lancet*. 2021 Jan 2;397(10268):8-10. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(20)32642-8. Epub 2020 Dec 10. PMID: 33308484; PMCID: PMC7832461.
- Su Z. Rigorous Policy-Making Amid COVID-19 and Beyond: Literature Review and Critical Insights. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2021 Nov 26;18(23):12447. doi: 10.3390/ijerph182312447. PMID: 34886171; PMCID: PMC8657108.
- van Schalkwyk MCI, McKee M. Research into Policy: Lessons from the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Eur J Public Health*. 2021 Nov 9;31(Supplement_4):iv3-iv8. doi: 10.1093/eurpub/ckab155. PMID: 34751362; PMCID: PMC8576298.

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SECTION FOUR: Evaluating Impact

SECTION FOUR OVERVIEW

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This section reviews the efforts to evaluate the impact of the RADx-UP program, providing insights into its efficiency and offering guidance for future public health initiatives. It comprises two chapters: one that examines the program's outcomes and the methods used to assess its success, and another that focuses on ensuring the sustainability of the community partnerships established during the initiative. Using collaborative and participatory evaluation techniques, this section emphasizes the challenges faced and the achievements made in measuring the program's impact.

Chapter 8: Program Evaluation

Summary:

Chapter 8 explores the comprehensive evaluation plan developed by the RADx-UP Tracking and Evaluation team, which involved partnerships in every phase of the process to ensure a participatory, collaborative, and results-driven approach. It outlines how various evaluation components were designed to measure the program's processes, outcomes, and impacts.

Key Topics Covered:

- Participatory evaluation methods and their importance in community-engaged research (CEnR)
- Development of evaluation objectives and questions in collaboration with program stakeholders
- Case examples on secondary data use and the creation of qualitative evaluation tools
- Mixed-method approaches that include both quantitative and qualitative data collection.
- Network analysis of RADx-UP's publications to assess academic-community collaboration

"This work is at the core of the historic response to COVID-19 and continues to change lives and promote health for all."

**GAURAV DAVE, MD,
DRPH, MPH**
Co-Principal Investigator,
RADx-UP Coordination and
Data Collection Center

Chapter 9: Positioned for Sustainability

Summary:

Chapter 9 emphasizes the importance of sustaining public health initiatives and partnerships beyond their funding cycles. It focuses on the asset-based analysis, such as identifying and leveraging the existing skills, relationships, and local organizations of community partnerships formed through RADx-UP, illustrating how these relationships can contribute to long-term public health resilience and preparedness.

Key Topics Covered:

- Asset-based analysis for sustainability in CEnR
- Types of partnerships: grassroots, crisis management, and hybrid models
- The role of community feedback in creating a sustainability roadmap
- Case examples on sustaining partnerships through community collaboration grants and pilot programs
- Insights into maintaining public health impacts, even after initial funding ends

Lessons Learned in this Section

The RADx-UP program emphasizes the importance of engaging communities in evaluating public health initiatives. By including stakeholders throughout the process, evaluations become more useful and fairer for everyone involved. This approach not only improves the quality of data but also builds trust and openness. Lessons from the program highlight the need to adapt to challenges such as funding delays and data collection difficulties, particularly during health crises. Partnerships made through RADx-UP have also proven essential for continuing public health efforts. Using community resources and keeping strong connections, these partnerships help maintain engagement and improve health long after the program ends.

How do you know your program made a difference?

Chapter 8 explores how the RADx-UP program applied a participatory, collaborative, and culturally responsive approach to assess program efficiency during the COVID-19 pandemic. This method of evaluation emphasized continuous engagement, real-time learning, and equitable participation of academic and community partners.

Key Topics Covered

- Aligning evaluation questions with program objectives and community needs
- Using secondary data, network analysis, and bibliometrics to measure impact
- Co-creating and adapting evaluation tools with stakeholders
- Integrating evaluation into day-to-day program operations

Lessons Learned

- Engaging partners throughout the evaluation process improves accuracy and relevance.
- Embedding evaluation into ongoing program operations enables real-time learning and responsiveness.
- Evaluation tools must be adapted to fit the cultural and contextual needs of diverse communities.
- Continuous engagement, not one-time input, is essential to inclusive and equitable evaluation.
- Transparent communication and flexible dissemination formats make sharing evaluation findings more effective for different audiences.

Case Examples

- **Bibliometric and network analysis:** Tracked scholarly and non-scholarly products to assess dissemination and collaboration across the consortium
- **Evaluation tool development:** Engaged partners in adapting validated surveys and tools to ensure they were relevant and accessible
- **Use of Most Significant Change (MSC) and health equity impact assessments:** Captured qualitative shifts in equity-focused outcomes across diverse RADx-UP sites

In Your Toolkit

Templates for the evaluation plans, planning frameworks, and real-world examples (like bibliometric analysis and adapted survey tools) that RADx-UP used to design and carry out program evaluations in community-engaged settings

CHAPTER EIGHT: PROGRAM EVALUATION

PHOTO COURTESY RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

The Importance of Participatory, Collaborative, and Utilization-Focused Program Evaluation

Participatory evaluation involves stakeholders in the evaluation process (Jackson & Kassam, 1998). Frameworks such as the Culturally Responsive and Equitable Evaluation help ensure that an evaluation is nimble, adaptive to feedback from staff and community partners, and collects accurate and meaningful data to inform program direction (Adedoyin et al., 2023). Participatory and responsive approaches build transparency and trust because the evaluation involves continuous input from those directly impacted. Program partners should remain involved through all stages of the evaluation process—from the initial design to the **dissemination** of results. This involvement helps improve the evaluation process and ensures that the results are used effectively in making program decisions (See **Figure 8.1**).

Public health emergencies like the COVID-19 pandemic have increased the need for rapid and coordinated interventions that reduce negative impacts. These evaluations allow programs to adjust responsively to changing needs and improve performance. The RADx-UP Tracking and Evaluation team developed a comprehensive, community-engaged, collaborative, participatory, and results-driven evaluation to assess the processes, outcomes, and impacts of the RADx-UP program. Their approach focused on collaboration, participation, and practical results to measure the program's processes, outcomes, and impacts.

GLOSSARY

Participatory evaluation

involves stakeholders in defining what will be evaluated, and how data will be collected and results communicated.

Dissemination means spreading or distributing information to a large number of people.

The RADx-UP Tracking and Evaluation team included experts from Abacus Evaluation at the University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill. They evaluated the program's short- and long-term effects. The three goals of the evaluation were to (1) measure CDCC's efficiency in supporting over 130 RADx-UP projects, (2) assess the overall impact of these projects, and (3) facilitate the strategic direction of the RADx-UP program.

The Tracking and Evaluation team created a detailed evaluation plan for RADx-UP, which outlined the team's goals, questions, and methods; these included quantitative and qualitative approaches, such as using numbers, stories, or interviews to gather data. The plan was designed to assess how well the CDCC's work improved RADx-UP's overall success and how effectively it reached out to the community. It also assessed the successes of RADx-UP projects like research and pilot programs. The process used to develop the plan can serve as a guide for other researchers or evaluators of complex health initiatives and is detailed in this chapter's case studies.

FIGURE 8.2: PYRAMID OF PARTICIPATORY ENGAGEMENT LEVEL

Adapted from IAP2 (2018).

In addition, the Tracking and Evaluation team identified and analyzed the engagement levels of key RADx-UP partners to understand how meaningful their participation was based on their roles, responsibilities, interests, and influence (See **Figure 8.2**).

Background

Aligning Specific Aims with Evaluation Objectives and Questions

During the planning stage of the evaluation process, the Tracking and Evaluation team met with program partners. These included:

- Investigators
- Program leads
- Staff from various RADx-UP CDCC cores (Testing, Community Engagement, Administration, and Data)
- Academic and community members involved in RADx-UP projects

These meetings helped the team:

- Agree on realistic program goals and objectives, as well as activities to achieve them.
- Set up evaluation objectives, questions, and tools that matched the program's aims.
- Check that the measures were relevant and made sense for the program.
- Ensure agreement on how the evaluation findings would be used.

Evaluation Questions

The Tracking and Evaluation team and program partners worked together to understand how well RADx-UP supported a community-focused and inclusive engagement program. Their questions focused on collecting and studying program data to measure progress towards its goals. (See **Figure 8.3**)

PHOTO COURTESY RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

FIGURE 8.3: CDCC EVALUATION QUESTIONS

RADx-UP Program: Successes, Challenges, Outcomes, Impacts, and Sustainability

What was the RADx-UP **program reach**?
(underserved populations, community outreach, and testing)

What were some of the RADx-UP programs' **benefits** to and **impacts** on communities?

How did the RADx-UP program **engage** and **collaborate** with communities?

What were some of the **successes** achieved and challenges faced by the RADx-UP program?

How **satisfied** were RADx-UP program projects with CDCC services and which did projects use?

To what extent will RADx-UP program activities and impacts be **sustained**?

RADx-UP Scholarship Impacts: Contribution, Collaboration, and Dissemination

What **types of scholarly and non-scholarly products** did the RADx-UP program projects develop?

How did the RADx-UP publications **advance** COVID-19 testing, vaccination, and community-engaged research?

What did the RADx-UP program **scholarly collaboration for research** dissemination look like?

What were some of the **bibliometric impacts** from RADx-UP publications?

Evaluation Components

The RADx-UP evaluation plan and its tools were created specifically for this program (See **Figure 8.4**), but other public health groups can use similar methods. By working with their partners to design evaluations, these groups can better understand how their activities affect communities.

PHOTO COURTESY RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

Case Studies

The case studies in this chapter highlight innovative evaluation methods used to assess the RADx-UP program's effectiveness. Emphasizing participatory and community-engaged evaluation, these examples provide a roadmap for how large-scale initiatives can measure impact, foster collaboration, and build equity into assessment practices.

- 1. Using Secondary Data to Answer Questions about Program Impact:**
Demonstrates how RADx-UP used publications tracking and bibliometrics to evaluate dissemination and the real-world impact of research findings.
- 2. Visualizing the Inclusion of Community Voices in Disseminating Research Findings:** Describes the approach used to show the inclusion of partners from different groups in sharing research findings in RADx-UP publications.
- 3. Developing, Adapting, and Administering Evaluation Tools:**
Describes a stakeholder-driven process for creating adaptable evaluation instruments, including surveys and qualitative methods, tailored to the diverse contexts of RADx-UP projects.

CASE STUDY 8.1

USING SECONDARY DATA TO ANSWER QUESTIONS ABOUT PROGRAM IMPACT

Secondary data is useful for studying how big programs affect people and communities. This kind of data is often already collected and organized, making it easier to analyze. For the RADx-UP program, secondary data like reports and publications helped the CDCC understand how academic and community partners collaborated to share lessons learned and findings relevant to communities and priority populations.

The Tracking and Evaluation team used publicly available online databases (PubMed and Scopus) to track RADx-UP products, including publications in peer-reviewed journals and conference presentations, using RADx-UP grant numbers. As a verification step, the team created a form for projects to confirm their products and report their other kinds of materials, like social media posts or newsletters.

The team then used different methods to evaluate how products created by and shared from RADx-UP reached people and communities and how impactful they were. **Altmetrics** showed how findings were shared with the public, such as in policy documents, news articles, and on social media. The team used **Bibliometrics**, a quantitative methodology, to evaluate how impactful the RADx-UP research publications were, such as how often they were cited by others and which high-impact journals published the articles, helping the team see patterns over time.

GLOSSARY

Secondary data Information that has been collected by someone else, rather than being gathered directly for a specific research purpose

Altmetrics A statistical approach to monitoring the reach and impact of scholarship and research through indicators such as online interactions

Bibliometrics Statistical analyses of publications

CASE STUDY 8.2

VISUALIZING THE INCLUSION OF COMMUNITY VOICES IN THE DISSEMINATION OF RESEARCH FINDINGS

To assess the inclusion of partners' and community members' voices in the dissemination of research findings, the Tracking and Evaluation team performed a **social network analysis**. Using the same publications data as described in [Case Study 8.1](#), the team categorized each co-author's primary group affiliation on every article and focused their analysis on the structure and quality of ties between authors of RADx-UP publications.

GLOSSARY

Social network analysis

A graphic map to show how key players are linked together

The network visualization showed how authors from different groups like schools, health departments, and community-based organizations worked together with academic groups to disseminate research findings. Expanding upon findings from the network analysis, the team further analyzed the content of the articles to assess which populations the articles were about.

They also looked at the outreach strategies projects used to reach their communities. The team again categorized publications to capture that information within the publication, summarized information within the publications, and created a narrative summary. The content analysis showed publications were about different communities that RADx-UP projects were working with, different strategies projects used to conduct outreach and engage communities to increase testing access, and findings from projects' work. This collaboration among partners from academic groups and those from the community highlighted the importance of including community voices to meaningfully share research findings and improve public health programs.

CASE STUDY 8.2 | VISUALIZING THE INCLUSION OF COMMUNITY VOICES

FIGURE 8.5: CO-AUTHOR NETWORK VISUALIZATION

196 RADx-UP publications (dark blue circles) and 844 co-authors (multicolor circles) connected (by lines) to their publications. Co-authors in RADx-UP were from community, professional, academic, and other groups, showing the importance of including community voices in the dissemination of research findings.

CASE STUDY 8.3

DEVELOPING, ADAPTING, AND ADMINISTERING EVALUATION TOOLS FOR A COMPLEX HEALTH INITIATIVE

The Tracking and Evaluation team and collaborators published the process used to develop a qualitative evaluation plan for RADx-UP and the lessons learned (Maras et al., 2024). The plan development process had the following steps:

- Planning
- Collaborations and approvals
- Sampling and interview guide development
- Recruitment
- Data collection and analysis
- Communication and dissemination

While the paper focused on qualitative evaluation approaches, the steps also show how evaluation tools were developed and administered for RADx-UP overall. This process serves as a guide for other researchers or evaluators of complex health initiatives.

Resource Spotlight

JOURNAL PUBLICATION

- *How to Develop a Qualitative Evaluation Plan for a Complex National Intervention: Key Steps and Reflections from the RADx-UP Program*

[\[Visit Website\]](#)

CASE STUDY 8.3 | DEVELOPING, ADAPTING, AND ADMINISTERING EVALUATION TOOLS**Survey Development**

Working with partners was key to creating other evaluation tools like surveys that included both numbers-based and open-ended questions. The process involved:

- Setting clear goals
- Making the survey language easy to understand
- Picking the right participants
- Timing the surveys properly
- Deciding how to share the results

For example, when developing surveys to get feedback from the CDCC, the team organized webinars and interviews to solicit feedback about the tools from consortium members. Regular meetings and online platforms helped everyone stay connected to coordinate the surveys, making sure the feedback process was convenient for participants.

To leverage previous successful efforts, the team adapted existing tools with the help of their partners. For instance, they used tested scales from the [Engage for Equity \(E2\)](#) project and the E2 Community Engagement Survey. They included these scales on the RADx-UP Project Implementation Survey to assess projects' academic-community partnerships, use of community engagement principles, contribution to health outcomes, and sustainability.

The team also adopted existing tools to evaluate health impacts, including a health impact assessment and the **Most Significant Change (MSC)** evaluation method. They simplified an existing health assessment tool to make it easier for RADx-UP projects to use (Maras et al., 2024). The updated MSC approach helped teams measure changes in underserved communities in these key areas:

- Access to COVID-19 testing and vaccination
- COVID-19 education
- Outreach efforts
- Overall social determinants of health improvements

Implementors and evaluators can use these approaches to assess community-engaged program impacts, depending on the context (Taheri et al., 2024).

GLOSSARY

MSC is an approach that generates and analyzes personal accounts of change, deciding what is most important, and why.

Key Takeaways for Future Public Health Emergencies

The RADx-UP program showcased major progress in using CEnR to handle public health emergencies. It reflected advances in evaluation methods, such as the Culturally Responsive and Equitable Evaluation approach, which includes impacted community members and local participants in decision-making and evaluation processes (Frierson et al., 2002).

Tips for Effective Evaluation During Public Health Emergencies

1. Plan for flexibility and realistic timelines

Evaluations during emergencies require adaptable plans. Be prepared for changes like delays, policy changes, shifting priorities, or limited availability of stakeholders. Use tools like timelines and project trackers to stay organized and adjust plans as needed.

2. Make findings easy to understand and use

Sharing findings effectively is key to driving action. For example, tools like SWOT (**strengths-weaknesses-opportunities-threats**) analyses can tailor findings for different groups. Community partners often benefit from short summaries, while funders and researchers may need detailed reports. Open communication with stakeholders ensures the insights are relevant and actionable. It's important to ask stakeholders what they need.

3. Build long-term community partnerships

True participatory evaluation involves more than one-time input. It's an ongoing process of collaboration. Create systems to keep community voices involved throughout all phases of evaluation, from planning to sharing results. This builds relevance, trust, and shared ownership of outcomes.

4. Embed evaluation in routine activities

Don't wait until the project ends to evaluate it. Including evaluation in everyday operations allows for constant feedback, quick learning, and improvements while the project is still ongoing. This is especially important during rapidly changing emergencies.

5. Engage partners in using evaluation for strategic planning

The RADx-UP program highlighted the benefits of engaging community members directly. Involving their perspectives makes evaluations more accurate, ensures they reflect real experiences, and promotes fair outcomes for everyone.

GLOSSARY

Strengths-Weaknesses-Opportunities-Threats (SWOT)

is a strategic planning tool used to identify potential areas for improvement.

Conclusion

Public health emergencies like the COVID-19 pandemic show the importance of intentional and adaptable evaluations. These evaluations help stakeholders such as community members, program staff, and decision-makers understand what's working and where improvements are needed. By involving people directly affected by the programs, evaluations become more accurate and useful.

Participatory evaluation is a powerful approach because it invites everyone affected by a program to contribute their ideas and feedback. This ongoing input makes evaluations more transparent and ensures they reflect real-world needs. This type of collaboration improves how programs gather data and share results, making it easier to take action based on findings.

The RADx-UP program is a good example of participatory evaluation. Its evaluation team worked closely with stakeholders to create a clear plan for measuring the program's success, including its reach, effectiveness, and impact on communities. By listening to the people involved at every step—from designing the evaluation to sharing results—the program ensured the findings were practical and meaningful. This approach demonstrates how public health programs can learn and improve, using evaluations to guide better decisions and outcomes.

PHOTO COURTESY RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

Toolkit

1. FEATURED RADx-UP RESOURCES

Practical resources developed directly by the CDCC or RADx-UP projects. These may include publications, guides, or curated tools specific to implementing a program like the RADx-UP initiative.

- **RADx-UP 2024 Tracking and Evaluation Global Report**

This report describes the participatory and utilization-focused approaches and mixed methods used to evaluate RADx-UP with attention to assessing community-engagement, implementation, outcomes, and impacts. (See Appendix H.1)

- **RADx-UP Summative Publications Content Analysis Report**

This content analysis report outlines key outcomes, impacts, and lessons learned from intervention implementation approaches in 231 RADx-UP peer-reviewed publications. Independent reviewers abstracted study characteristics, translational science benefits, key emergent themes, and lessons learned. These abstracts were then synthesized and categorized thematically. (See Appendix H.2)

2. SUPPLEMENTAL RESOURCES

Resources developed outside the CDCC but shared via the Engagement Resource Center or by project partners. These materials offer supplemental value and represent real-world utility during a PHE response.

- **Better Evaluation:** an online library resource containing curated resources to support programs and evaluators create evaluation plans and methods, including evaluation measurement tools. <https://www.betterevaluation.org/tools-resources>
- **National Academy of Medicine's Assessment Instruments for Measuring Community Engagement:** Twenty-eight instruments were identified to support assessing community engagement. In this context, instruments are standard questions, or question sets, designed to assess community engagement in a consistent way. These instruments can be used to measure various domains and indicators in the Conceptual Model.
- **National Academy of Medicine's Community Engagement in Research:** provides a framework and resources to support the evaluation of outcomes and impacts community-engaged research and program. <https://nam.edu/community-engagement-in-research-index/>
- **National Academy of Medicine's Assessing Meaningful Community Engagement metrics:** <https://nam.edu/product/engage-for-equity-key-informant-survey/>
- **Culturally Responsive and Equitable Evaluation:** <https://aea365.org/blog/expanding-the-bench-week-culturally-responsive-and-equitable-evaluation-what-is-it-and-why-is-it-important-by-karla-mendez-alina-taniuchi/>

3. “DOWNLOAD & DO” — READY-TO-USE TOOLS

This section includes hands-on templates, workflows, sample communications, onboarding documents, planning checklists, data collection tools, or forms for immediate application.

- The Translational Science Benefits Model is a framework with an impact toolkit that can help public health research and programs demonstrate the impact of their work in the real world. <https://translationalsciencebenefits.wustl.edu/>

4. RELEVANT PUBLICATIONS

A list of publications, data sources, or scholarly work that support the evidence base and offer pathways for further reading.

- Adedoyin AC, Amutah-Onukagha NN., Jones CD, eds. Culturally Responsive and Equitable Evaluation: Voices and Visions of Emerging Scholars. Cognella; 2023.
- Jackson ET, Kassam Y. Knowledge Shared: Participatory Evaluation in Development Cooperation. Kumarian Press, 1998.
- Fetterman DM, Rodríguez-Campos L, Zukoski AP. Collaborative, Participatory, and Empowerment Evaluation: Stakeholder Involvement Approaches. Guilford; 2017.
- Frierson H, Hood S, Hughes G. A guide to conducting culturally responsive evaluation. In: Frechtling J, ed. The 2002 User-Friendly Handbook for Project Evaluation. National Science Foundation; 2002:63-73.
- International Association for Public Participation (IAP2). IAP2 Spectrum of Public Participation. 2018. <https://iap2.org.au>
- Luke DA, Sarli CC, Suiter AM, et al. The translational science benefits model: A New framework for assessing the health and societal benefits of clinical and translational sciences. Clin Transl Sci. 2018;11(1):77-84. doi:10.1111/cts.12495
- Maras S, Yusuf B, Roberts R, et al. Lessons Learned: Adapting a Health Impact Assessment Tool Using Cognitive Interviews. 2024. https://cdr.lib.unc.edu/concern/scholarly_works/m039kk492?locale=en
- Maras SA, McKelvy J, Milligan K, et al. How to develop a qualitative evaluation plan for a complex national intervention: Key steps and reflections from the RADx-UP program. Qual Rep. 2024;29(3):705-721. doi:10.46743/2160-3715/2024.6541
- Maras SA, Osinuga A, Gallo IV, et al. Qualitative evaluation of RADx-UP projects addressing COVID-19 testing disparities among underserved populations. Am J Public Health. 2024;114(S5):S410-S415.
- Patton MQ, Campbell-Patton CE. Utilization-Focused Evaluation. 5th ed. SAGE Publications; 2022.
- Pope J, Jolly P; Department of Planning and Community Development. Evaluation step-by-step guide. 2008. http://www.dhs.vic.gov.au/_data/assets/pdf_file/0011/769943/Evaluation-Step-by-Step-Guide.pdf
- Taheri C, Maras S, Roberts R, et al. Most Significant Change: A Technique to Evaluate Successes in RADx-UP C2G Pilot Projects. 2024. <https://doi.org/10.17615/3jgj-g666>

How do you make sure good work continues after funding ends?

Chapter 9 focuses on sustainability, specifically how RADx-UP worked to ensure that partnerships, trust, and health equity efforts would endure beyond the immediate COVID-19 response. This chapter examines what it takes to embed community engagement into research infrastructures for the long term.

Key Topics Covered

- Defining sustainability in community-academic partnerships
- Strategies for sustaining trust, collaboration, and shared goals
- Building mechanisms for continued funding, leadership, and infrastructure
- Institutionalizing community engagement practices within research organizations
- Evaluating partnership outcomes and long-term impacts

Lessons Learned

- Sustainability must be planned from the start—not as an afterthought
- Lasting partnerships require ongoing communication, shared leadership, and equitable resource distribution
- Embedding community engagement in institutional policies and practices strengthens commitment
- Continuous learning and adaptation are key to keeping partnerships responsive and effective

In Your Toolkit

Explore partnership sustainability planning guides, evaluation tools, templates for sustaining collaboration, and case studies that illustrate successful models for long-term community engagement.

OVERVIEW

Case Examples

- **Faith-Based COVID-19 Outreach:** Shows how churches used trust and tradition to deliver COVID-19 testing and education
- **Sustainable Infrastructure in Puerto Rico:** Highlights how PR-CARE built lasting community partnerships and secured new funding for future equity-focused work
- **Flexible Grantmaking Models:** Describes how small grants like C2G and RP2 supported local leadership and ongoing public health efforts after RADx-UP funding ended

CHAPTER NINE: POSITIONED FOR SUSTAINABILITY

PHOTO COURTESY RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

Background

Keeping public health funding in communities is important for research that includes and supports the people who live there. Investments within communities are crucial to community-engaged research (CEnR).

The fundamental principles of sustainability in CEnR emphasize the importance of “building capacity and assisting the community in utilizing their data to sustain their efforts once the intervention has concluded” (Israel et al., 1998). Long-term partnerships are key to tackling public health emergencies and delivering impactful results.

Partnerships formed during the RADx-UP study are among its most valuable achievements. These relationships brought together community members, scientists, academics, government agencies, and local health departments to create and adapt new ideas for public health services. Together, they worked to meet the unique needs of different communities, improving access to healthcare for groups that often face challenges in getting services.

RADx-UP partnerships strengthened existing connections and built new ones. As highlighted previously in chapter 5 (Best Practices for Conducting Community-Engaged Research), these partnerships included diverse groups such as churches, community organizations, health departments, and local governments. Each partnership brought its own unique perspective, reflecting the communities it served. The case examples, A Faithful Response to COVID-19 and Puerto Rico Community Action Research and Engagement (PR-CARE), show how different partners approached partnerships.

During the COVID-19 health emergency, programs like Say Yes! COVID Test and You & Me COVID-Free worked with community networks to quickly provide tests and information. Trusted local messengers were key in delivering over 2 million tests to homes in need. These programs demonstrate how RADx-UP partnerships worked and the unique challenges they faced. For these campaigns, RADx-UP CDCC partners identified three partnership models that helped deliver services effectively:

- 1) Grassroots:** The lead partner is a community-based organization that uses a team-based approach to carry out programs in the community.
- 2) Crisis management:** The lead community partner is a governmental organization with full-time personnel who manage or resolve a major crisis like a health department or military unit.
- 3) Hybrid Model:** The lead community partner is an agency, like the United Way, with the capacity to deliver much of the intervention through its organization and resources.

Partnerships that already have strong connections, teamwork, and a history within a community are more likely to succeed and can provide helpful examples for newer partnerships. This chapter's case study from the PR-CARE project provides an excellent example of how established partnerships served to guide successful, sustainable public health work.

Sustaining Community Partnerships After Funding Ends

When funding for public health projects ends, it can be hard for communities to keep their programs going. This can stop progress and weaken the partnerships built during the project. To make a lasting impact, funders and researchers need to support partnerships that can continue beyond the grant.

So how do communities keep moving forward when the money runs out? One way is to plan for the future from the beginning. Funders should encourage grantees to think about long-term goals and support community groups in learning how to plan ahead. The PR-CARE case study shows how research teams helped community organizations take the lead and keep programs running after funding ended.

Each partnership faces its own challenges, especially during times like the COVID-19 pandemic. Many groups also dealt with “**Pandemic Fatigue**,” where people became tired of hearing about and dealing with COVID-19. Even with these difficulties, RADx-UP partnerships stayed strong and provided trusted support. These community-based organizations became important messengers and service providers. Their work during the pandemic showed they can play a key role in future health efforts.

To make this possible, stable funding must continue. Local organizations already have strong ties in their communities and are often the first to respond during public health emergencies. Supporting them is key to keeping public health work going long after the grant ends.

GLOSSARY

Pandemic Fatigue Characterized by a progressive decline in adherence to prevention guidelines and is thought to be associated with pandemic-related emotional burnout

USING COMMUNITY FEEDBACK TO BUILD ON STRENGTHS: THE RADx-UP PLAN FOR LONG-TERM SUCCESS

The RADx-UP CDCC engaged RADx-UP projects, community partners, and other stakeholders in a series of **visioning and strategic thinking sessions** to help set a roadmap for the future. They recognized the opportunity within the project to inform preparedness for the next public health threat as well as the enormous future potential for a research-ready infrastructure and community partnerships in the RADx-UP consortium. Through visioning sessions with over 100 RADx-UP partners, they created a roadmap to sustainability.

FIGURE 9.1: STRATEGIC ROADMAP PROCESS

Resource Spotlight

- A Strategic Roadmap: Advancing Health Equity through Community-engaged Research (See Appendix I.1)
- Strategic Roadmap Process (See Appendix I.2)

Assets Built from RADx-UP Projects

RADx-UP significantly advanced community-engagement in public health emergency responses and research by delivering results and data that exceeded National Institutes of Health (NIH) expectations. The program represents a substantial investment in **CEnR** and provided an opportunity to quickly and effectively form new partnerships for pandemic preparedness. **Figure 9.2** highlights the areas of impact as indicated through Project Implementation Survey responses.

- **Community capacity building for research:** Many research projects plan to sustain community engagement strategies and activities after grant funding ends, indicating a commitment to ongoing support for communities.
- **Community and public health benefits:** Research projects contributed to public health infrastructure by providing testing in underserved communities, by addressing and overcoming barriers, which was particularly valuable during times of strained public health resources.
- **Economic and policy benefits:** Research projects successfully reduced the cost of testing through various means, including a decrease in the monetary costs of tests and acceleration of test processes. Over half (56%) of the projects provided economic benefits, primarily through minimizing test costs (n=38/83; 46%), reducing time to complete tests (n=33/83; 40%), and decreasing time to receive test results (n=28/83; 34%). Some projects (n=23/82; 28%) engaged in policy activities, such as presenting data to government agencies, contributing to policy briefs, and participating in advisory committees, demonstrating a broader impact beyond testing.
- **Community partnerships:** RADx-UP is an important development in NIH's interest in supporting community partnerships for research. Subsequent programs such as the NIH Common Fund's "Community Partnerships to Advance Science for Society" (ComPASS) directly fund community partners. Community engagement requirements in federal research continue to advance through other programs, such as the "Multi-sectoral preventive interventions that address social determinants of health in populations that experience health disparities." This is a program similar to RADx-UP in that it comprises multiple research sites and a coordinating center, but with a mission address health disparities through community engagement. These research configurations recognize community partnerships as the key mechanism to deliver research results and replicate the RADx-UP

GLOSSARY

Community-engaged research (CEnR) is related to Community-based Participatory Research (CBPR), and Community-engaged Research (CER).

Over half (n=52/80; 65%) of RADx-UP research projects on the Project Implementation survey indicated they collaborated with community-based organizations, forming partnerships to overcome implementation barriers, address recruitment challenges, and build trust within target communities.

model of CEnR sites with central coordinating centers. These changes in NIH funding priorities benefit sustainability for CEnR partnerships.

- **Scientific evidence for pandemic preparedness:** Survey results suggest that many research project activities (n=59/82; 72%) are agile and replicable, especially COVID-19 testing (n=43/47, 91%), contributing to improved pandemic preparedness in underserved communities.

Many research project activities are agile and replicable, contributing to improved pandemic preparedness in underserved communities.

Case Studies

The case studies in this chapter demonstrate how RADx-UP projects fostered sustainability through asset-based, community-driven approaches. These examples highlight how partnerships formed during the pandemic evolved into long-term collaborations that continue to support public health infrastructure, preparedness, and equity in underserved communities.

- 1. Partnership Highlight:** A Faithful Response to COVID-19: Showcases how faith-based organizations became trusted hubs for COVID-19 education and testing, leveraging spiritual leadership and community trust to sustain health outreach efforts beyond the immediate crisis.
- 2. Learning from Established Partners:** RADx-UP Puerto Rico Community Action Research and Engagement (PR-CARE) Details a project that built local capacity through community collaboration and responsive infrastructure, illustrating how pilot funding was used to address longstanding disparities and build sustainable testing and engagement systems.
- 3. Sustaining Community Networks: Community Collaboration Grants (C2G) and Rapid Research Pilot Program (RP2):** Highlights the Communities to Gather (C2G) initiative, which provided flexible funding for projects that strengthened community-academic partnerships, prioritized local leadership, and fostered durable systems for future health emergencies.

CASE STUDY 9.1

PARTNERSHIP HIGHLIGHT: A FAITHFUL RESPONSE TO COVID-19

Faith leaders and scholars from the University of Missouri-Kansas School of Medicine in the Greater Kansas City area continued a partnership that began during the HIV/AIDS epidemic, to tailor COVID-19 interventions for the African American community model, research teams and community partners conducted in-person outreach and recruitment. During the pandemic, the “COVID-19 Testing and Linkage to Care with African American Church and Health Agency Partners: A Faithful Response to COVID-19” research teams and churches provided on-site testing for members following Sunday services. Faith leaders also recommended having contact tracers on-site during testing events to address distrust among community members. These interventions made COVID-19 testing more accessible by bringing the services to a familiar and trustworthy place.

“That’s one of the unique things about our COVID-19 testing project. Not only is our intervention culturally and religiously tailored, but even for the testing services that are provided they are happening at nontraditional times, such as testing services offered immediately after the church services,” said Jannette Berkley-Patton, the principal investigator and a professor at the University of Missouri-Kansas School of Medicine.

The churches delivered the intervention. “Our role was managing the faith partners that are involved in the process and the program,” said Reverend Eric Williams, Pastor of the Calvary Temple Baptist Church and Executive Director of the Calvary Community Outreach Network. “It is being able to recruit, train, mobilize, sensitize people to the need; arming faith-based institutions with the information that they need to preach from their pulpits.”

PROJECT SPOTLIGHT: A FAITHFUL RESPONSE TO COVID-19 [\[WATCH VIDEO\]](#)

CASE STUDY 9.2

LEARNING FROM ESTABLISHED PARTNERS: RADx-UP PUERTO RICO COMMUNITY ACTION RESEARCH AND ENGAGEMENT (PR-CARE)

This example highlights how a RADx-UP project successfully used resources and sustained strong community-based research partnerships. The Puerto Rico Community Action Research and Engagement (PR-CARE) project worked to reduce COVID-19 disparities in rural and underserved areas. Using support from RADx-UP, the project gained funding from the NIH Common Fund Community Partnerships to Advance Science for Society (ComPASS) program, which started in 2023. This funding focused on tackling health disparities by addressing deeper structural issues in communities, with leadership from community organizations rather than universities.

PR-CARE evolved into a new program called Puerto Rico Collaborative Advancement of Research, Innovation, Best Practices, and Equity for Children, Youth, and Families (PR-CARIBE). This program builds on decades of teamwork between agencies and strong community connections to deal with health challenges. It shows how long-term partnerships can lead to bigger and more impactful health programs. PR-CARIBE has set four main goals:

- Reduce child poverty
- Create more chances for social and economic growth
- Support equity, well-being, and healthy development
- Add more resources to local communities

CASE STUDY 9.2 | LEARNING FROM ESTABLISHED PARTNERS: PR-CARE

The main group driving this project was the ComPASS PR Health Equity Research Assembly, which included 47 members working together. This Assembly was a key space where partnerships and collaboration occurred, using two important ideas:

- The Stakeholder Engagement Wheel was a model that showed how community engagement happens in a cycle, making it easier to involve everyone, rather than following strict steps (Quinsee & Parker, 2020).
- The Assembly used a collective impact model to help make decisions based on data. This approach ensured that decisions were inclusive and thoughtful, benefiting all involved.

PR-CARE was able to partner with these existing organizations and use proven community engagement models to coordinate RADx-UP funding and activities early on to ensure solutions that can last over time.

CASE STUDY 9.3

SUSTAINING COMMUNITY NETWORKS: COMMUNITY COLLABORATION GRANTS (C2G) AND RAPID RESEARCH PILOT PROGRAM (RP2)

C2G Projects:

Charged with expanding the geographic and population-specific reach of the RADx-UP program, the RADx-UP CDCC Community Collaboration Grant (C2G) program supported small, targeted community partners in advancing capacity, training, support, and community experience with COVID-19 testing initiatives among communities adversely affected by the pandemic. The C2G program projects grants provided up to \$50,000 to community groups to improve COVID-19 testing and slow the spread of the virus. The goal of this direct-cost grant program was to increase testing capabilities and train organizations to handle COVID-19 testing in underserved communities.

Examples of the 70 C2G projects include:

- **COVID-19 Testing Outreach and Education for New York Immigrant and Working-Class Communities:** Make the Road New York served the migrant and immigrant communities in Queens, New York. The project team served on New York City's Test and Trace Community Advisory Board and advocated for accessible healthcare and reliable information in the languages of local immigrant communities. The project promoted COVID-19 testing and education through the creation of culturally tailored materials distributed by in-person outreach through lay community health workers (promotoras), workshops, and social media.

CASE STUDY 9.3 | SUSTAINING COMMUNITY NETWORKS: C2G AND RP2

• **Faith-based Education and Outreach in Bridgeport, CT:**

The National Hispanic Christian Leadership Conference—Connecticut Chapter is a faith-based network of 104 Hispanic congregations Hispanic/Latino communities throughout Connecticut. The COVID-19 Community Pastoral Response center staff partnered with Southwest Community Health Center to host virtual and in-person town hall meetings to educate and encourage COVID-19 testing and vaccination as well as train clergy members to disseminate facts from the pulpit.

- **Rapid Response COVID-19 Testing:** A Community of Caring Christians served the elderly, disabled, and indigent in Shubuta, Mississippi. Through call centers and field staff, the program delivered and administered at-home COVID-19 tests to those who requested a test but had little or no access to get one. After ensuring the completed test was delivered to the lab, the program staff informed the patient of the results, along with next steps, and vaccination information.

Leaders of C2G projects report that many activities from the program are still ongoing, even if funding has ended. While more money is often needed to continue these efforts, many organizations have managed to keep COVID-19 testing and education programs running in their communities. The C2G projects have helped kickstart long-term health initiatives, providing tools, knowledge, and partnerships that support healthier communities.

“We had no intention of stopping providing our neighbors with access to public health-related content. We also applied for a second round of funding and were awarded it. In the meanwhile when we were getting the paperwork set up and all of that, we were still working with our local health department and through our relationships with our local elected officials at the state level, securing testing and disseminating that amongst our neighbors, particularly like with the back to school and all that stuff.”

C2G PROJECT_32

“This pilot study has already been used as preliminary data to demonstrate engagement and funding feasibility of data collection in the South Asian community for an R01 that was submitted in February 2023.”

RP2 PROJECT_141

RP2 Projects:

The Rapid Research Pilot Program (RP2) showcased how successful projects can continue after funding ends. Many participants used their achievements from novel pilot studies to apply for more funding and expand their work. They also focused on sharing their results at events like conferences and in publications, showing their dedication to improving health equity in the future.

Key Takeaways for Future Public Health Emergencies

Building Strong Partnerships: More than half of the projects (65%) worked with community-based organizations. These partnerships helped them overcome challenges, reach a wider audience, and establish trust with the communities they served.

Tips for Better Collaboration:

- **Match resources with community needs:** Focus on what the community actually needs, rather than following a set plan.
- **Include community leaders:** Make sure community partners have a say in decisions about both research and healthcare projects.
- **Support long-term change:** Build resources and programs directly within the community to ensure their sustainability. Big organizations may not always remain involved, but local groups are a constant presence.
- **Keep funding local:** Before giving money to outside groups, try to support local efforts first.
- **Plan for the future early:** Think about how the project will continue after funding ends. Projects that planned ahead were able to get more funding and keep growing. Include sustainability goals from the start and check on progress regularly.
- **Build relationships in the community around preparedness, and connect with local leaders:** Overall, partnerships with longer histories and more community connections were more likely to sustain their work.

Conclusion

RADx-UP made a significant impact in building strong partnerships that can help during future public health emergencies. During the COVID-19 emergency, it connected communities with public health agencies and provided data showing how CEnR can effectively support underserved groups during a crisis.

The program's results showed that while funding problems could make it difficult for some projects to continue, many activities are ready to proceed. About 28% of projects that worked to make COVID-19 testing more accessible plan to keep offering testing. Around 70% of projects plan to continue their community engagement work. Additionally, about one-third of the projects have already secured or are seeking new funding to continue providing essential health and social services to underserved communities. This shows a strong effort to maintain the progress made during the RADx-UP program.

The NIH and RADx-UP CDCC are committed to continuing the important work started by RADx-UP. The CDCC has helped projects expand their reach through new grants and has led efforts to develop strategies for lasting impact.

The playbook is designed to document and summarize the RADx-UP legacy and lessons of the program, which includes data, publications, and resources that will help in future public health emergencies. By collecting best practices, lessons learned, and successful strategies, the CDCC ensures that the benefits of RADx-UP will continue to make a lasting impact even after the program concludes.

Toolkit

1. FEATURED RADx-UP RESOURCES

Practical resources developed directly by the CDCC or RADx-UP projects. These may include publications, guides, or curated tools specific to implementing a program like the RADx-UP initiative.

- RADx-UP Strategic Roadmap
 - **A Strategic Roadmap: Advancing Health Equity through Community-engaged Research** — The CDCC asked members of the RADx-UP consortium how we could expand the community-engaged work of the RADx-UP program to address health disparities research in the U.S. beyond the COVID-19 pandemic. More than 100 members of the consortium shared valuable insights and experiences that informed them of the outlined strategic directions and themes. (See Appendix I.1)
 - **Strategic Roadmap Process** — Presentation explaining the process by which the strategic roadmap was developed. Demonstrates the rigor and inclusion that was built into the strategic roadmap creation process. (See Appendix I.2)

2. RELEVANT PUBLICATIONS

A list of publications, data sources, or scholarly work that support the evidence base and offer pathways for further reading.

- Israel BA, Schulz AJ, Parker EA, Becker AB. Review of community-based research: assessing partnership approaches to improve public health. *Annual Rev Public Health*. 1998;19(1):173-202.
- Quinsee S, Parker P. CIRCLE: a cyclical approach to stakeholder engagement for change management. In *Delivering Educational Change in Higher Education* (pp. 139-149). Routledge; 2020. [[Visit Website](#)]

CLOSING AND BEYOND

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The RADx-UP program was one of the most significant NIH-funded projects to use a community-engaged research approach to reduce health disparities during the COVID-19 pandemic. The results surpassed NIH expectations for the number of people getting involved, data collected, and new ideas and solutions created by communities in underserved areas and populations.

Outcomes and Achievements

The *RADx-UP Public Health Emergency Preparedness Playbook* is the culmination of an unprecedented nationwide effort to center and engage community members in underserved populations in every aspect of a public health crisis response. From the initial days of the COVID-19 pandemic, RADx-UP demonstrated that meaningful change in health equity is achievable when trust is prioritized, engagement is purposeful, and community-focused design takes precedence.

Here is a snapshot of the overall results:

More than 120 partnerships were created between community groups and academic institutions, focusing on teamwork in locations such as rural towns, small cities, and places often left out of research collaborations. These partnerships weren't just for show; they brought real care and action.

RADx-UP helped with testing, education, and outreach that connected people across different regions and backgrounds, directly involving nearly 900,000 participants. Over 60 million pieces of data were collected, creating one of the most detailed collections of information about how underserved communities dealt with the pandemic. These data have been used to guide decisions at both local and national levels. The RADx-UP CDCC, led by DCRI, UNC, and CCPH, coordinated efforts to share information and keep communities involved.

The RADx-UP consortium published over 370 research papers, presented at more than 400 conferences, and generated bilingual and culturally responsive materials to help communities stay informed and involved. These partnerships also created new opportunities and solutions, bringing different groups together to solve health challenges as a team.

The Impact

This playbook was created to share the most useful tools and resources developed by the RADx-UP team and to make sure they reach the people who need them most.

The main goals were:

- First, to show ways to quickly and effectively respond to public health emergencies while focusing on equity and including underserved communities.
- Second, to give important resources and findings to help guide future community involvement in research and public health projects.
- Third, to highlight a community-based research model that includes the voices and needs of underserved groups in decisions.

It is our hope that this playbook inspires changes in policies and systems to better support health equity for everyone.

As Dr. Eliseo Pérez-Stable, Director of the National Institute on Minority Health and Health Disparities (NIMHD) from 2015–2025, noted, ***“The scientists need to be engaged with the community ... shoulder to shoulder with our community organizations.”*** This principle guided every element of RADx-UP, from how studies were designed to how results were interpreted and used.

“The scientists need to be engaged with the community ... shoulder to shoulder with our community organizations.”

DR. ELISEO PÉREZ-STABLE
Director of the National Institute on Minority Health and Health Disparities (NIMHD) from 2015–2025

PHOTO COURTESY RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

The voices of community members, research teams, faith leaders, and local health workers illustrate the rich ecosystem of partnerships that made this work real and relevant. Their experiences helped shape a new standard for community-engaged research, and their stories will continue to inform the national dialogue on equity, trust, and accountability.

The playbook illustrates the lasting effects of the RADx-UP program and highlights how the work of RADx-UP can continue to enrich the environment for discovery and learning through including community voices, giving underserved populations a bigger role, sparking national conversations about community-based research, and inspiring new programs and ideas to make health equity a reality for everyone.

“The future will include research strategies that prioritize community collaborators and partners,” said Dr. Monica Webb Hooper, Deputy Director of NIMHD from 2020–2025 and now interim Director of NIMHD at the time of playbook publication. This prioritization of community participation is not simply an ideal — it is a necessity. The RADx-UP model makes it clear that equity cannot be achieved without structural transformation, and that transformation starts by reimagining who holds power in public health research and how that power is shared.

The lessons outlined in the playbook are intended to inform the public about emergency preparedness and promote purposeful representation of underserved populations in decision-making and policy development, with the ultimate goal of saving lives.

“The future will include research strategies that prioritize community collaborators and partners.”

DR. MONICA WEBB HOOPER
Deputy Director of NIMHD
from 2020–2025

How to Use and Share the Playbook

During the COVID-19 Public Health Emergency, people and organizations that rarely worked together came together to respond. RADx-UP community leaders emphasized that every community has its own unique networks. A key question to ask is:

“WHERE DO PEOPLE GO TO GET EMERGENCY INFORMATION?”

The answer often isn't a government website—it might be a trusted community leader or local doctor.

To make the most of the playbook, start by identifying and reaching out to your own trusted networks. This playbook is both a resource and a starting point for planning. Local health departments, community organizations, researchers, and funders are encouraged to adapt and use it in ways that fit their specific needs.

The playbook—and all linked document resources—will be hosted on the [NIH RADx® Data Hub](#), where they will remain freely accessible to serve as a tool for equity-centered planning and response.

Also included in the playbook's appendix are **five one-page user guides** (See Appendix J for each) intended to help share the playbook with different audiences.

THEME	TARGET AUDIENCE
Engagement Foundations & Best Practices (See Appendix J.1)	Public Health Agencies, CBOs, Nonprofits
Tailoring Outreach for Different Stakeholders (See Appendix J.2)	Local and State Government, Policymakers, Funders
Building & Sustaining Community Partnerships (See Appendix J.3)	Healthcare Organizations, Advocacy Groups, Research Institutions
Effective Communication & Messaging Strategies (See Appendix J.4)	Communications Teams, Media, Social Impact Groups
Evaluation & Impact Measurement (See Appendix J.5)	Program Managers, Grant Administrators, Funders

“Public health emergencies demand professionalism, cultural sensitivity, efficiency, rich and resilient alliances across sectors. The RADx-UP Coordination and Data Collection Center and the RADx-UP projects set a high standard for community engagement and sustained research collaboration”

DOROTHY CASTILLE, PHD

Training Coordinator and Senior Program Official, National Institute on Minority Health and Health Disparities (NIMHD)

The RADx-UP Pandemic Preparedness Playbook was made possible thanks to the dedication, teamwork, and valuable insights of many individuals and organizations involved in its creation.

This playbook stands as proof of what can be achieved when communities are prioritized, equity is embraced, and partnerships lead the way.

PHOTO COURTESY RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

When community is at the center, preparedness becomes more than a plan—it becomes a promise.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

PHOTO COURTESY RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

The playbook was created by the partners who make up the RADx-UP CDCC—Duke Clinical Research Institute (DCRI), Community-Campus Partnerships for Health (CCPH), and the University of North Carolina—in collaboration with a playbook task force representing diverse contributors and beneficiaries of this material. The development was funded as part of NIH emergency cooperative agreement 1U24MD016258. The content is solely the responsibility of the authors and does not necessarily represent the official views of the NIH.

The RADx-UP CDCC thanks community partners and organizations across the country for their courage, trust, and creativity. Their experiences, local knowledge, and strength were key to this effort. Thanks also go to the National Institute on Minority Health and Health Disparities (NIMHD) for their leadership, vision, and support throughout the RADx-UP project.

The CDCC's three partner organizations, dedicated staff, and many local and national collaborators worked hard to make this playbook possible. Their teamwork helped create a resource that is both accurate and meaningful. Special thanks are also shared with those behind the scenes—communications teams, evaluators, organizers, and others—who made sure every part of the project showed the best work and shared purpose.

Lastly, the CDCC is grateful for the generosity of the photographers and community models involved in the creation of the RADx-UP Image Bank, whose work and likeness is featured throughout the playbook.

RADx-UP CDCC Partners:

DUKE CLINICAL RESEARCH INSTITUTE (DCRI)

The DCRI, affiliated with Duke University, is a leading academic research organization focused on advancing clinical and translational research to improve patient care. Established in 1996, DCRI conducts innovative clinical trials and collaborates with industry, government, and healthcare partners. Committed to education and mentorship, DCRI also plays a key role in training future leaders in clinical research.

COMMUNITY-CAMPUS PARTNERSHIPS FOR HEALTH (CCPH)

CCPH is an international, nonprofit membership organization that supports individuals and organizations in their efforts to form authentic, equitable partnerships, which in turn allow the pursuit of policy, practice, and systems-level changes that will support the health of our communities and eliminate health disparities.

UNIVERSITY OF NORTH CAROLINA AT CHAPEL HILL (UNC-CH)

UNC and its partner affiliates at Abacus Evaluation bring together multidisciplinary teams of stakeholder communities from academia, healthcare, and industry with a shared commitment to innovation, health, and well-being for everyone.

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Playbook Contributing Authors:

This talented RADx-UP legacy planning and writing team brought a wealth of knowledge and diverse perspectives to the playbook. Their collaboration and commitment have been crucial in developing a valuable resource designed to help communities and public health organizations effectively respond to future public health emergencies.

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